

Bahir Dar University
College of Science
Department of Physics

Investigating Troposphere Lower Stratosphere Dynamics over Tropical
and subtropical region Using Ground Based and Satellite Data

By

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Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

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and subtropical region Using Ground Based and Satellite Data

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A Dissertation Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D)
in Atmospheric Physics

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Declaration

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**Investigating Troposphere Lower Stratosphere Dynamics over Tropical and subtropical region Using Ground Based and Satellite Data**”, submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Atmospheric Physics in Department of Physics, Bahir Dar University, is a record of original work carried out by me and has never been submitted to this or any other institution to get any other degree or certificates. The assistance and help I received during the course of this investigation have been duly acknowledged.

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Approval of Dissertation

I hereby certify that I have supervised, read, and evaluated this dissertation entitled **“Investigating Troposphere Lower Stratosphere Dynamics over Tropical and subtropical region Using Ground Based and Satellite Data”** by Tsehaye Negash Gebreteklie prepared under my guidance. I recommend the dissertation be submitted for oral defense.

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Abstract

This dissertation investigates the complicated troposphere-lower stratosphere (TLS) region, with an emphasis on trace gas transport across the tropical tropopause and how it affects climate and weather systems. There is a paucity of extensive research on the spatial and temporal variations of TLS temperature over tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt using numerous data sources, despite earlier research on natural influences. This study analyzes long-term trends in TLS temperature from 2006 to 2020 by utilizing both ground-based and COSMIC satellite data, focusing on TLS variability and its influencing drivers through wavelet analysis and multivariate linear regression methods. It also examines Kelvin wave patterns observed from 2019 to 2020 using Radiosonde and AIRS satellite datasets, along with the exchange of trace gases ozone and water vapor in the UTLS region.

Our study demonstrates that the tropopause height decreases from the tropics to the subtropics with a slight increase in temperature. The tropical station Addis is located at 17 km and has a temperature of 190-194 K, while the subtropical Cairo is located at 15 km and has a temperature of 201 K. Morlet wavelet analysis applied to cold point tropopause temperature (CPTt) exhibits AO and cold point tropopause height (CPT_h) exposes QBO-like signal patterns. An investigation of the response to natural drivers such as ENSO, SF, QBO, IOD, and aerosols on temperature variability reveals positive peaks at various altitudes. Lag analysis indicates delays in natural forcing effects, revealing a warming trend in the tropospheric region and a cooling trend in the upper troposphere lower stratosphere (UTLS) region identified through multiple linear regression trend analysis. The tropical Addis station has the highest cooling rate of -0.38 K/decade at 12 km and the highest warming rate of 0.28 K/decade at 3 km, to the subtropical Cairo station, which has the highest warming rate of 0.38 K/decade at 2 km and the maximum cooling rate of -0.2 K/decade at 10 km.

Further studies explores the activity of Kelvin wave (KW), focusing on their distinctive features such as periodicity and vertical wavelenghts in tropical and subtropical regions. This analysis uses longitude-time and altitude-time data sourced from RS and AIRS satellite observations, covering the period from March 2019 to February 2020 in the TLS region. In Addis, KW periodicity ranges from 9.2 to 14.5 days with vertical wavelenghts of 3.8 to 12.5 km, while in Cairo, it ranges from 6.4 to 13.3 days with vertical wavelenghts of 6 to 11.2 km. KW shows pronounced downward propagation, especially in summer, with maximum amplitudes of 8 K in Ethiopia and 4 K in

Egypt. This suggests that the KW exponentially decreases as it moves from the tropics to the subtropics. The study finds strong correlations between tropopause height and KW is 0.86 and gravity waves with tropopause height is 0.48. High KW activity is linked to low Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR) values, indicating significant convective activity during summer KW events.

Our study further focus on the roles of trace gases such as water vapor and ozone in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS), as well as their impact on climate change. Ozone distribution remains stable in the UTLS, except during spring in Ethiopia and autumn in Egypt. The transport of ozone and water vapor across the tropopause is controlled by the cold-point tropopause height (CPT_h) and temperature (CPT_t), respectively. In Egypt, the annual mean ozone volume mixing ratio (OVMR) ranges from 6 to 9 ppmv, while in Ethiopia, it ranges from 6 to 10 ppmv. Water vapor mixing ratio (WVMR) peaks at 600-400 ppmv in Ethiopia and 200-100 ppmv in Egypt. Egypt has a higher ozone mass flux (5 kg/s) compared to Ethiopia (3.4 kg/s), while Ethiopia has a higher water vapor mass flux (68 kg/s) compared to Egypt (30 kg/s). The study also identifies semi-annual oscillation (SAO) in WVMR and annual oscillation (AO) in OVMR in Ethiopia, and triannual oscillation (TAO) in WVMR and AO in OMR in Egypt.

Publications

1. **Tsehaye**, & U.Prakash Raju (2024). Study on Long Term Troposphere lower stratosphere Temperature (TLST) trend in tropical and subtropical Northern hemisphere Using ground based and COSMIC Satellite data. published in the Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2024.106306>.
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Dedication

This dissertation is dedicated to all my family members to my mother, my sisters, and my brothers.

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Acronyms

AO	Annual Oscillation
AM	Ante meridiem
AMSU	Advanced microwave sounding unit
AIRS	Atmospheric Infrared Sounder
BDC	Brewer–Dobson Circulation
BP	Back propagation
COSMIC	Constellation observation system for meteorology, ionospheric and climate constellation
COT	Convective heating region
CSRT	Clear sky radiative tropopause
CFCs	Chlorofluorocarbons
CESM	Community Earth System
CMAM	Canadian Middle Atmospheric Model
CPT _h	Cold point Tropopause height
CPT _t	Cold Point Tropopause temperature
CT	Canonical transform
CFH	Cryogenic frost point hygrometer
CALIPSO	Cloud aerosol lidar and infrared pathfinder satellite observations
CWT	Continuous wavelet transform
CrIS	Cross–track infrared sounder
DU	Dobson Unit
DJF	December, January, and February
ECMWF	European centre for medium range weather forecasts
E	East
EW	Equatorial Wave
EUV	Extreme Ultraviolet
EOS	Earth observation satellite
ENSO	El Nino Southern Oscillation
FSI	Full spectrum inversion
FFT	Fast fourier transform
F10.7	Solar 10.7 cm Radio flux
GCOM	Global change observation mission
GPS	Global Position System
GPM	Global Positionig meteorology
GNSS–RO	Global Navigation Satellite System Radio Occultation
GW	Gravity Wave

GHG	Greenhouse gas
GRACE	Gravity Recovery and climate Experiment
GWPS	Global wavelet power spectrum
h	height
HIRS	High resolution infrared radiation sounder
HIRDLS	High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder
IOD	Indian Ocean Dipole
IR	Infrared
IPCC	International Panel on Climate Change
ITCZ	Intertropical Converge Zone
IGRA	Integrated global radiosonde archive
IOC	Initial Operational Capability
IASI	Infrared atmospheric sounding interferometer
JJA	Jun, July, and August
KW	Kelvin Wave
LRT	Lapse rate tropopause
LT	Lower troposphere
LEO	Low earth orbit
MT	Middle troposphere
MJO	Madden julian oscillation
MLR	Multiple Linear Regression
MLS	Multiple Limb Sounder
MCS	Master control station
MAM	March, April and May
NWP	Numerical weather prediction
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NSPO	National space organization
NH	Northern Hemisphere
NWP	Numerical weather prediction
N	North
NCEP	National Centers for environmental
n	Refractive index
OMR	Ozone mixing ratio
OMI	Ozone monitoring instrument
OH	Hydroxyl radical
OLR	Outgoing Longwave Radiation
ODs	Ozone depleting substances
PV	Potential Vorticity
P	Pressure

PM	Post meridiem
QBO	Quasi–Biennial Oscillation
RS	Radiosonde
RO	Radio Occultation
RTE	Radiative transfer equation
SF	Solar flux
STE	Stratosphere–Troposphere Exchange
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
SH	Southern Hemisphere
S	South
SAO	Semi–Annual Oscillation
SS	Sliding spectral
SON	September, October, and November
STJ	Subtropical jet stream
TLS	Troposphere–Lower Stratosphere
TLST	Troposphere–Lower Stratosphere Temperature
TTL	Tropical tropopause layer
TTT	Tropical thermal tropopause
TPL	Tropopause pressure level
TES	Tropospheric emissions spectrometer
TIP	Tiny Ionosphere photometer
T	Temperature
UTLS	Upper Troposphere–Lower Stratosphere
UV	Ultraviolet
USDoD	United states department of defense
UCAR	University corporation for atmospheric research
UT	Upper troposphere
WPS	Wavelet power spectrum
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
W	West

Chapter 1

Background of Study:

Troposphere lower stratosphere (TLS, surface to 30 km) is a complex region of the earth's surface, where the mixing of ozone (O_3) rich stratospheric air and humid (H_2O) tropospheric air takes place across the tropical tropopause (Holton et al., 1995). The tropopause is a stable layer that is created by natural atmospheric inversion. It regulates the vertical distributions of ozone, water vapor, aerosols, and other trace elements and sets the upper limit for cloud cover. TLS is highly dynamic region of the atmosphere is affected by deep convection, breaking gravity waves, and natural forcings, and interact with the surface and middle atmosphere. Several prominent long term and short term atmospheric oscillations, including El Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO), 11-year solar flux (SF), Quasi Biennial Oscillation (QBO), aerosol, and oceanic influences such as IOD, Annual Oscillation (AO) and semiannual Oscillation (SAO), have a strong influence on the variability in TLS temperature. TLS temperature variation in the tropics is known to be significantly influenced by ENSO episodes, which are characterized by a cooling of the lower stratosphere coupled with an increase in moist convection and a warming of the SST (Avery et al., 2017) and also ENSO is a dominant mode of the inter-annual variability of the TLS region (Philander et al., 1989).

The QBO, characterized by alternating easterly and westerly winds in the equatorial stratosphere, strongly affects vertical momentum transfer and wave propagation. It modulates planetary waves and atmospheric circulation, impacting TLS temperature variability at multiple levels (Dunkerton, 1997; Holton and Tan, 1980). The solar flux indices (SF) (F10.7 index) shows variations in solar activity which affect TLS dynamics. Changes in solar radiation can alter atmospheric circulation patterns. This has the potential to affect TLS related weather and climate trends (Warren et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2022). Studying the IOD in the TLS involves examining its impact on atmospheric dynamics and ozone variability. Australia experiences severe droughts and heavy rainfall due to the high temperatures along Africa's coast during the IOD's positive phase. Increased risks of coastal flooding and its effects are another consequence of the IOD-related sea level fluctuations. Numerous scientists and organizations study the IOD and how it affects the TLS (Kumar et al., 2020; Nath et al., 2024). Studying atmospheric aerosols in the TLS often understand the sources, transport, and impacts of aerosols on climate, air quality, and human health

(Chin et al., 2016). In addition to natural atmospheric forcing seasonal oscillations (AO and SAO) also affect TLS region. SAO and AO are well-known atmospheric oscillations in the TLS regions, and they are important drivers of intra-annual fluctuations. The moist process and dynamic heating are the main drivers of the SAO in the TLS region (Shangguan and Wang, 2022). The main cause of the AO in the TLS region is primarily related to thermal fluctuations and Earth's orbit around the Sun, leading to seasonal variations in temperature, pressure, and other atmospheric parameters (Baldwin et al., 1994).

Apart from natural factors such as environmental forcing and seasonal oscillations, the TLS dynamics also affected by atmospheric waves, including Kelvin and gravity waves. Gravity waves that originate in the troposphere have the ability to reach the tropopause and impact the stratospheric ozone layer over a period of many hours to days (Langford et al., 1996). The study conducted by Kim (2015) investigated the impact of gravity waves on the transportation and deposition of ice crystals into the TLS region. Additionally, the study examined the changes in cold point temperature (CPT) caused by these gravity waves. Atmospheric waves in the equatorial region are mainly generated by convection. Kelvin waves are an important mode of short time scale variability in the tropical TLS region. Kelvin waves in the troposphere are convectively coupled and can be observed through outgoing longwave radiation and albedo. In the stratosphere, these waves become free traveling waves with significant temperature amplitudes (Wallace and Gousky, 1968), making them easily detectable in temperature data. The propagation of Kelvin waves is strongly influenced by variations in static stability and zonal wind. Temperature trends help scientists track global warming and its impacts. Rising temperatures in the troposphere and cooling in the stratosphere are indicators of climate change driven by greenhouse gases (Seidel et al., 2011). Temperature trends in the stratosphere affect the ozone layer. Cooling in the stratosphere can slow down ozone depletion, while warming can accelerate it. Bencherif et al. (2006) examined long-term climatology and climate change using 22 years of radiosonde and ECMWF reanalysis data over the southern hemisphere. The average temperature trends for the troposphere and stratosphere are, respectively, -0.08 to 0.28 and -1.08 to -0.44 . The TLS region has been studied using ground-based Radiosonde (RS) data (Seidel et al., 2004), model data (Gettelman and Birner, 2007) and COSMIC satellite data (He et al., 2009). The examination of TLS dynamics is aided by the extended period of global data with strong spatial and temporal resolutions provided by COSMIC satellite observations (Kishore et al., 2009; Negash and Raju, 2024). Using data obtained from radiosondes (Seidel et al., 2001), a few studies on tropopause height and its climatology have been reported with respect to sub-tropical latitudes. Kelvin waves have been identified in

the troposphere lower stratosphere using COSMIC (Randel and Wu, 2005) and AIRS (Flannaghan and Fueglistaler, 2012). According to Dobson et al. (1929), the tropics are expected to have a higher concentration of ozone, making it the primary photochemical source region. Brewer (1949) conducted measurements of water vapor using a frost-point hygrometer and found that the air over the mid-latitude stratosphere was extremely dry. These observations by Brewer marked the beginning of the study of the STE and provided further evidence of a global-scale meridional circulation in the stratosphere, now known as the Brewer-Dobson circulation (BDC). The BDC is a global-scale meridional mass circulation process in which tropical air crosses the tropical tropopause, ascends, and then moves towards the poles before descending into the middle and high latitudes of the Earth. An examination of the literature revealed that there are no publications on TLS regions of temperature trend, Kelvin wave analysis, and trace gas exchanges over the tropical region Ethiopia and the subtropical region Egypt. This dissertation is to link the tropical and subtropical TLS region using long-term ground based and satellite data, to estimate temperature trends by accounting for natural periodic effect. Moreover previous researchers concentrates on $5^{\circ}N$ - $5^{\circ}S$ belt of kelvin wave observations, we extended this narrow latitudinal belt for tropical (0 - $15^{\circ}N$) and (22 - $35^{\circ}N$) regions.

1.1 Statement of Problem

The Tropical Lower Stratosphere (TLS) is a complex and dynamic region of Earth's atmosphere, where key processes such as trace gas exchange, atmospheric oscillations, and wave dynamics play a pivotal role in influencing global climate, weather patterns, and air quality. The key drivers of temperature trends in the tropical region Ethiopia and subtropical region Egypt in the TLS regions are multifaceted, involving a combination of natural (ENSO, QBO, SF, and IOD) and anthropogenic factors. Although previous studies have extensively examined Kelvin waves, there is a lack of research on their behavior in subtropical regions. This study seeks to address this deficiency by exploring Kelvin wave characteristics in Ethiopia and Egypt. The findings enhance our understanding of how atmospheric waves interact with tropopause dynamics and contribute to broader atmospheric oscillations. An examination of the literature revealed that there are no publications on TLS regions of temperature trend, Kelvin wave analysis, and trace gas trace gas exchanges over the tropical region Ethiopia and the subtropical region Egypt, which motivates the need for this study. Our study is pioneering in linking the tropical and subtropical TLS regions using long term ground based and satellite data. Moreover previous researchers concentrates on $5^{\circ}N$ - $5^{\circ}S$ belt of kelvin wave observations, we extended this narrow latitudinal belt for tropical (0 - $15^{\circ}N$) and subtropical (22 - $35^{\circ}N$) regions. This dissertation addresses this gap through observational and analytical approaches, offering valuable insights into

this highly dynamic region. In this dissertation the following questions are answered:

- What are the key drivers of temperature trends in the TLS in the tropical and subtropical Northern Hemisphere?
- Are kelvin waves prevailing at sub tropical regions, if so which waves are (either kelvin or gravity waves) shown major influence on tropical and subtropical tropopause?
- How does the exchange of ozone and water vapor between the troposphere and stratosphere influences the TLS region over tropical and subtropical regions?

The following objectives were designed to solve the aforementioned problems.

1.2 Objectives of the study

1.2.1 General Objective

The main objective of the study is to investigate troposphere and lower stratosphere thermal interactions over tropical and subtropical northern hemispheres using ground based and satellite data.

1.2.2 Specific Objective

The specific objective of this thesis is:

- To investigate Long Term Troposphere and lower stratosphere Temperature (TLST) trend in tropical and subtropical Northern hemisphere by considering natural drivers (periodic oscillations).
- Observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data.
- To study Troposphere–stratosphere trace gases (ozone and water vapour) exchange in UTLS region over tropical and subtropical regions.

1.3 Significance of study

The main advantage of TLS study is crucial for weather prediction and climate modelling, air quality and pollution monitoring, ozone layer protection, aviation and flight safety, and space exploration. The TLS studies are crucial for aviation department as the exact identification of altitude of tropospheric turbulence/eddy layers and jet streams which will affect accuracy of numerical weather prediction and climate models. Temperature change in TLS is an important component of climate change, so the decision makers to take pay attention has been extensively studied. The study

provides a detailed analysis of long term temperature trends, natural oscillations, and wave dynamics (Kelvin and Gravity waves) in the TLS region. The findings contribute to understanding the impacts of climate change, such as tropospheric warming and stratospheric cooling, and their implications for the ozone layer, weather systems, and global energy balance.

1.4 Dissertation Structure

The dissertation organized as follows: **Chapter 1:** Provides a general introduction to the thermal structure and chemical composition of the Earth's atmosphere. The significance of the research, statement of the problem and motivation, objective of the study, and thesis structure were explained. **Chapter 2:** Offers an overview of Earth's atmospheric system, focusing on its thermal structure and variability influenced by atmospheric waves and oscillations. It examines the thermodynamics of the dry atmosphere, dynamics of the tropopause, and variability of the tropopause on seasonal and interseasonal timescales, including tropical and subtropical regions. Additionally, the chapter addresses atmospheric radiative processes and the exchange between the troposphere and lower stratosphere. **Chapter 3:** details the instruments, datasets, methodologies, and analysis techniques employed in the thesis. It also includes a brief explanation of the methodology used for detecting temperature measurements with the COSMIC RO technique. **Chapters 4–6** outline the specifics of each objective addressed in the investigations, detailing the approaches and findings related to those goals as follows: Study on Long Term Troposphere lower stratosphere Temperature (TLST) trend in tropical and subtropical Northern hemisphere Using ground based and COSMIC Satellite data is presented in **Chapter 4**. **Chapter 5** deals with Observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data. Investigation of the role of trace gases exchange from Troposphere to lower stratosphere in tropical and subtropical region using MLS satellite is discussed in **Chapter 6**. Finally, **Chapter 7** of the dissertation summarizes the conclusions and offers recommendations for future research directions.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Background

The Earth's atmosphere is very important for the existence of life on Earth as it absorbs the high energy ultraviolet and x-ray solar radiation from entering the Earth's surface. The medium for life on Earth is the fluid atmosphere. It is made up of gases, primarily oxygen and nitrogen molecules, and extends from the Earth's surface to the upper boundary, which is typically understood to be the highest point that rotates in tandem with the planet. Weather and climate change as a result of constant energy exchange between space and the atmosphere on Earth's surface. The Earth-atmosphere system, on average, reflects roughly 30% of the incoming solar radiation to the top of the atmosphere, with the Earth's surface absorbing 51% and the atmosphere absorbing 19%. In order to keep the energy balance, the Earth's surface and atmosphere reemit the energy that has been received as long wave or thermal infrared radiation into space. Even though the Earth's atmosphere is in a state of global energy balance, atmospheric transport mechanisms are triggered by localized radiation imbalances. The energy that is received and re-emitted is what drives the dynamics of the atmosphere at all sizes, from micro to planetary. Therefore, a full understanding of the thermal structure, composition, and dynamics of the Earth's atmosphere is necessary.

2.1 Atmospheric Thermal structure

Temperature variation determines the names of the several regions that make up the neutral atmosphere. The troposphere (0–15 km), stratosphere (15–50 km), and mesosphere (50–90 km) are the three zones that make up the neutral atmosphere. The terms tropopause, stratopause, and mesopause respectively, refer to the borders of these regions.

2.1.1 Troposphere

The troposphere which translates from Greek to mean "turning or changing layer" is the lowest layer of the Earth, where temperature drops with altitude. This layer ranges in depth from roughly 6 to 17 km. The tropics, where warm temperatures force the lower atmosphere to expand vertically, are where the greatest depths are found. The troposphere increasingly thins as one moves from the tropics to the polar regions of Earth. Figure 2.1 shows that the troposphere's average depth is roughly 11 kilometers. The troposphere contains about 80% of the atmosphere's total mass.

Figure 2.1: Vertical thermal structure of the atmosphere to a height of about 100 km an illustrative diagram.

Additionally, most of our weather occurs in this stratum. In this layer, the maximum air temperature also happens close to the Earth's surface. Because infrared radiation decreases as one ascends above the earth's surface, air temperature falls consistently with altitude at a rate of around 6.5°C per kilometer. This is known as the zone of negative lapse rate. The Environmental Lapse Rate is a term used to describe this phenomena. The top of the troposphere is reached when the temperature reaches an average of -56.5°C . The tropopause, a tiny transition zone where the temperature gradient is constant, is located at the upper boundary of the troposphere. Most of the fluctuations in the local weather are caused by active convection, which is common in this unstable location.

2.1.2 Stratosphere

The stratosphere is located above the tropopause. It is a sensitive part of the climate system that can influence the troposphere through coupling mechanisms. Warmer, lighter air is layered on top of denser, cooler air in this stratified layer. As a result, the temperature rises with height. Most aircraft choose to fly in the stratosphere because it is less turbulent than other places. This layer, which ranges in average height from 11 to 50 km above the surface of the Earth, makes up 19.9 % of the atmosphere's total mass. The thermal energy produced by these molecules' absorption of UV light warms the stratosphere. In recent years, there has been increased attention on determining the long-term trend in stratopause temperature due to stratospheric ozone depletion.

2.1.3 Mesosphere

Directly above the stratosphere and below the thermosphere lies the mesosphere. It stretches between 50 and 85 kilometers above Earth. Over the mesosphere, temperature drops with height. The lower temperatures are caused by the mesosphere's extremely low quantities of ozone and water vapor in comparison to lower locations. There is relatively little pressure. The level of the atmosphere that typically has the lowest temperatures is called the mesopause. However, the mesopause's temperature can fluctuate greatly, falling as low as 150 K. The mesosphere's temperature decreases with altitude due to a decrease in the absorption of penetrating solar radiation. This is where noctilucent clouds can occasionally form, which then absorb and reflect solar energy to alter the Earth's temperature.

2.2 Thermodynamics of Dry Atmosphere

Dynamics of the troposphere and stratosphere are fundamentally inseparable. However, the mechanism involved in the generation and maintenance of the circulation in the troposphere and stratosphere are different. Large-scale circulation in the troposphere is primarily driven by the differential absorption of solar energy at the surface, whereas in the stratosphere, eddies are as fundamental to the circulation as the differential solar heating. Waves and eddies play a major role in maintaining the global atmospheric circulation. The waves generated in the troposphere propagate into the stratosphere with absorption, so that stratospheric changes depend upon where and how they are absorbed, and in turn these changes can affect the troposphere. Without eddies the zonal mean temperature would match the radiative equilibrium temperature with a ~ 10 – 20 day lag, and would vary annually. Heating and cooling patterns result from eddies driving the stratosphere away from radiative equilibrium.

2.2.1 Hydrostatic balance

If atmosphere is static or at rest, the air pressure at any level depends on the weight of the fluid lying above that level. Therefore, the atmospheric pressure decreases with increasing altitude above the Earth's surface. The rate at which the atmospheric pressure or density decreases with altitude can be inferred from the hydrostatic balance. Consider an air mass lying between heights z and $z + dz$ as shown in Figure 2.2. The vertical pressure gradient acting on the air mass is $\frac{\partial p}{\partial z}$. The weight of the air mass per unit area is ρg . Under hydrostatic equilibrium, the vertical pressure gradient force (also known as the buoyancy force) is balanced by the body force (gravity force). The hydrostatic equation can be written as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = -\rho g \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 2.2: Balance between upward buoyancy force and downward gravity force maintaining the hydrostatic equilibrium.

where ∂p is the decrease in pressure with the small change in altitude ∂z , ρ is the air density and g is the acceleration due to gravity. The minus sign in the equation 2.1 indicates that, as the altitude increases, the air pressure decreases. In most of the case atmosphere can be approximated to hydrostatic balance, but this balance does not occurs when significant vertical accelerations are present, especially during the time of intense thunderstorms and cyclones. Most of the vertical mixing in the atmosphere, between few centimeters above the Earths surface and levels below the tropopause, is attained by the interchange of macroscale air parcels. An air parcel can be considered as air placed in an imaginary thin, flexible balloon-like wrap with horizontal dimension varying from millimeters to planetary scale.

2.2.2 Dry adiabatic balance

While undergoing an adiabatic process, ideal gas expands or compresses without any heat exchange with the surroundings. An adiabatic expansion decreases the internal energy of the system and results in cooling. On the other hand, an adiabatic compression increases the internal energy of the system and results in warming. In an atmosphere which obeys hydrostatic equilibrium, the lapse rate of a parcel of dry air that experiences only adiabatic changes (being raised or lowered in the atmosphere) can be derived from the first law of thermodynamics and the hydrostatic equation as given by equation 2.2

$$\left(\frac{dT}{dz}\right)_{dryparcel} = \frac{g}{c_p} = \Gamma_d \quad (2.2)$$

where Γ_d is the dry adiabatic lapse rate and c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure. By substituting the values of g and c_p , numerical value of dry adiabatic lapse rate can be obtained as 9.8 Kkm^{-1} . The measurement of actual temperature lapse rate (e.g., from radiosonde) generally provides a mean value of $6-7 \text{ Kkm}^{-1}$ in the troposphere, which is known as environmental lapse rate (Γ).

2.2.3 Potential Temperature

Potential temperature (θ) is an important conserved quantity during adiabatic displacement of an unsaturated air parcel. It is defined as the temperature that a parcel of dry air at pressure p and temperature T would have if it is brought adiabatically to a standard pressure of p_o , which is normally taken as 1000 hPa. From first law of thermodynamics, the expression for potential temperature can be derived as given in equation (2.3).

$$\theta = T \left(\frac{p_o}{p} \right)^{\frac{R}{C_p}} \quad (2.3)$$

This expression is known as Poisson's equation. Where, T and p are the initial temperature and pressure of the parcel of air, p_o is the standard pressure level (1,000 hPa), R is the universal gas constant, and C_p is the specific heat constant. Generally atmospheric processes are close to adiabatic and thus θ remains constant and significant in thermodynamics of the atmosphere. Vertical gradient of θ is a measure of stratification of the air. If θ increases (decreases) with altitude air is said to be stably (negatively) stratified. If θ remains constant with altitude, then air is said to be neutrally stratified. In the stratosphere, θ increases with altitude making it a stably stratified region. Potential temperature is conserved when there are no diabatic effects.

2.2.4 Stability of the atmosphere

A measure of the extent to which the atmosphere resists turbulence and vertical motion is generally termed as atmospheric stability. The thermal structure of the atmosphere plays a crucial role in determining static stability, which in turn influences various dynamical features in the atmosphere. It describes whether a displaced parcel of air returns to its original position or not. This depends on the values of Γ and Γ_d . By differentiating Poisson's equation and using hydrostatic and state equations, we have

$$\Gamma = \Gamma_d - \frac{T}{\theta} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial z} \quad (2.4)$$

The stability of the atmosphere can be assessed by the three conditions.

1. $\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial z} > 0$, then $\Gamma < \Gamma_d$, Statically stable

Figure 2.3: Potential Temperature.

2. $\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial z} = 0$, then $\Gamma = \Gamma_d$, Neutrally stable
3. $\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial z} < 0$, then $\Gamma > \Gamma_d$, Unstable stratification

Where, Γ is environmental lapse rate, and Γ_d is dry adiabatic lapse rate. If $\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial z} > 0$, then $\Gamma < \Gamma_d$, so the atmosphere is statically stable. In this case an adiabatic ascent of a parcel of air, which is cooler than the environment, will return to its original position. When, $\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial z} = 0$, then $\Gamma = \Gamma_d$, and the atmosphere is neutrally stable. The lifted air parcel of a dry air will occupy a new position, because the temperature of the parcel and the surrounding are the same. In the third condition, if $\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial z} < 0$, then $\Gamma > \Gamma_d$, which corresponds to an absolutely unstable stratification. In this case a dry air parcel lifted will always be warmer than the surroundings and move away from its original position, and is freely convective.

2.2.5 Brunt Vaisala Frequency

In a statically stable atmosphere, if a parcel is colder than its environment upon being lifted, it will be forced to move back downward to its original level once the impulse force is exhausted. The frequency of these buoyancy oscillations is termed Brunt–Vaisala frequency, which depends on the restoring force (the product of gravity and the density difference between the parcel and the environment) that acts on them. The buoyancy oscillations are the main reasons for waves in the atmosphere. The expression for Brunt–vaisala frequency can be written as

$$N = \left[\frac{g}{T}(\Gamma_d - \Gamma) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left[\frac{g}{\theta} \frac{\partial\theta}{\partial z} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.5)$$

Where, N is Brunt–vaisala frequency in s^{-1} and corresponding period is $\frac{2\pi}{N}$. For average tropospheric conditions, $\sim 1.2 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$ so that the period of buoyancy oscillation

is about 8 minutes. Similarly, the value of N in the stratosphere is $\sim 2.2 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$, the period of buoyancy oscillation is about 4 minutes. For a statically stable atmosphere ($\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial z} > 0$), $N > 0$ and buoyancy oscillations are generated. For the absolutely unstable case ($\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial z} < 0$), N is imaginary and corresponds to a growing disturbance. In the neutral case ($\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial z} = 0$), and $N = 0$, there is no buoyancy oscillations. Air parcels undergo buoyancy oscillations in association with atmospheric gravity waves (Nappo, 2012).

2.3 Dynamics of tropical and subtropical tropopause

The tropopause marks the transition between the well mixed troposphere and the stably stratified stratosphere. Over the past few decades, there has been a noticeable increase in tropopause height (decrease in tropopause pressure and temperature), which has been observed in the tropics (Seidel et al., 2001). In the tropics, exchange between the troposphere and the stratosphere is mainly determined by deep convection. Tropical cross tropopause transport is the main source of water vapor in the stratosphere and plays an important role in stratospheric chemistry and its radiative budget (Fueglistaler et al., 2009). The mass and energy exchange between the stratosphere and troposphere is also dependent on the tropopause's climatology (Holton et al., 1995). The following is a list of acronyms that are used to define tropopause.

Cold point tropopause (CPT): The troposphere's minimum temperature is found at the altitude known as the cold point tropopause (CPT).

Lapse rate tropopause (LRT): The lapse rate refers to the rate at which temperature decreases as altitude increases. In the troposphere the lapse rate is usually around $6.5^{\circ}C$.

Tropical thermal tropopause (TTT): LRT and CPT are typically less than 0.5 km apart in the tropics, with LRT being the lower. The TTT, which is normally between 16 and 17 km. Day-to-day variations in the tropopause height can also be caused by large-scale meteorological processes, such as low and high pressure systems.

The 100 mb surface: Tropopause level in the tropics, or 100 mb, is directly available from the model and is used as a proxy for the tropical tropopause (Mote et al., 1996). However, it should be emphasized that utilizing this 100 mb as a proxy for temperature minimums that occur above it can cause an overestimation of the minimum mixing ratio of water vapor saturation.

Ozonopause: The ozone content close to the tropopause serves as the basis for this

definition. Sharp positive gradients in the ozone mixing ratio (OMR) are a prominent characteristic in the upper troposphere during most seasons. The ozonopause, according to bet, is defined as the point at which OMR and its vertical gradient surpass 80 ppbv and 60 ppbv km^{-1} , respectively. The ozonopause is also defined as an OMR value threshold of 100 ppbv.

Hygropause: It is regarded as the point at which the least water vapor mixing ratio happens, either above or below the critical point (CPT) (kle).

Tropical tropopause layer (TTL): The tropical tropopause layer (TTL) is the zone that demonstrates tropospheric and stratospheric air properties. TTL's thickness, however, is dependent on the boundary definition because there isn't a generally accepted upper and lower limit (Gettelman et al., 2002b). In general, it is described as the area of the tropical atmosphere that is between the CPT (~ 17 km) and the top of the major cumulus outflow layer (~ 12 km). Tropopause can be vary thermally, dynamically and chemically.

2.3.1 Thermal Tropopause

The thermal tropopause is a region in the atmosphere where the environmental lapse rate changes from negative in the stratosphere to positive in the troposphere. It is also the altitude below which major weather disturbances occur, except for sporadic overshooting thunderstorms in tropical areas. The altitude of the tropopause varies, with it being around 17 km above the equator and approximately 9 km above the poles. The thermal tropopause exhibits interesting characteristics in terms of seasonal cycle, spatial distribution, interannual variation, and diurnal variation (Highwood et al., 2000).

2.3.2 Dynamical Tropopause

The tropopause is commonly defined in dynamical meteorology as an isosurface of potential vorticity (PV), typically found at about 2 PVU. This is because the stratosphere has significantly higher PV values compared to the troposphere. PV is conserved in adiabatic and frictionless flow, making it a reliable indicator of the boundary between the troposphere and stratosphere. The dynamical tropopause displays complex features such as folds and intrusions, which help in understanding atmospheric dynamics and weather patterns. On isentropic surfaces transitioning from the troposphere to the stratosphere, sharp PV gradients between the two air masses are usually observed (Hirschberg and Fritsch, 1991).

2.3.3 Chemical Tropopause

The chemical tropopause involves identifying the boundary based on the concentration of certain trace gases, such as ozone and water vapor. The chemical tropopause can be identified by a sharp increase in ozone concentration and a decrease in water vapor concentration as it moves from the troposphere to the stratosphere. As we go from the troposphere to the stratosphere, we can spot the tropopause by noticing a sudden increase in the concentration of ozone and a reduction in the concentration of water vapor. This chemical transition has consequences for atmospheric chemistry and climate research, and it is crucial for comprehending the gas exchange between these two atmospheric layers (Xian and Homeyer, 2019).

2.4 Tropopause relation with convection

Convection at the tropopause plays a significant role in atmospheric dynamics, particularly in the tropics. Convection in the troposphere is driven by warm air rising from the Earth’s surface. As the warm air rises, it cools, and when it reaches a certain altitude, it condenses into clouds. Deep convection events, like thunderstorms, have the ability to push the tropopause, thereby deepening the troposphere. Convection and outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) are closely related in the Earth’s atmosphere, especially in the context of weather systems and climate dynamics. OLR as a measure of convection strength. Meteorologists and climate scientists use OLR as an indirect measure of convective activity. Low OLR values correspond to regions with strong convection and thick cloud cover, while high OLR values indicate regions with little to no convection. Heat and moisture travel vertically due to convection, and the height and stability of the tropopause are impacted by strong convection. OLR affects the energy balance at the tropopause and is influenced by cloud cover due to convection. While changes in OLR and convection patterns affect the general structure and dynamics of the tropopause at different latitudes, low OLR in convective regions contributes to the maintenance of a cooler, more stable tropopause.

2.5 Tropopause variability due to intra and inter seasonal fluctuations

2.5.1 Intra Seasonal Tropopause Variation

Intra–annual tropopause fluctuation in the lower atmosphere detected in a brief period of time, which is controlled by SAO, AO, aerosol effect, IOD, EW, and GW, is particularly noticeable in tropical regions.

2.5.1.1 Annual Oscillation (AO)

The regular, yearly cycle of variations in the atmospheric condition is referred to as annual oscillation (AO). AO dominates the high latitude middle atmosphere, which can be attributed the annual cycle of solar insolation. In the northern hemisphere troposphere–stratosphere system, AO is the greatest and most fundamental mode of variability. The main cause of the annual oscillation (AO) in the troposphere and lower stratosphere is primarily related to thermal fluctuations and Earth's orbit around the Sun, leading to seasonal variations in temperature, pressure, and other atmospheric parameters (Hio and Hirota, 2002). The AO is also observed in general circulation models of the stratosphere–troposphere, and its trend suggests a potential connection to increases in greenhouse gases (Shindell et al., 1999). Kodera et al. (1999) demonstrated about how the downward propagation of stratospherically-derived zonal wind anomalies is linked to the establishment of an AO-like circulation in the troposphere. The study of the annual oscillation (AO) in the troposphere and lower stratosphere has been conducted by (Hio and Hirota, 2002). Additionally, Basha et al. (1999) has found that the AO dominates the troposphere, with maximum amplitude near 12–14 km.

2.5.1.2 Semiannual Oscillation(SAO)

Semiannual Oscillation (SAO) durations are approximately six months. SAO was initially detected in the lower atmosphere by Shangguan and Wang (2022) using temperature data collected by COSMIC and rocketsonde measurements. The amplitude of the surface-SAO can be affected by changes in the seasonal cycle of sea surface temperatures (SSTs), as surface-SAO is a connected ocean-atmosphere phenomenon. With two maxima in March and September close to the equinoxes, the temperature SAO over the middle troposphere in the SH was recorded by Van Loon (1967). A more thorough analysis of the tropical-subtropical SAO (TS-SAO) in the troposphere lower stratosphere was conducted by Shea et al. (1995).

2.5.1.3 Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD)

The Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) is an irregular oscillation of sea surface temperatures (SST) gradients between the western equatorial Indian ocean (50°E and 10°S – 10°N) and the south eastern equatorial Indian Ocean (90°E – 110°E and 10°S – 0°N). The warm phase of the IOD is present with higher sea levels in the western Indian Ocean and lower sea levels in the eastern Indian Ocean when the time series value is positive. Warm waters are forced into the western Indian Ocean during a positive phase, while cold, deep waters are raised to the surface in the eastern Indian Ocean (Ashok et al., 2003; Black et al., 2003). The patterns of rainfall and

high temperatures are inverted during a negative phase. Increased risks of coastal flooding and its effects are another consequence of the IOD-related sea level fluctuations. Numerous scientists and organizations study the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) and how it affects the troposphere and lower stratosphere (Kumar et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021).

2.5.1.4 Aerosol effect on the tropopause

Small airborne particles with a highly variable chemical makeup are known as atmospheric aerosols. The primary sources of anthropogenic aerosols are the combustion of biomass and fossil fuels. Aerosols can originate from natural sources or human activity. They also absorb, reflect, and scatter incoming solar radiation. The geochemical cycle and the global/regional climate system are significantly impacted by aerosols in the troposphere and lower stratosphere (TLS) (Borrmann et al., 1997; Hanson et al., 1994). Even though they happen seldom, volcanic eruptions can inject large amounts of ash and sulfur dioxide (SO_2) into the stratosphere, where homogeneous nucleation converts the injected SO_2 to sulfuric acid particles. Researchers studying atmospheric aerosols in the troposphere and lower stratosphere often understand the sources, transport, and impacts of aerosols on climate, air quality, and human health (Bourassa et al., 2012; Chin et al., 2016).

2.5.2 Short term tropopause variability due to wave activity

2.5.2.1 Gravity wave

The disturbance that moves energy from the troposphere into the stratosphere is called atmospheric wave. Gravity waves are generated by disturbances such as mountains, thunderstorms, wind shear activity, convective activity, and topographic activity. They propagate vertically and can transfer energy from the troposphere to the stratosphere, affecting weather and climate patterns. The emphasis after Holton and Lindzen (1972) was on broad scope gravity waves to supply the required momentum transmission. Atmospheric gravity waves are crucial for large-scale circulation, thermal structure, component distribution, and the movement of chemical constituents from the troposphere to the thermosphere (Lindzen and Holton, 1968; TJ, 1995). The atmospheric gravity waves assist in the transportation of atmospheric elements such as water vapor and affect the thermal structure of the tropopause (Yu et al., 2019). As the atmospheric density decreases exponentially, gravity waves (GWs) propagate upward and their amplitudes grow exponentially. Because of instability or critical level filtering, GWs break or disappear at higher altitudes (Fritts and Alexander, 2003). The tropopause fluctuations are closely linked to atmospheric waves, Particularly the effects of gravity waves. A fluid's stability to vertical displacements, in the

Figure 2.4: Dynamics of the troposphere–stratosphere–mesosphere exchange.

atmosphere, is measured by the Brunt–Vaisala frequency (N), sometimes referred to as the buoyancy frequency. It shows the rate of vertical oscillation of a displaced air parcel in a statically stable environment. The mathematical equation of the N can be expressed as:

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{\theta} \frac{d\theta}{dz} \quad (2.6)$$

Where θ is potential temperature, g is the acceleration due to gravity and z is the altitude. Since the potential temperature in the air parcel is

$$\theta = T \left(\frac{P_o}{P} \right)^{\frac{R}{c_p}} \quad (2.7)$$

Where P_o is a constant reference pressure, for a perfect gas this expression is equivalent to:

$$N^2 = g \left(\frac{1}{T} \frac{dT}{dz} - \frac{R}{c_p} \frac{1}{P} \frac{dP}{dz} \right) = g \left(\frac{1}{T} \frac{dT}{dz} - \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{1}{P} \frac{dP}{dz} \right) \quad (2.8)$$

Where in the last form $\gamma = \frac{c_p}{c_v}$ the adiabatic constant. Using the ideal gas law, we can eliminate the pressure of the air parcel to express N^2 in terms of temperature is:

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (2.9)$$

where $\Gamma_d = \frac{g}{c_p}$ is adiabatic lapse rate, c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure of the atmosphere and for this study 9.8×10^{-3} (K/m) lapse rate is adopted. The baseline temperature profile T and the fluctuation component T' make up the atmospheric temperature profile (T) from AIRS satellite, which is a function of height (h). The potential energy E_p has been used as a proxy for studying the gravity wave activities as presented by Tsuda et al. (2000) is given by:

$$E_p = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{g T'}{N T} \right)^2 \quad (2.10)$$

Where T' is temperature fluctuation, g is acceleration due to gravity, N is Brunt–Vaisala frequency and E_p is potential energy of the gravity wave. The potential energy that is utilized to determine how much the atmospheric gravity wave affects atmospheric dynamics.

2.5.2.2 Kelvin wave

Kelvin waves (KW) are eastward propagating Equatorial waves (EW) generated in the equatorial lower atmosphere and that is convectively coupled in the troposphere (Kiladis et al., 2009) and plays a significant role in the atmospheric and oceanic dynamics. They are mostly driven by the Sun through convective clouds close to the tropopause area, where they evaporate and then release latent heat. The Coriolis force confines KW to equatorial and low latitudes. Diabatic heating by organized tropical convection can excite atmospheric equatorial waves, which control the spatial and temporal distribution of convective heating (Dunkerton and Delisi, 1985). Theoretical description of planetary scale equatorial wave on an equatorial beta plane with the Coriolis parameter is:

$$f = \beta * y \quad (2.11)$$

Where y is meridional distance from the equator and β is the gradient of the coriolis parameter at the equator. The most well-known examples of equatorial waves are eastward propagating KW and westward propagating Rossby waves. These waves are usually observed as disturbances that either raise or lower the equatorial thermocline. These thermocline disturbances are mirrored by small anomalies in sea – level elevation, which offer a practical method for tracking these waves from space. The dispersion relation for frequency ω and wave number k

$$\omega^2 = g' H k^2 \quad (2.12)$$

and a first order ordinary differential equation for the meridional structure of b

$$\frac{db}{dy} = -\frac{\beta}{\omega}kyb \quad (2.13)$$

The only solution of this equation decaying for large y , called the kelvin wave solution is

$$b = b_o \exp\left(-\frac{\beta}{2c}\right)y^2 \exp i(kx - \omega t) \quad (2.14)$$

Where c is the phase speed and b_o is an arbitrary amplitude. The meridional scale with which these solutions decay away from the equator is the equatorial Rossby radius of deformation defined as

$$L_R = \left(\frac{c}{\beta}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.15)$$

Now let us look for the solutions that have nonzero meridional velocity v is

$$\frac{d^2}{dy^2}v + \left(\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} - k^2 - \frac{\beta k}{\omega} - \frac{\omega^2}{c^2}y^2\right)v = 0 \quad (2.16)$$

The solutions of the above that decay far away from the equator exist only when an important constraint connecting its coefficients is satisfied:

$$\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} - k^2 - \frac{\beta k}{\omega} = (2n + 1)\frac{\beta}{c} \quad (2.17)$$

A modified form of the general dispersion relation is needed for atmospheric kelvin waves, which inherently have no meridional motion. The resulting equation for ω takes the form:

$$\omega = kc \quad (2.18)$$

Where the phase speed $c = (g'H)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ Thus, the kelvin waves are eastward propagating (that means the bouyancy term ($c = (g'H)^{\frac{1}{2}}$) is positive, as well as k is positive, ω is positive, and the phase speed also positive the motion is along the positive x axis towards the east) ($\frac{\omega}{k} > 0$) and nondispersive. The KW vertical wavelengths were calculated using the following dispersion relation:

$$\lambda_z = \frac{2\pi}{N}\left(\frac{\lambda_x}{\tau} - \bar{U}\right) \quad (2.19)$$

Where, \bar{U} , N , τ , λ_x , and λ_z are velocity of mean zonal wind, bouyancy frequency, wave period (observed parameter), zonal wavelength, and vertical wavelength (observed parameter) respectively. N is approximately equal to 0.02 s^{-1} , zonal wavelength λ_x for wave number 1 is equivalent to 40,200 km, which is the circumference of the earths mean radius plus height from the surface, for wave number 2, λ_x is equivalent

to 20,100 km and \bar{U} is variant by time and altitude depending on the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO). According to monthly mean zonal wind data at Singapore, \bar{U} is approximately equal to -1.73 m/s, -1.63 m/s, 0.13 m/s, and 0.88 m/s during Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter respectively, where the minus sign indicates easterly.

2.5.3 Inter Seasonal temperature variation at tropopause

The tropopause height and structure exhibit significant inter-seasonal variations, influenced by factors like Quasibiennial Oscillation (QBO), El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO), and Solar 10.7 cm radio flux (F10.7).

2.5.3.1 Quasibiennial Oscillation (QBO)

A tropical phenomena known as the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO) is caused by winds that propagate eastward and westward lower in the equatorial stratosphere. The length of the QBO varies from 22 to 34 months, with an average of roughly 28 months. The majority of the momentum flux required to drive the QBO is now thought to be provided by a combination of smaller-scale gravity waves, Rossby gravity, inertia gravity, and kelvin (Dunkerton, 1997). The winter NH polar vortex tends to be small when the tropical lower stratospheric wind is easterly (EQBO) and powerful when the tropical lower stratospheric wind is westerly (WQBO). Numerous studies have examined the impact of the QBO on the troposphere (Gray et al., 2018; Marshall and Scaife, 2009). The QBO affects the troposphere and lower stratosphere in a number of important ways, including stratospheric ozone mixing, monsoon precipitation (Claud and Terray, 2007), stratospheric circulation, and hurricane frequency (Huangfu et al., 2021).

2.5.3.2 El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO)

The El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is a climate phenomenon that involves periodic fluctuations in both sea surface temperatures (SST) and atmospheric pressure in the equatorial Pacific Ocean (Cane, 1983). It is a coupled ocean-atmosphere mode. El Niño/La Niña is associated with anomalous patterns and processes in the tropical Pacific (Philander, 1990). During an El Niño phase, the SST of the eastern equatorial Pacific Ocean becomes warmer than usual (Cane et al., 1986). ENSO is considered one of the primary causes of interannual variability in weather and climate, according to Kiladis and Diaz (1989). Many researchers have studied the effects of ENSO on the troposphere and lower stratosphere (Albers et al., 2022). During the El Niño phase of the oscillation, SSTs in the eastern equatorial Pacific are unusually warm. The Northern Hemisphere (NH) responds to both positive ENSO and sudden stratospheric warming (SSW) episodes (Rezaei, 2021; Toniazzo and Scaife, 2006). When sea surface temperatures are abnormally high in the western section of the basin and

cold in the eastern portion, the gradient in SSTs increases. This, in turn, leads to stronger easterly surface winds and a higher likelihood of the La Nina phase occurring. The increased surface winds cause more surface water to be drawn away from the eastern edge of the basin, promoting more cold water upwelling and contributing to the growth and persistence of the La Nina Phase (Davey et al., 2014; Jin et al., 2003).

2.5.3.3 Solar 10.7 cm radio flux (F10.7)

The 11-year solar cycle’s variations in ultraviolet light have a significant impact on the production of stratospheric ozone. A common name for the solar 10.7 cm radio flux is the F10.7 index, which is a measurement of solar activity. It displays the strength of the Sun’s radiation at a wavelength of 10.7 cm (2800 MHz) (Wallace and Hobbs, 2006). The F10.7 is primarily raised by the upper chromosphere and the base of the corona. Compared to other measurements like sunspot number, extreme ultraviolet (EUV), ultraviolet (UV), and X-rays, F10.7 is more measurable and weather-independent (Lampropoulos et al., 2016). The F10.7 index shows variations in solar activity, which can affect how much solar radiation reaches Earth’s atmosphere. This can affect the temperature and dynamics of the tropopause. Increased solar activity can enhance the production of ozone in the stratosphere. Since the tropopause is closely linked to the stratosphere, changes in ozone levels can impact the temperature and stability of the tropopause.

2.6 The Tropical and Subtropical Tropopause

The well-mixed, wet troposphere and the steadily stratified, dry stratosphere are separated by the tropopause, which is a naturally occurring temperature inversion layer. Additionally, it controls the two-way movement of air and significant trace species like ozone and water vapor (Lu et al., 2021). The tropopause is constantly being pushed upward in the tropics by frequent convective activity and strong thunderstorms. Consequently, across the tropics, the tropopause altitude is higher than at higher latitudes. Tropopause temperature is generally observed to be cold when it reaches very high values (Highwood and Hoskins, 1998). Tropopause temperatures can drop as low as 191 K. The midlatitude tropopause (12–14 km) is located several kilometers below the tropical tropopause (16–18 km). This elevation shift typically coincides with the abrupt shift brought on by subtropical jets. The tropopause altitude (6–9 km) is lower in the polar areas because of poor convection caused by extremely cold temperatures.

2.6.1 Variability of the Tropical and Subtropical Tropopause

A number of variables, such as seasonal patterns, temperature variations, and atmospheric dynamics, affect how variable the tropical and subtropical tropopause is. Over the past few decades, there has been a general rise in height and cooling trend of the tropical tropopause (Zou et al., 2023). Equatorial waves, such Kelvin and Rossby-gravity waves, as well as localized convection and tides, all affect variations in the tropical tropopause. Tropopause parameters' sub-seasonal fluctuation is mostly related to tropical convective activity and the corresponding waves that propagate vertically (Randel and Wu, 2005). Earlier studies Highwood and Hoskins (1998) revealed that the tropopause parameters follow a distinct seasonal cycle. The QBO and ENSO are the primary causes of the interannual variations in the tropical tropopause (Randel and Jensen, 2013).

2.6.2 Significance of Tropical and Subtropical Tropopause

The regulation of climate and atmospheric dynamics depend heavily on the tropopause. The following are some essential details regarding the importance of the tropical and subtropical tropopause:

Climate Regulation: The tropopause helps regulate the entry of air from the troposphere into the stratosphere, influencing the distribution of greenhouse gases and other atmospheric constituents.

Weather Pattern: Variations in the tropopause can impact global and regional weather patterns. For instance, changes in tropopause characteristics can affect atmospheric circulation and the distribution of weather systems.

Chemical Composition:The tropical tropopause layer (TTL) is essential for determining the composition of the global upper atmosphere. It influences the levels of ozone, water vapor, and other trace gases in the stratosphere.

Convection and Circulation:In the tropics, strong convection and large-scale circulation patterns play a significant role in maintaining the tropopause layer. This layer is crucial for the transport of energy, water vapor, and other trace constituents in the climate system.

Climate Change: The tropopause is sensitive to climate change. Enhanced large-scale upwelling of air, changes in tropical convection, and variations in air temperature and chemical composition are some of the expected impacts of climate change on the

tropopause layer. Generally, understanding the dynamics of the tropical and subtropical tropopause is vital for predicting weather patterns, studying climate change, and managing the Earth's climate systems.

2.7 Dynamics of tropical and subtropical Troposphere and stratosphere Exchange

2.7.1 Atmosphere and Its Radiative Process

The primary energy source and sink in the atmospheric system are radiative processes. They control the amount of energy entering and leaving the Earth's atmosphere system. Radiative processes, which use energy to heat the air, evaporate water to produce moisture, and move air masses, have a big influence on how the atmosphere acts (Liou, 2002). Shortwave radiation from the Sun is the first form in which this energy enters the atmosphere. The transmission of the particles, however, occurs in different ways for the troposphere and stratosphere. As a result, these two levels of the atmosphere exhibit unique structures and properties, as illustrated in Figure 2.5. Different methods of radiative energy transmission to the atmosphere lead to different temperature trends in the troposphere and stratosphere (Baldwin and Dunkerton, 2005). As oxygen and ozone absorb powerful UV light, the stratosphere heats up from the top down (Randel and Wu, 1999). As longwave infrared radiation from the Earth's surface, which has been warmed by incoming solar radiation, is absorbed and re-emitted by greenhouse gases in the upper atmosphere, the troposphere warms from the bottom up. Additionally, a tiny quantity of heat is released into the atmosphere through direct contact with the surface as well as moisture evaporating and condensing.

2.7.2 Radiative Process in the Troposphere

In the troposphere, very little of the incoming solar radiation is absorbed directly by the atmosphere. The Earth's surface receives heat energy from shortwave radiation, which is then transferred to the atmosphere through a number of processes. These include direct contact between the surface and the air, moisture evaporating and condensation, and the emission of longwave infrared radiation, which is absorbed by water vapor and other greenhouse gases (CO_2 , CH_4 , N_2O , and O_3) in the atmosphere. These gases contribute to the Earth's warming by retaining heat at the bottom of the atmosphere by re-emitting a portion of this longwave radiation back toward the surface. Air in the troposphere is generally warmest at the surface and becomes cooler with increasing altitude. The Earth's rotation, surface characteristics, and temperature variations between the equator and the poles all affect convective movement. The analysis of satellite, ground-based, or aircraft measurements has raised concerns

Figure 2.5: Radiation balance of the Earth atmosphere system (Adapted from (CHANGE, 1995)).

that the radiative algorithms used in climate models may significantly underestimate the atmospheric shortwave absorption.

2.7.3 Radiative Process in the Stratosphere

The stratosphere makes up just approximately 10–20% of the entire atmospheric mass, its dynamics and chemical changes have a significant impact on the tropospheric weather systems. Strong UV_c radiation from the Sun absorbs by oxygen molecules and splits them, adding heat to the stratosphere. The majority of the UV_b light that is dangerous to Earth’s plant and animal life is filtered out in the stratosphere and does not reach the surface, which is a positive result of these processes. An increase in CO_2 content results in a very slight increase in absorbed radiation, whereas an increase in emission causes the stratosphere to cool at all heights. Large amounts of aerosols are deposited in the stratosphere after volcanic eruptions, which increases temperature. According to Bengtsson et al. (1999), the majority of the reported drops in upper-tropospheric and lower-stratospheric temperatures appear to have been caused by ozone depletion rather than rising CO_2 . The stratospheric heating rates per unit of ozone present are impacted by the modified UV light. According to Shindell et al. (1999), the stratosphere thus offers a potential response to the tropospheric weather systems.

2.8 General Circulation in TLS region

The general circulation of the troposphere and lower stratosphere involves complex interactions between various atmospheric layers and phenomena. The general circulation of the atmosphere is a representation of the regular air flow over the planet that establishes Earth's climate. The mean meridional mass flow in the troposphere is explained by the three-cell model circulation as illustrated in Figure 2.7 as describe: **Hadley Cells** are large-scale circulation patterns where warm air rises near the equator, moves towards the poles at high altitudes, cools and sinks at around 30° latitude, and then returns to the equator as trade winds. **Ferrel Cells** are situated between 30° and 60° latitudes, cause westerly winds in the mid-latitudes by causing air to rise at around 60° latitude and sink at 30° latitude. **Polar Cells** are found near the poles, where cold air sinks and moves towards the equator at the surface, rising again at around 60° latitude. Stratosphere–Troposphere Exchange involves the movement of air between the stratosphere and troposphere, driven by wave-induced forces that transport air poleward and downward into the extratropical troposphere (tuz; Holton et al., 1995).

2.8.1 TLS exchange over Tropics and Subtropics

The stratospheric circulation and global features of stratosphere–troposphere exchange (STE) are intimately related. Holton et al. (1995) examine the global dynamical elements of STE. As the primary photochemical source region for ozone, the tropics are projected to have a higher concentration of the gas according to Dobson et al. (1929). Brewer (1949) measured the water vapor using a frost-point hygrometer, which showed that the air over the mid-latitude stratosphere was extremely dry. The global scale meridional mass circulation, or BDC, is the process by which tropical air crosses the tropical tropopause to reach the stratosphere, rises, and moves poleward before falling into the middle and high latitudes. We now understand that BDC is the cause of the ozone buildup in the lower stratosphere at high latitudes. The tropical tropopause zones over the tropics are the main conduits for air movement from the troposphere to the stratosphere. Air rises from the surface to the upper troposphere in the tropics during the Hadley cell. Tropospheric column ozone decreased by 4–8 DU in the eastern Pacific and increased by 10–20 DU in the western Pacific. Tropospheric ozone typically rises as a result of stratospheric intursion and photochemical production brought on by lightning, advection, and human activity. Typically, stratospheric intursions cause an increase in tropospheric ozone over medium and high latitudes, which is associated with synoptic scale disruptions. Tropopause stability, which is essential to the interaction between the stratosphere and the troposphere, can be weakened by overshooting convection linked to trop-

Figure 2.6: The tropical and subtropical tropopause diagram.

ical cyclones. Deep convection, which further moves stratospheric ozone into the troposphere, decreases the tropopause's stability and raises the risk of stratospheric intrusion. The tropical areas of NH have higher levels of ozone than SH.

2.8.2 Troposphere–Lower Stratosphere (TLS) exchange

Stratosphere–troposphere exchange (STE) is a part of the general circulation of the atmosphere that transports air and atmospheric constituents across the tropopause. Stratosphere and troposphere are the two adjoining regions of different characteristics which are coupled radiatively, chemically, and dynamically. Radiation from the Sun warms up the land, sea surface, and air. Heating is greatest in the tropics, and less in the mid- and high latitudes. In the troposphere the atmospheric stability is much smaller than that in the stratosphere and therefore mixing is much more rapid in the troposphere than in the stratosphere. Vertical air exchange in the troposphere takes hours to days whereas mixing in the stratosphere takes months to years. The difference between the vertical transport timescales in the stratosphere and troposphere is mainly due to the rapid increase in ozone mixing ratio and the rapid decrease in water vapor mixing ratio with altitude observed just above the tropopause. Various observational techniques have shown that anthropogenic and natural trace chemical species are transported from the troposphere to the stratosphere and initiate the chemical reactions responsible for the ozone depletion. The transport of anthropogenic gases, like chlorofluorocarbons, from the troposphere into the stratosphere, affects the chemical balance in both regions and provides the catalysts necessary for stratospheric ozone destruction. Stratospheric tropospheric exchange also controls the rate of transport between source and sink regions for both tropospheric and stratospheric source gases (Holton et al., 1995).

Figure 2.7: Basic mechanism for the dynamical and exchange between the stratosphere and troposphere (Adapted from Holton et al. (1995)).

Chapter 3

Data Source

This chapter presents overview of data sources and methods used in this study. Various data sources including insitu measurement of Radiosonde data, satellite measurements of COSMIC, AIRS, and MLS, Natural forcing indices (Eli Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO), Indian Ocean dipole (IOD), Aerosol index, Quasibiennial Oscillation (QBO) and Solar 10.7 cm radio flux (F10.7)) that provides the necessary information regarding the various processes occurring in the troposphere and lower stratosphere are briefly discussed here.

3.1 Radiosonde Data

In order to study TLS dynamics over tropical and subtropical region, we used long term daily temperature data from Radiosonde in Addis station ($9^{\circ}N, 38.8^{\circ}E$) represent tropical latitude and from Cairo station ($30^{\circ}N, 31.23^{\circ}E$) represents subtropical latitude. Radiosondes are battery-powered telemetry instrument packages that are carried into the atmosphere typically by a weather balloon; they measure altitude, pressure, temperature, relative humidity and wind (both speed and direction) at high altitudes and transmit them by radio to a ground receiver. Radiosonde observations have been carried out daily at the Addis Ababa synoptic meteorological station since 1969. The radiosonde data from Addis Ababa synoptic meteorological station has undergone quality checks by Global Radiosonde Archive (IGRA) through scrutinizing presence of physically implausible values, climatological outliers, and temporal and vertical inconsistencies in temperature (Durre et al., 2006). In this study, we use high - resolution Radio sounding data at tropical Addis Ababa station and subtropical Cairo station covering the period from 2006 - 2020. Before blowing up, weather balloons usually raise for 90 minutes are fewer, covers a distance of 19 to 32 km. In Ethiopia and Cairo station launched balloons burst after 25 km. Both data sets are obtained from Ethiopian Meteorological Institute (EMI) and the CDAAC webpage (<https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds351.0/>).

3.2 COSMIC GPS Radio Occultation Data

A crucial element of the tropopause investigations is temperature data in the UTLS region with a respectable degree of vertical resolution. The coarse vertical resolution ($\sim 3-4.5$ km) of limb sounding satellite observations limits the use of the data for tropopause investigations, although they can give an overall picture of the tempera-

Figure 3.1: Diagrammatic representation of Radiosonde Observation.

ture close to the tropopause. According to Kursinski et al. (1997), the relatively new spaceborne GPS-RO approach has shown to be a potent instrument for determining the vertical structure of air temperature and humidity in all weather scenarios. It offers temperature data with great precision and exceptional vertical resolution for the entire globe. Furthermore, the accuracy of occultation measurements is equivalent to radiosondes due to recent advancements in recovery technique. These qualities make the RO approach a highly effective tool for monitoring climate change.

3.2.1 Introduction to Radio Occultation (RO)

RO is a measurement technique for obtaining information on the vertical gradient of atmospheric refractive index, which is related to the gradients temperature and pressure (Melbourne et al., 1994). When a radio signal from a transmitter on a GPS satellite passes through the limb of the atmosphere, the signal is delayed and its path is bent by gradients in the refractivity field. If this signal is intercepted by a GPS receiver on another satellite, behind the Earth's limb, then the time of receipt and the direction from which the signal is received are different from those that would have been obtained from an unrefracted path. The angle through which the ray is deflected the bending angle, is related in a simple way to the measured Doppler shift or phase delay of the received signal (Healy, 2001). During an occultation event, the GPS satellite sets or rises relative to the receiving satellite, and the ray between them sweeps out a path of changing tangent height through the atmospheric limb; a typical occultation takes ~ 1 minute to profile the atmosphere (0–60 km)

Figure 3.2: Diagrammatic representation of the occultation geometry used to calculate the bending angle based on the Doppler shift observation.

and thus provides a profile of bending angle against height (more strictly, impact parameter). RO data is used to improve numerical weather prediction models by providing accurate profiles of atmospheric temperature, pressure, and humidity (Eyre, 1994). RO technique is valuable because it provides high-precision, high-resolution data that is crucial for understanding atmospheric processes and improving weather and climate models. According to Kuo et al. (2004) the RO soundings have the highest accuracy between 5 and 25 km of altitude with observational errors (including measurement and representativeness errors) in the range 0.3–0.5% in refractivity. Several GPS RO missions are working at present, providing a high density of vertical profiles with a good time and space coverage of the Earth, like the Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere and Climate (COSMIC) six-satellite constellation (Anthes et al., 2008).

3.2.2 Inversion of GPS Radio Occultation (GPS–RO) signals in the neutral atmosphere

The Global Positioning System (GPS) Radio Occultation (RO) technique scans the Earth's atmosphere in a limb mode. RO receivers onboard Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) track the bending of RO signals emitted by GPS satellites and traversing the atmosphere. The bending angle profile of the radio waves is obtained from relative motion of the GPS and LEO satellites. This bending angle is used to derive refractivity, pressure, temperature, and water vapor profiles in the neutral atmosphere. The GPS data observable is expressed, as it is well known, in the function of the radial velocity between the emitter (i.e. LEO satellite) and the transmitter (i.e. GPS satellite).

$$D = -\frac{f_e}{c}v_p \quad (3.1)$$

where f_e is the nominal transmitted frequency, c is the speed of light in the vacuum and v_p is the radial velocity. By inspecting the geometry involved in an occultation Figure 3.2, one can obtain an equation that will allow to solve for the angles θ_{LEO} and θ_{GPS} and let \vec{k}_{GPS} and \vec{v}_{GPS} be the unit vectors of the ray at the GPS location and velocity vector of the GPS respectively (and similarly \vec{k}_{LEO} and \vec{v}_{LEO} for the LEO satellite), therefore, the Doppler shift can be expressed in the following way:

$$D = \frac{f_e}{c}(\vec{v}_{GPS} \cdot \vec{k}_{GPS} - \vec{v}_{LEO} \cdot \vec{k}_{LEO}) \quad (3.2)$$

$$D = \frac{f_e}{c}(v_{GPS}\cos(\phi_{GPS} - \theta_{GPS}) - v_{LEO}\cos(\phi_{LEO} - \theta_{LEO})) \quad (3.3)$$

An important point that allows to give for the angles required to obtain the bending angle is the assumption of spherical symmetry, Born and Wolf (2013) states that:

$$n_{GPS}r_{GPS}\sin(\theta_{GPS}) = n_{LEO}r_{LEO}\sin(\theta_{LEO}) = a = constant \quad (3.4)$$

In this expression it is commonly assumed that either n_{LEO} and n_{GPS} (index of refraction at the location of the LEO and GPS respectively) is one. The angles ϕ_{GPS} and ϕ_{LEO} can be directly found using the dot product of the velocity and position vectors of the GPS and LEO satellites. Afterwards, the angles θ_{GPS} and θ_{LEO} are obtained using the previous relationships, thus allowing to solve for the bending angle α . The assumption of spherical symmetry allows to set out a relationship between the bending angle (α) and the index of refraction (n), using the Bouguer's formula. Since the impact parameter (a) is constant in the straight line, it is possible compute the bending angle (which is the departure of the true ray from the ideal assumption of a straight line). Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{straightline} : r\sin(\theta_s) &= a_s \\ \text{Truesay(Bouguer's formula)} : nr\sin(\theta) &= a \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

Differentiating both expressions, multiplying the straight line one by the refraction index and subtracting both equations it is obtained the following:

$$dnr\sin(\theta) + ndr(\sin(\theta) - \sin(\theta_s)) + nr(\cos(\theta)d\theta - \cos(\theta_s)d\theta_s) \quad (3.6)$$

Since the bending angle at the ionospheric heights, specially from the F layer, does not exceed 0.03^0 even during daytime and near solar maximum (Gurvich, 1990), it is possible to approximate the above equation to:

$$dnr \sin(\theta) + nr \cos(\theta)(d\theta - d\theta_s) \quad (3.7)$$

The differential of the bending angle $d\alpha$ is, in fact, the quantity $d\theta - d\theta_s$, therefore recalling the Bouguer's formula, the previous expression yields to:

$$d\alpha = -\frac{\sin\theta}{\cos\theta} \frac{dn}{n} = -\frac{\sin\theta}{\cos\theta} d\ln(n) = -\frac{a}{\sqrt{(x^2 - a^2)}} d\ln(n) \quad (3.8)$$

where $x = nr$. The bending angle α is obtained integrating the previous expression for the path towards the GPS and the path towards the LEO, that is

$$\alpha(a) = -a \left[\int_a^x + \int_a^x \right] \frac{1}{\sqrt{(x^2 - a^2)}} \frac{d\ln(n)}{dx} dx \quad (3.9)$$

3.2.2.1 Refractivity from bending angle

The ionosphere and neutral atmosphere both contribute to the overall bending of the light path. Ionospheric refractivity at microwave frequencies is inversely proportional to the square of the transmitted (carrier) frequency and almost proportionate to the local electron density. By comparing the bending in L1 and L2 frequencies, the dispersive nature of the ionosphere facilitates the isolation of the neutral atmospheric bending component. As a result, the neutral bending angle can be determined based on the impact parameter. The refractive index (n) profile is then obtained using an Abel transform on the whole bending angle observations made during an occultation event. The total refractive bending angle for neutral atmosphere can be expressed as:

$$\alpha(a) = -2a \int_a^\infty \frac{1}{\sqrt{(x^2 - a^2)}} \frac{d\ln(n)}{dx} dx \quad (3.10)$$

Note that the assumption of physical symmetry implies that the refractivity index depends only on height. Applying the Abel integral transform on this expressions, it is possible to obtain the index of fraction in function of the impact parameter a :

$$\ln(n(x)) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_x^\infty \frac{\alpha(a)}{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}} da \quad (3.11)$$

The requirement for a priori knowledge at the outset is indicated by the upper bound of integration, or infinity. The underlying presumptions of the Abel transform include the following: each atmospheric shell has a uniform refractive index and is spherical. It is discovered that adding local horizontal structure information to the retrieval process can increase accuracy.

$$n(r) = \exp\left[\frac{1}{\pi} \int_a^{\infty} \frac{\alpha(a)}{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}} da\right] \quad (3.12)$$

3.2.2.2 Temperature profile from refractivity

The ratio of light speed in a vacuum to that in a medium is known as the refractive index. Since the refractive index in the atmosphere is so near to unity, it is typically expressed in terms of refractivity (N), which is written as:

$$N = (n - 1) \times 10^6 \quad (3.13)$$

The interaction of an electromagnetic wave with the molecules and electrons in an atmosphere affects the wave's speed. The density of dry atmospheric molecules and atoms n_d , water vapour molecules n_w , free electrons in the ionosphere n_e , and particles like liquid water content n_p are the primary sources of refractive index at microwave frequencies. Through their polarizability, the molecules of N_2 , O_2 , Ar, and CO_2 are examples of nonpolar components whose total contributions to refractivity are shown by the n_d term. Due to its significant permanent dipole moment and polarizability, the n_w term represents the contribution of water vapor molecules to refractivity. The contribution to refractivity in the ionosphere n_e is due to free electron. The scattering term, or n_p term, is the part of refractivity that increases in direct proportion to the mass of condensed water in the atmosphere. Combining all four factors contributions to refractivity, the result can be expressed as follows at first order Smith and Weintraub (1953),

$$N = 77.6 \frac{P}{T} + 3.37 \times 10^5 \frac{e}{T^2} + 4.03 \times 10^7 \frac{n_e}{f^2} + 1.4W \quad (3.14)$$

Where, P is the pressure in hPa, T is temperature in K, e is water vapor partial pressure in hPa, n_e is the local electron density in the ionosphere in m^{-3} , f is the transmitted radio frequency in Hz and W is the mass of the condensed water in the atmosphere. According to Smith and Weintraub (1953), the scattering term n_p , which results from liquid water or ice suspensions, is generally excluded because it is insignificant when compared to the other three factors. Therefore, refractivity is

primarily contributed by the dry and moist atmosphere factors (n_d and n_w) after ionospheric correction. In atmospheric regions (above 8-10 km altitude) when the water vapour mixing ratio is less than $\sim 10^{-4}$, the moist term can be ignored. Therefore, equation 3.14 reduce to

$$N = 77.6 \frac{P}{T} \quad (3.15)$$

Further equation of state for dry air is given as

$$\rho = 0.3484 \frac{P}{T} \quad (3.16)$$

Where, ρ is the air density in kgm^{-3} . Equation 3.15 and 3.16 show that the refractivity of dry air is directly proportional to density, so that density may be calculated using these equations. Additionally, by integrating the equation of hydrostatic equilibrium, pressure can be determined from density,

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = -\rho g \quad (3.17)$$

Where, z is the altitude and g is the acceleration due to gravity. Finally, using pressure and density data, temperature can be estimated using equation 3.16. Therefore, the vertical profile of refractivity can be used to determine the vertical profiles of temperature, pressure, and density. The temperature data from reanalysis or climatology is acquired at the altitude where the hydrostatic integral is to begin in order to define the unknown constants of integration. When integration proceeds to lower atmospheric levels, the pressure inaccuracies brought on by this temperature guess decrease quickly. When water vapor is present in significant amounts, as it is in the lower and middle troposphere, its contribution to refractivity cannot be neglected. Hence equation 3.14 in the neutral atmosphere (mostly troposphere and stratosphere) is expressed as:

$$N = 77.6 \frac{P}{T} + 3.37 \times 10^5 \frac{e}{T^2} \quad (3.18)$$

There are two unknowns in equation 3.18: water vapour pressure and temperature. Therefore, information about one variable from an independent source is required to compute the other in order to separate the contributions of the dry and wet terms to refractivity. We refer to the temperature profile that results from ignoring the second term in equation 3.18 as dry-air retrieval, and the temperature profile that results from taking the second term into consideration as moistair retrieval (also called wetPrf). The GPS-RO approach and data inversion are described in depth in Melbourne (2004). Long-term stability, all-weather operation, worldwide coverage, high accuracy, and independent height, pressure, and temperature data are some of

the key benefits of RO measurements. However, multipath errors and the presumption of spherical symmetry are drawbacks of RO measurements.

3.2.3 Radio Occultation Characteristics

For a RO receiver on a satellite in a high inclination orbit, RO measurements are globally distributed in a quasi-random manner. They provide temperature information for the stratosphere and upper troposphere, and humidity information for the lower troposphere. They have a high vertical resolution of 0.5-1 km, but low horizontal resolution of ~ 200 km. They provide information of low noise, equivalent to random errors in temperature of ~ 1 K. Moreover their systematic errors are very low: < 0.2 K RO measurements are all-weather, as they are negligibly affected by cloud and precipitation. The space or time sampling of the measurements is determined by the number of GPS receivers multiplied by the number of transmitters; a constellation of 6 satellites (receiving signals from 24 GPS satellites) can provide ~ 3000 occultations per day. Furthermore, by the standards of space-borne remote sensing, they are relatively inexpensive.

3.2.4 The COSMIC Mission

The University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (UCAR) and the National Space Organization (NSPO) of Taiwan collaborated to undertake the successful COSMIC/Formosa Satellite Mission 3 (FORMOSAT-3). Six Low Earth orbit (LEO) satellites with GPS capability were launched into a circular orbit in April 2006 as part of the COSMIC mission. COSMIC mission is to demonstrate the value of near-real-time GPS Radio Occultation (GPS-RO) data to global users. It is the worlds first operational GPS-RO mission for global Earth weather forecasting; climate monitoring; and atmospheric, ionospheric, and geodetic research. The satellites had an inclination of 72 degrees and were approximately 512 km in diameter. Phase delay profiles are obtained in approximately one minute by a bottom-to-top (rising event) or top-to-bottom (setting event) limb scan of the atmosphere caused by the relative motion of GPS and LEO satellites. With two forward and two backward antennas, each satellite in the constellation may produce between 2000 and 2500 occultation events every day. From the near surface to an altitude of ~ 40 km, the COSMIC GPS-RO mission delivers temperature profiles with greater vertical resolution. Global coverage is possible because to the polar orbiting, 72 degree inclined COSMIC satellites.

3.2.5 Resolution of COSMIC GPS-RO Observations

Depending on the retrieval method, the GPS-RO profile's vertical resolution changes. The time derivative of the excess phase and the exact orbit determination of the GPS and LEO satellites are used in the geometrical optics technique to determine the neu-

tral atmospheric bending angle. Additionally, the Fresnel zone restricts the vertical resolution in the geometrical optics profile. It is measured to be approximately 0.5 km in the lower troposphere and ~ 1.4 km in the UTLS region. The distance traversed by the radio path as it enters and exits a layer having a vertical resolution of Δz can be used to establish the horizontal resolution of radio occultation measurements. RO measurements typically have a horizontal resolution of around 270 km, which equates to a vertical resolution of 1.4 km.

3.2.6 Validation of COSMIC GPS–RO data

Numerous variables, including sensor quality, atmospheric multipath, orbit determination precision, ionospheric circumstances, and Abel integral initialization, affect the accuracy of GPS-RO observations. Temperature accuracy in the UTLS was found to be better than 0.5 K for individual profiles and ~ 0.1 K for averaged profiles, according to validation of temperature profiles from earlier GPS–RO missions. According to (Kuo et al., 2004), RO sounding accuracy is highest between 5 km and 25 km. Many in situ observations, reanalysis, models, and extensive validation of temperature data derived from the COSMIC observation have been conducted in the past (Noersomadi and Tsuda, 2017; Wang et al., 2013). A -0.09 K global mean temperature bias and a 1.72 K standard deviation were found in an excellent agreement between COSMIC temperature data and global radiosonde data. According to Schreiner et al. (2007), the accuracy estimations of the GPS-RO data from the COSMIC mission showed a precision that is roughly twice as good as that of earlier GPS-RO missions like CHAMP and SAC-C. The precision of temperature and refractivity data in the COSMIC observations ranges from 8 to 25 km, with an accuracy of 0.1% (Alexander et al., 2014).

3.3 Microwave Limb sounder (MLS) Satellite data

Aura–MLS is a limb-viewing spectrometer that observes microwave emission of molecules from the Earth’s atmosphere in 5 spectral bands between 118 GHz and 2.5 THz. These spectral bands are centred near 5 frequencies: 118 GHz, 190 GHz, 240 GHz, 640 GHz, and 2250 GHz. Limb sounding is a technique in which the atmospheric emission of electromagnetic radiation at the Earth’s limb is measured from a remote platform. Numerous chemical species found in the Troposphere and stratosphere are measured by MLS, including sulphur dioxide (SO_2), hydrogen chloride (HCl), methanol (CH_3OH), bromine monoxide (BrO), methyl chloride (CH_3Cl), methyl cyanide (CH_3CN), nitric acid (HNO_3), peroxy radical (HO_2), hypochlorous acid (HOCl), nitrous oxide (N_2O), ozone (O_3), hydroxyl radical (OH), and sulphur dioxide (SO_2) as illustrated in Figure 3.3. Every twenty-five seconds, the MLS instrument field-of-view scans the orbital plane from the surface to about 90 km, providing

Figure 3.3: Model of the Aura spacecraft with its four sensors (modified from sch): the Tropospheric Emission Spectrometer (TES), the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI), the High-Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS), and the Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS).

latitude coverage between 82°N and 82°S for each orbit. After a continuous scan of around 20 seconds, an antenna retrace and calibration activities take about 5 seconds out of the total 25 seconds. Radiances are reported at regular intervals (~ 0.16 s) during the continuous scan. Every day, Aura–MLS covers the entire world with about 3500 vertical profiles and 15 orbits. MLS completes 240 limb scans every orbit, it can offer an along-track separation of 1.5° (or around 165 km) between successive scans. Figure 3.4 shows the observation geometry of MLS. According to Livesey and Wu (2004), the MLS viewing geometry in Figure 3.4 shows that temperature and atmospheric composition have an impact on radiance measurement during individual limb scans throughout a range that corresponds to multiple neighboring profiles. The roughly horizontal lines show three of the 120 limb ray pathways for five scans. The recovered atmospheric profiles are shown by the straight radial lines. The thin black line under the central profile indicates the locus of the limb tangent point for one scan, including the effects of refraction. We employed MLS version 4.2 level–2 products of ozone and water vapor in the current thesis.

3.3.1 MLS water vapor measurement

Data on water vapour at various pressure levels obtained from rotational line radiance measurements at 190 GHz. The range between 316 hPa to 0.001 hPa is important to taking water vapor for scientific research. Table 3.1 lists the water vapour mea-

Figure 3.4: The MLS viewing geometry detecting limb radiances in the direction of motion (forward direction) is depicted in the top figure. The roughly horizontal lines show three of the 120 limb ray pathways for five scans. The boxed area above is expanded in the diagram at the bottom. The recovered atmospheric profiles are shown by the straight radial lines. The thin black line under the central profile represents the locus of the limb tangent point for one scan, taking into account the effects of refraction (modified from Livesey and Wu (2004)).

Table 3.1: Summary of MLS water vapour product (adapted from Livesey et al. (2017))

Water vapour	
Retrieval	190 GHz (1.57 mm)
Resolution (vertical X horizontal)	~2.5x180 km (68 – 215hPa)
Precision (for single profile)	~6–20% (68–178 hPa), ~40%(215hPa)
Accuracy	~7–20 (68–215 hPa)
Minimum measurable H_2O	0.1 ppmv (68–47 hPa), 3 ppmv (178–215 hPa)

measurements’ vertical and horizontal (along-track) resolution, accuracy, and precision in the UTLS. For the years 2019 to 2020, we used monthly mean MLS water vapour data that was gridded with a 2.5 degree latitude by 5 degree longitude spatial resolution (<https://mls.jpl.nasa.gov>).

3.3.2 MLS ozone measurement

Radiance measurements taken close to 240 GHz are used to get MLS Ozone measurements at various pressure levels. The range from 261 hPa to 0.001 hPa is suitable for scientific research. For all pressure levels, the horizontal cross track resolution is 6 km, which is dictated by the MLS 240 GHz field-of-view width. The MLS orbit determines the daily MLS ozone measurements’ longitudinal separation, which is approximately $10-20^\circ$ over middle and lower latitude (Livesey et al., 2017). Table 3.2

Table 3.2: Summary of MLS Ozone product (adapted from Livesey et al. (2017))

Ozone	
Retrieval	240 GHz (1.25 mm)
Resolution (vertical X horizontal)	$\sim 3 \times 350$ km (68 – 215 hPa)
Precision (for single profile)	$\sim 40 - 20$ ppbv (68–215 hPa)
Accuracy	$\sim 50 - 20$ ppbv (68–215 hPa)

provides a summary of the typical vertical and horizontal (along-track) resolution, accuracy, and precision of ozone observations in the UTLS.

3.4 AIRS Satellite

The Atmospheric Infrared Sounder (AIRS) is a hyperspectral infrared instrument on the EOS Aqua Spacecraft, launched on May 4, 2002. Atmospheric Infrared Sounder (AIRS) is one of the six instruments onboard the aqua satellite which has a sun synchronous orbit. Aqua crosses the equator from South to North at 1:30 PM local time (day time) in an ascending orbit, and from North to South at 1:30 AM (night-time) in a descending orbit. Therefore twice daily temperature profiles are obtained by AIRS. AIRS is a high resolution infrared sounder which main purpose being to acquire atmospheric temperature and humidity profiles from the surface upward to an altitude of 40 km. AIRS, in conjunction with the Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit (AMSU), produces temperature profiles with one Kelvin per kilometer on a global scale, as well as water vapor profiles and minor gas amounts for CO_2 , CO , SO_2 , O_3 and CH_4 (Aumann et al., 2005). AIRS data are used for weather forecasting and studies of global climate change.

3.4.1 AIRS measurement technique and Observation geometry

The Atmospheric Infrared Sounder is an infrared grating spectrometer that operates in the thermal infrared portion of the spectrum, from $3.7 \mu\text{m}$ to $15.4 \mu\text{m}$. It has 2378 channels covering about three fourth of this range, with a spectral resolution $\frac{\lambda}{\Delta\lambda}$ of about 1200. Radiometric sensitivity is typically about 0.25 K. This system measures upwelling thermal radiation emitted from the atmosphere and the surface. By analyzing an observed spectrum it is possible to infer vertical distribution of temperature and water vapor. This is essentially accomplished by inverting the so called radiative transfer equation (RTE), which models the spectral intensity for a given distribution of the geophysical parameters. The microwave observations are used to describe the average cloud cover in a limited area surrounding a cluster of infrared observations in a combined sounding system. The typical cloud cover has a high degree of spatial variability. With the aid of microwave observations, it is possible to "extrapolate" between a highly cloudy sub-scene and a less cloudy sub-

Figure 3.5: AIRS Viewing Geometry and Coverage.

scene to zero cloudiness by analyzing the infrared spectra from small portions of this region, with varying amounts of clouds in each.

3.4.2 AIRS Mission

The primary AIRS mission is to address various science questions related to climate and global change manifested in the atmosphere. The mission was later expanded to encompass weather prediction and atmospheric chemistry. There are thousands of radiosondes released globally every day, but they provide only a spotty coverage on a global scale and very sparse coverage over oceans and uninhabited regions. Weather satellite measurements have been available since the late 1970s, but measurement accuracy has not been adequate for climate studies. The AIRS system was designed to provide continuous global observations with an accuracy equal to that of radiosondes. This is now being achieved. Generally the primary mission of AIRS satellite is to support climate research and improve weather forecasting. Airs provides critical data for monitoring Earth's atmosphere. It uses infrared technology to create three dimensional maps of air, surface temperature, water vapor, and cloud properties. AIRS data has a wide range of applications including: Weather forecasting, Climate monitoring, Atmospheric composition, Sever weather events, water cycle studies and Environmental monitoring.

3.5 Proxy data for Natural Forcing

The current study examined long-term variability and trend in the TLS using the following proxy data sets. These proxy data supports background influence in addition to RS, COSMIC, MLS, and AIRS observations. Aerosol index data corresponding to

time t from 2006 to 2020, Quasi–Biennial east–west zonal winds at 30 hPa data as a proxy of QBO(t), Monthly mean Nino 3.4 index data as a proxy of ENSO(t), Oceanic influences index data as a proxy of IOD(t), and F10.7 solar radioflux data as a proxy of solar cycle activity SC(t). The Nino 3.4 index, which provides monthly mean temperature anomalies of the equatorial Pacific Ocean sea surface across $5^{\circ}\text{S} - 5^{\circ}\text{N}$, $120^{\circ}\text{E} - 170^{\circ}\text{W}$, was sourced from the following website: (<https://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/data/indices/ersst5.nino.mth.91-20.ascii>). (<ftp://ftp.geolab.nrcan.gc.ca/data/solarflux/monthly/averages/maver.txt>) is where the solar radioflux data for F10.7 was obtained. The website (<https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/met/ag/strat/produkte/qbo>) provided the QBO winds that were collected from the Singapore station between pressure levels of 70–10 hPa. The data on oceanic influences for IOD was obtained from the following (https://ioc3.unesco.org/oopc/state_of_the_ocean/sur/ind/dmi.php). The MODIS satellite provided the aerosol data, which were downloaded via the (<https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov>).

3.6 Methods of analysis for the study of TLS dynamics

3.6.1 Multivariate linear regression (MLR) Analysis

A multivariate linear regression analysis has been performed on the long term monthly mean temperature signals to extract the intra–annual (annual and semiannual) and interannual (ENSO, SC, QBO, IOD and aerosol) components in the least square technique to fit the signals over the altitude range of 1 km to 25 km on 15 years of data (January 2006 to December 2020) over the tropical and subtropical regions. We followed the methodology mentioned by previous Authors (Randel and Cobb, 1994). At each altitude, we applied multivariate regression model equation as follows:

$$T(t, z) = \alpha(z) + \beta(z)t + \gamma(z)ENSO(t) + \delta(z)SF(t) + \epsilon(z)QBO(t) + \zeta(z)IOD(t) + \eta(z)Aerosol(t) + r(t) \quad (3.19)$$

Where $T(z,t)$ is an estimate of temperature measurements at a vertical height of $z(1-25 \text{ km})$ and time t denoting the number of month's from (2006–2020), β is the trend per month. The coefficients α , γ , δ , ϵ , ζ and η are determined in least squares sense. $\alpha(z)$ represents seasonal and intra–seasonal variations. $r(t)$ is the residual term. $\alpha(z)$ in the above equation is in the form:

$$\alpha(z) = a_o + \sum_{i=1}^2 [A_i \cos(\omega_i(t - p_i))] \quad (3.20a)$$

where $\omega_i = \frac{2\pi i}{12}$, t is time in month's, p_i is the phase of SAO and AO, a_o is constant, A_i is the amplitude of SAO and AO.

3.6.2 Wavelet Analysis method

Wavelet analysis is a relatively new technique that is an important addition to standard signal analysis methods. It provides information about what frequency band exists at what time interval. The wavelet transform uses multiresolution analysis which analyzes the signal at different frequencies with different resolutions. We applied wavelet analysis technique to identify dominant modes of tropospheric lower stratospheric oscillations (IOD, AO, SAO, QBO, ENSO and SF) by using RS and COSMIC temperature data in Addiss and Cairo station. Mother morlet wavelet functions are

$$\psi(t) = \exp(i2\pi t) \exp\left(-\frac{t^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (3.21)$$

The tropospheric lower stratospheric monthly mean temperature signals of (2006–2020) observation data is represented by $x(t)$, its CWT with respect to the wavelet ψ is a function of two variables, $\psi_{S,\tau}$:

$$Y(S, \tau) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \psi_{S,\tau}^* dt \quad (3.22)$$

$$Y(S, \tau) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \psi_{S,\tau}^* dt = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \frac{1}{\sqrt{|S|}} \psi^* \left(\frac{t - \tau}{S} \right) dt \quad (3.23)$$

Where the (*) indicates the complex conjugate of the wavelet function. The position of the wavelet in the time domain is given by τ , while the position in the frequency domain is given by S . The above equation provides information simultaneously on time and frequency. To retrieve the oscillatory behavior of the temperature signals, this wavelet function was preferred for noise removal and resolution enhancement with smoother variations. The wavelet power spectrum (WPS) is defined by:

$$WPS(\tau, S) = |Y(S, \tau)|^2 \quad (3.24)$$

which is called scalogram or wavelet periodogram. Average of wavelet power spectrum is known as global wavelet power spectrum GWPS, which is given by:

$$GWPS(S, \tau) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |Y(S, \tau)|^2 d\tau \quad (3.25)$$

The global wavelet power spectrum (GWPS) is useful for producing the power of the temperature variability as a function of oscillation frequency (period).

3.6.3 Two Dimension Fast Fourier transform (2D-FFT) Analysis

The Two-dimensional Fast Fourier Transform (2D FFT) is an algorithm that extends the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to two dimensions. It is commonly used to convert a 2D signal, such as an image, from the spatial domain to the frequency domain. This transformation is particularly valuable in fields like image processing and signal processing, where analyzing the frequency components of a 2D signal is crucial. Typically, the input for the 2D FFT is a 2D array of values, like pixel intensities in an image. The algorithm applies the FFT to each row of the array and then to each column of the resulting array. This process effectively breaks down the 2D signal into its frequency components. As a result, the output is a 2D array of complex numbers that represent the amplitude and phase of the frequency components. The expected Fourier transform of a discretized signal is given by the convolution of the true transform and the transform of a Dirac comb window function designating those measurement times (Cooley and Tukey, 1965). We applied 2-D FFT analysis technique to identify the periodicity of upper tropospheric lower stratospheric kelvin wave oscillations by using RS and AIRS temperature data in Addis and Cairo station. Interested readers may refer the theory of 2 D FFT technique by Babu and Stoica (2010).

3.6.4 Sinusoidal Fitting

Equatorial Kelvin waves have the strongest amplitudes at the equator with zonal wave number 1 and 2 predominant (Mote et al., 2002). To isolate dominant wave numbers, a fitting function, is used

$$T(\lambda, d) = \sum_{i=1}^2 [A_i \sin(\omega_i(\lambda - p_i))] \quad (3.26)$$

where $\omega_i = \frac{2\pi i}{P}$, λ is longitude, p_i is the phase of wave, P is periodicity of the wave, $T(\lambda, d)$ is temperature in a function of longitude and days, A_i is the amplitude of the wave. Mixing with wave 1 and wave 2 components is then applied to best fit the temperature fluctuations of T' data with the amplitude A and phase p for all longitudes λ solved by means of a nonlinear least-square method. The back ground temperature profile T_o (fitted model temperature) curve reveals a mixed wave with wave 1 and wave 2 components.

3.6.5 Kelvin Wave Identification Procedure

The atmospheric temperature profile is believed to be composed of the background and fluctuating temperature profiles due to different oscillation mode waves such as kelvin waves. Identifying the characteristics of kelvin waves from the temperature profiles requires removing the background temperature profile. Sinusoidal fitting has been usually applied to estimate the background temperature profiles (Mote et al., 2002). In the present study, the background temperature profile variations are estimated by sinusoidal fitting explained by (Tsuda et al., 1994), and hence the temperature profiles are estimated by subtracting the background quantity from the original measurements. we use a sinusoidal T_o to best fit to the interpolated data, which is considered to be background temperature (model temperature T) variation.

The background values were then removed from each temperature profile corresponding to each altitude and the resulting fluctuation ($T' = T - T_o$) data has been utilized to identify the Kelvin wave features. Furthermore, fluctuation data during every three month (season) period are put together as ensembles to show the seasonal variation of Kelvin wave activity for Spring (March, April and May (MAM)), summer (Jun, July and August (JJA)), Autumn or Fall (September, October and November (SON)) and winter (December, January and February (DJF)) of March 2019 to February 2020. As a final step, we applied a 2-D Fast Fourier Transform (2D-FFT) on large scale temperature fluctuation components and the subsequent application of incoherent integration on the output of the FFT to identify the typical characteristics of Kelvin waves. The vertical wavelengths (lambda in the z axis) estimated from simple wave theory for kelvin waves:

$$\lambda_z = \frac{2\pi}{N} \left(\frac{\lambda_x}{\tau} - \bar{U} \right) \quad (3.27)$$

Where, \bar{U} , N , τ , λ_x , and λ_z are velocity of mean zonal wind, bouyancy frequency, wave period (observed parameter), zonal wavelength, and vertical wavelength (observed parameter) respectively. N is approximately equal to 0.02 s^{-1} (hol), zonal wavelength λ_x for wave number 1 is equivalent to 40,200 km, which is the circumference of the earths mean radius plus height from the surface, for wave number 2, λ_x is equivalent to 20,100 km and \bar{U} is variant by time and altitude depending on the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO). According to monthly mean zonal wind data at Singapore, \bar{U} is approximately equal to -1.73 m/s, -1.63 m/s, 0.13 m/s, and 0.88 m/s during Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter respectively, where the minus sign indicates easterly.

3.6.6 Gravity wave energy

In the atmosphere, gravity waves play a crucial role in transferring energy and momentum between different layers, influencing weather patterns and the general circulation of the atmosphere. They can also affect the distribution of temperature and moisture, making them an essential component of atmospheric dynamics. We have calculated the wave kinetic energy using fluctuation of zonal and meridional wind observed by radiosonde using equation 3.28 and also potential energy from RS temperature fluctuation data with integrated over the heights of 15 – 25 km. The linear correlation between kinetic and potential energy was particularly significant (0.716). Gravity Wave(GW) activity is estimated by calculating the potential(E_p), kinetic(E_k) and total(E_t) energies per unit mass as defined by:

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2}(u'^2 + v'^2) \quad (3.28)$$

$$E_p = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{g}{N} \frac{T'}{T} \right)^2 \quad (3.29)$$

where $g(z)$ is the acceleration due to gravity. $N(z)$ is the oscillation frequency of the parcel of the atmosphere (usually called Buoyancy or Brunt–vaisala frequency) and it is expressed as

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (3.30)$$

where $\Gamma_d = \frac{g}{c_p}$ is adiabatic lapse rate, c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure of the atmosphere and for this study 9.8×10^{-3} (K/m) lapse rate is adopted.

$$E_T = E_k + E_p \quad (3.31)$$

3.6.7 Trace gas mass flux of in the tropopause

The mass flux can be estimated by multiplying the concentration of a tracer (in this case ozone and water vapor) that indicates stratospheric or tropospheric air by the cross-tropopause. To calculate the mass flux across a surface, we count the number of trajectories that cross the tropopause. The general formula for mass flux of the tracer is:

$$F_{flux} = \rho v A \quad (3.32)$$

Where, F_{flux} is the mass flux of Ozone and Water vapor, ρ is the density of the gas (density of ozone and water vapor) in the tropopause, v is the velocity of Ozone and Water vapor during the tropopause crossing, and A is the cross sectional area of Ozone and Water vapor in the tropopause variation. The stratosphere to the troposphere

(STT) density of ozone and Troposphere to the stratosphere (TST) density of water are calculated as:

$$\rho_{O_3} = 1.66 \frac{P}{T} C \quad (3.33)$$

$$\rho_{H_2O} = 0.62 \frac{P}{T} C \quad (3.34)$$

Where, P is tropopause pressure (in our study the tropopause pressure of tropical (Ethiopia) is 100 hPa and tropopause pressure of subtropical (Egypt) is 150 hPa), T is tropopause temperature, and C is concentration or mixing ratio of Ozone or water vapor we get from Aura/MLS satellite. Apart from the tropopause altitude oscillation, the tropopause temperature oscillation plays a significant role in the transport of water vapour from the troposphere to the lower stratosphere (Brewer, 1949). The holding capacities of water vapour in the air and hence the saturation mixing ratio of air is a strong function of air temperature (Clausius-Clapeyron relation). The Saturation Mixing Ratio (SMR) with respect to ice is estimated using the following equation (Bolton, 1980)

$$SMR = 0.623 \left(\frac{e_{si}}{P - e_{si}} \right) \quad (3.35)$$

Where, SMR is saturation mixing ratio, P is pressure in hPa, and e_{si} is saturation vapor pressure in hPa is given by

$$e_{si} = \exp\left(9.550426 - \frac{5723.265}{T} + 3.53068 \ln(T) - 0.00728332T\right) \quad (3.36)$$

T is the tropopause temperature in Kelvin and P is the pressure in hPa at tropopause (Pressure near the tropopause in tropical region is 100 hPa and subtropical region is 150 hPa).

Chapter 4

Study on Long Term Troposphere lower stratosphere Temperature (TLST) trend in tropical and subtropical Northern hemisphere Using ground based and COSMIC Satellite data

This chapter presents the findings and a detailed discussion of the research done on Troposphere lower Stratosphere temperature trend in the tropical and subtropical northern hemisphere from 2006–2020 using ground based and COSMIC satellite data. The results presented here are published in the Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics by Negash and Prakash (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jastp.2024.106306>

4.1 Introduction

The tropical troposphere and lower stratosphere (TLS) is a complex region of the Earth's atmosphere, where the mixing of ozone (O_3) rich stratospheric air and humid (H_2O) tropospheric air takes place across the tropical tropopause (Holton et al., 1995). The tropopause is a stable layer that is created by natural atmospheric inversion. It regulates the vertical distributions of ozone, water vapor, aerosols, and other trace elements and sets the upper limit for cloud cover. Two definitions of the tropopause are commonly employed in the tropics: one is based on the cold point, while the other is based on the lapse rate's properties. According to Highwood et al. (2000), the cold point tropopause is the point at which the vertical temperature profile achieves its minimum and the lowest temperatures are experienced by air parcels traveling from the troposphere to the stratosphere. The cold point tropopause effectively controls the total amount of water vapor in the lower stratosphere (Randel et al., 2000). A surge in stratospheric water vapor could result from overshooting convection and a warmer tropical tropopause temperature. This would have a significant effect on both the stratospheric chemistry and the global radiation budget. The stratosphere cools when stratospheric ozone is depleted and tropospheric carbon dioxide levels rise. By lowering the amount of ozone in the stratosphere, more water vapor tends to cool the stratosphere and warm the troposphere (Forster, 1999). The atmosphere in the troposphere tends to cool as a result of volcanic activity. The variation in the average state of the climate from year to year is known as interannual variability. The primary drivers of interannual variability, or long-term variability, in

the tropical troposphere are El Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO), 11-year solar flux (SF), Quasi Biennial Oscillation (QBO), aerosol, and oceanic impacts like IOD. Sea surface temperature (SST) variations over the Equatorial central and Eastern Pacific between anomalously warm (El Nino) and cold (La Nina) conditions are the natural occurrence of ENSO, one of the most significant coupled ocean atmosphere phenomena (Calvo et al., 2010). ENSO episodes, which are defined by a cooling of the lower stratosphere combined with an increase in moist convection and a warming of the sea surface temperature (SST), are known to have a major impact on lower stratospheric temperature fluctuation in the tropics (Pan and Oort, 1983). The QBO drives the vertical momentum transfer by equatorial waves (Holton and Lindzen, 1972; Kawatani and Hamilton, 2013; Lindzen and Holton, 1968) and regulates the effects of vertically propagating planetary waves (Holton and Tan, 1980). All latitudes experience tropospheric warming as solar activity reaching its peak. Numerous observational methods, such as balloon soundings and rocket sonde observations, have been used to monitor temperature variations in the troposphere and lower stratosphere (Eckermann et al., 1995). Data from the 63-station radiosonde network used by Angell (1990) show that during the late 1970s and early 1980s, the tropospheric (850-300 hPa) layer saw generally increase of about 0.3 K. Using data from radiosondes and rocket sondes, Ramaswamy et al. (1999) estimated tropical and NH midlatitude solar cycle fluctuations of around 0.2 - 0.8 K from the lower to the upper stratosphere, respectively. There was a minor cooling indicated by the tropospheric temperature trends from 1979 to May 1995 (-0.06° /decade from MSU and -0.07° /decade for radiosondes). However, climate records constructed from radiosonde data sometimes include temporal or geographical inhomogeneities due to time-varying biases caused by changes in instruments and measurement procedures (Wang et al., 2012). Compared to Radiosonde, climate records from radio occultation utilized satellite data offer substantially greater spatial coverage and density, High vertical resolution, high accuracy, long-term stability, and overall coverage in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) can be obtained using the global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) radio occultation (RO) technique (Kuo et al., 2005; Rao et al., 2009; Rocken et al., 2000; Schreiner et al., 2007).

Bencherif et al. (2006) examined long-term climatology and climate change using 22 years of radiosonde and ECMWF reanalysis data over the southern hemisphere. The average temperature trends for the troposphere and stratosphere are, respectively, -0.08 to 0.28 and -1.08 to -0.44 . Tropical radiosonde and COSMIC Radio Occultation (COSMIC - RO) lower-air measurements have yielded insights into the tropopause and thermodynamic features in recent decades. Many research using radiosonde data, satellite observations, reanalysis, and climate models have investigated

the variability and trends of the tropical tropopause layer (wan; Fujiwara et al., 2022; Randel et al., 2017; Schmidt et al., 2008; Seidel and Randel, 2006; Wang et al., 2012). Using data obtained from radiosondes (Bischoff et al., 2007; Gettelman et al., 2002a; Seidel et al., 2001; Sivakumar et al., 2011), a few studies on tropopause height and its climatology have been reported with respect to sub-tropical latitudes. Rodriguez-Franco and Cuevas (2013) define the subtropical tropopause region in respect to the position of the subtropical jet stream (STJ) using long-term highly-resolved sonde and ERA data records over Tenerife. More recently, Shangguan and Wang (2022) investigated the semi-annual oscillation (SAO) of temperature in the UTLS region from the subtropics to middle latitudes using satellite measurements, reanalysis data and model simulations (Son et al., 2011). QBO, SC, ENSO, AO, SAO, IOD, and aerosol have all been thoroughly investigated in the middle atmosphere. An examination of the literature revealed that there are no publications on tropospheric and lower stratospheric trends over the Ethiopian region, which motivates the need for this study. Our results are the first of their kind to link the tropical and subtropical TLS region using long-term RS and COSMIC data, and to estimate trends by accounting for natural periodic effect. The methodology and data availability are covered in section 4.1 and 4.2. Section 4.3 describes the results and discussion.

4.2 Data and the Analysis Methods

4.2.1 Radiosonde data

Radiosondes are battery-powered telemetry instrument packages that are carried into the atmosphere typically by a weather balloon; they measure altitude, pressure, temperature, relative humidity and wind (both speed and direction) at high altitudes and transmit them by radio to a ground receiver. Radiosonde observations have been carried out daily at the Addis Ababa synoptic meteorological station since 1969. The radiosonde data from Addis Ababa synoptic meteorological station has undergone quality checks by Global Radiosonde Archive (IGRA) through scrutinizing presence of physically implausible values, climatological outliers, and temporal and vertical inconsistencies in temperature (Durre et al., 2006). In this study, we use high-resolution Radio sounding data at tropical Addis Ababa station and subtropical Cairo station covering the period from 2006 - 2020. Before blowing up, weather balloons usually raise for 90 minutes are fewer, covers a distance of 19 to 32 km. In Ethiopia and Cairo station launched balloons burst after 25 km, the radiosonde data were accessed through CDAAC webpage (<https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds351.0/>).

4.2.2 COSMIC Satellite

Six microsattellites with cutting-edge GPS receivers for measuring radio occultation make up the Constellation observation system for meteorology, ionospheric and climate constellation (COSMIC). On April 15, 2006, the six COSMIC micro satellites were launched into a 512 km high, circular orbit with a 72° inclination. How the COSMIC satellite operates GPS satellites continuously transmit signals to Earth-based receivers; however, due to variations in Earth's atmosphere density with altitude, these signals are distorted in transit. Any slight bends in those signals before they are cut off by the Earth's horizon can be found and measured by COSMIC-2 satellites. Radio occultation, or the three minutes before the radio signal is cut off, provides scientists with almost real-time information on the Earth's atmosphere, including density, temperature, pressure, and water vapor. COSMIC's main goal is to expand the low-cost research method of refractive GPS radio occultation observations in order to get crucial data for weather and climate research, such as air temperature, moisture content, and pressure. The COSMIC data, used in this study were obtained from the following link: (<https://data.cosmic.ucar.edu/gnss-ro/cosmic2/nrt/>).

4.2.3 Proxy data for Natural Forcing

To support the background influences, we used additional proxy data sets in addition to the RS and COSMIC data. Aerosol index data corresponding to time t from 2006 to 2020, Quasi-Biennial east-west zonal winds at 30 hPa data as a proxy of QBO(t), Monthly mean Nino 3.4 index data as a proxy of ENSO(t), Oceanic influences index data as a proxy of IOD(t), and F10.7 solar radioflux data as a proxy of solar cycle activity SC(t). The Nino 3.4 index, which provides monthly mean temperature anomalies of the equatorial Pacific Ocean sea surface across $5^\circ\text{S} - 5^\circ\text{N}$, $120^\circ\text{E} - 170^\circ\text{W}$, was sourced from the following website: (<https://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/data/indices/ersst5.nino.mth.91-20.ascii>). (<ftp://ftp.geolab.nrcan.gc.ca/data/solarflux/monthly/averages/maver.txt>) is where the solar radioflux data for F10.7 was obtained. The website (<https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/met/ag/strat/produkte/qbo>) provided the QBO winds that were collected from the Singapore station between pressure levels of 70–10 hPa. The data on oceanic influences for IOD was obtained from the following (https://ioc3.unesco.org/oopc/state_of_the_ocean/sur/ind/dmi.php). The MODIS satellite provided the aerosol data, which were downloaded via the (<https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov>). The current study examined long-term variability and trend in the TLS region using the aforementioned proxy data sets.

4.2.4 Methods of analysis

4.2.4.1 Wavelet Analysis

Wavelet analysis is a relatively new technique that is an important addition to standard signal analysis methods. It provides information about what frequency band exists at what time interval. The wavelet transform uses multiresolution analysis which analyzes the signal at different frequencies with different resolutions. We applied wavelet analysis technique to identify dominant modes of tropospheric lower stratospheric oscillations (IOD, AO, SAO, QBO, ENSO and SF) by using RS and COSMIC temperature data in Addiss and Cairo station. Further information on wavelet technique has been furnished in methodology section 3.6.2 in chapter 3.

4.2.4.2 Multivariate linear regression Analysis (MLR)

A multivariate linear regression analysis has been performed on the long term monthly mean temperature signals to extract the intra–annual (annual and semiannual) and interannual (ENSO, SC, QBO, IOD and aerosol) components in the least square technique to fit the signals over the altitude range of 1 km to 25 km using 15 years of data (January 2006 to December 2020) over the tropical and subtropical regions. We followed the methodology mentioned by previous Authors (Randel and Cobb, 1994) in our work. At each altitude, we applied multivariate regression model equation as follows:

$$T(t, z) = \alpha(z) + \beta(z)t + \gamma(z)ENSO(t) + \delta(z)SF(t) + \epsilon(z)QBO(t) + \zeta(z)IOD(t) + \eta(z)Aerosol(t) + r(t) \quad (4.1)$$

Where $T(z,t)$ is an estimate of temperature measurements at a vertical height of $z(1-25 \text{ km})$ and time t denoting the number of month's from (2006–2020), β is the trend per month. The coefficients α , γ , δ , ϵ , ζ and η are determined in least squares sense. $\alpha(z)$ represents seasonal and intra–seasonal variations. $r(t)$ is the residual term. $\alpha(z)$ in the above equation is in the form:

$$\alpha(z) = a_o + \sum_{i=1}^2 [A_i \cos(\omega_i(t - p_i))] \quad (4.2a)$$

where $\omega_i = \frac{2\pi i}{12}$, t is time in month's, p_i is the phase of SAO and AO, a_o is constant, A_i is the amplitude of SAO and AO.

4.3 Result and Discussion

4.3.1 Long-term monthly and annual mean TLS Temperature variability in Addiss and Cairo Station

This section makes use of 15 years (2006–2020) of temperature data from RS and COSMIC satellite in the 1–25 km height range (Troposphere lower stratosphere or TLS). The tropical Addiss station’s monthly and annual mean temperature profiles in the height range of 1 to 25 km were illustrated in the contour shown in Figure 4.1 (a – d). The left vertical panels of Figure 4.1 (a & b) show the contours of monthly mean temperature variations from (a) RS and (b) COSMIC observations, while the right panel of Figure 4.1 (c & d) shows the annual mean temperature variations from (c) RS and (d) COSMIC observations over tropical Addiss Station. The tropical Addiss station’s monthly maximum and minimum temperature range is shown in Figure 4.1 (a & b) as 290 K, 190 K based on RS data and 300 K, 190 K based on COSMIC data respectively. The composite annual mean maximum and minimum temperatures are shown in the right panel of Figure 4.1 (c & d) at 296 K, 294 K from RS and 185 K, 180 K from COSMIC, respectively. In the lower troposphere, a strong annual oscillation (AO) is observed from COSMIC data in Figure 4.1 with a peak around June/July. In the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS), semiannual oscillations (SAO) are observed from RS data in Figure 4.1 (c), with peaks in February/March and again in July/August. A cold spot is noticed observable around 17 km in the solstice period (Jun/July) with a temperature of 183 K.

Similar analyses of the monthly mean and annual mean temperature profile for the subtropical Cairo station were depicted in Figure 4.2 (a – d), with contours representing the height range of 1–25 km. The monthly mean temperature variations from (a) RS and (b) COSMIC observations are contoured in the left vertical panels of Figure 4.2 (a & b), while the annual mean temperature variations from (c) RS and (d) COSMIC observations over subtropical Cairo Station are displayed in the right panel of Figure 4.2 (c & d). Based on Figure 4.2 (c & d) of the RS/COSMIC data, we have observed the presence of semiannual oscillation (SAO) in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS). This oscillation exhibits peaks in February/March and again in July/August. Additionally, we have identified an annual oscillation (AO) in the lower troposphere, which reaches its peak around June/July based on the RS/COSMIC data. Around 15.5 km in the summer (Jun/July/August), a cold spot with a temperature of 195 K is easily visible. The annual and semi-annual variations are the most prominent short-term climate signals. Many investigations into the annual and semi-annual cycle in the surface and UTLS region over tropical latitudes have been conducted in recent decades; however, only a few attempts

Figure 4.1: Vertical distribution of temperature variability in TLS region for monthly (a & b), and composite (c & d) from RS and COSMIC data in Addis station.

Figure 4.2: Vertical distribution of temperature variability in TLS region for monthly (a & b), and composite (c & d) from RS and COSMIC data in Cairo station.

have been made to analyse the AO & SAO in the sub-tropical latitudes. Our data demonstrates unequivocally the prevalence of strong AO oscillations up to the middle and high troposphere in both tropical and sub-tropical latitudes. The general consensus is that sensible heat transfer at the earth-air interface is mostly to blame for variations in temperature in the lower troposphere, while latent heat released during water vapor condensation is thought to be the primary cause of heating in the middle and higher troposphere (Asnani and Verma, 1977). Even earlier research (Frierson, 2006) stated that the latent heat release caused by thermal forcing in the troposphere is what creates the strong AO in temperature. In contrast, the stratosphere is observed to be colder in the winter and warmer in the summer, with the exception of higher latitudes when there is a dramatic increase in stratospheric warming. The ozone layer in the tropical atmosphere absorbs semi-annually changing solar UV flux, which causes SAO in stratospheric temperature (Mohanakumar and Kumar, 1998). However, at sub-tropical latitudes, the sub-tropical jet stream's (STJ) seasonal movement determines the occurrence of the AO and SAO components. If there is a significant half-yearly component to the jet stream's seasonal migration, the second harmonic in the subtropical temperatures will be marked. If the first harmonic dominates the movement, a first harmonic prevail in the annual march of the subtropical temperatures (ste; Gao et al., 1987; Keller et al., 2022; Meehl et al., 1998). According to (vAN LooN and Jenne, 1969), tropical and sub-tropical SAO (TSSAO) is most pronounced in the areas where the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) crosses the Equator twice a year, in particular, from Eastern Africa to the central Pacific Ocean. This is why our analysis shows pronounced signatures of SAO at UTLS region from both tropical and sub-tropical stations. Shea et al. (1995) discovered that a notable semi-annual variations in the winds in the tropics, with a maximum in the inter-monsoon months, was the cause of the temperature's TS-SAO, which peaks in the extreme seasons in the subtropics and reaches its maxima in the transitional seasons in the tropics. More recently, based on thermal budget analysis, (Shangguan and Wang, 2022) provided a tenable explanation for the SAO of temperature in the UTLS region. In the NH, the primary cause of the first temperature peak in February is dynamical heating, whereas a combination of moist and dynamical processes is responsible for the second peak in July. The additional energy budget analysis shows that there is much stronger vertical water vapor transportation and condensation in the upper troposphere, which results in a stronger summer temperature peak in the NHM.

Further, they investigate the connection between the surface – SAO and the UTLS – SAO. Since the surface – SAO is a coupled ocean – atmosphere phenomenon that is heavily influenced by the seasonal cycle of SSTs and the surface serves as the

atmosphere's primary energy source, it can be concluded that the SST – SAO primarily modifies the UTLS – SAO by altering the summer time moist heating, the autumn radiative cooling, and the dynamical heating. In our analysis, we observed a pronounced SAO signatures at the LS region in sub – tropical station Cairo compared to tropical station Addiss. we found that the sub – tropical station Cairo had a month – long delay in its AO oscillation peak (in July) compared to the tropical station Addiss (in June). This could be explained by the explanation provided by (James and Legras, 2008, 2009). They explained that From Hadley circulation, poleward transport of tropical air in the subtropical LS and equatorward transport of subtropical air in the tropical ascent are identified in the layer extending from the top of the winter subtropical jet to the isentrope 430 K. This bidirectional exchange layer's existence provides a clear explanation for the air mass's meridional transport between the tropical UTLS and the subtropical LS. Further they concluded based on rocket measurements, the newly entered tropical branch of tropospheric air mixes within the subtropical stratosphere over a month, and then mixes within the extratropics over an estimated period of 1 to 4 months (Appenzeller et al., 1996; Grewe et al., 2002; Read and Castrejón-Pita, 2012).

4.3.2 Tropopause height and its temperature variations in tropical station Addiss

In this section, using RS and COSMIC daily data for the tropical Addiss station, we were able to determine the frequency distribution of cold point tropopause height (CPT_h) and cold point tropopause temperature (CPT_t). We used the definition provided by the world meteorological Organization (WMO) to identify CPT_h and CPT_t from daily temperature profiles of RS and COSMIC data from 2006 to 2020 (Hoinka et al., 1996; Krzyscin et al., 2007). Figure 4.3 (a & b) depicts the frequency distribution of CPT_h for the Addiss station, based on COSMIC and RS data. The range of CPT_h values from RS is 14–18.8 km, with a mean of 17.1 km and a standard deviation (std) of 0.69 km. On the other hand, the range of CPT_h values from COSMIC is 14.5–19.4 km, with a mean of 17.3 km and standard deviation (std) of 1.17 km. The Gaussian fit is superimposed on Figure 4.3 (a & b). Moving on to Figure 4.3 (c & d) displays the frequency distribution of the CPT_t for the Addiss station, based on RS and COSMIC data. The range of CPT_t values from RS is 182.45 to 200 K, with a mean of 190.86 K and standard deviation (std) of 2.84 K. From COSMIC observations, the range of CPT_t values is 183 to 210 K, with a mean of 194.64 K and a std of 6.63K. The Gaussian fit is also shown in Figure 4.3 (c & d).

Figure 4.3: Frequency distribution of daily (a) CPTH in *RS*, (b) CPTH in *COSMIC*, (c) CPTt in *RS* and (d) CPTt in *COSMIC* Over Addiss Ababa, Ethiopia during the year from 2006 to 2020 obtained from the *RS* and *COSMIC*. The solid red line shows a Gaussian fit.

4.3.3 Tropopause height and its temperature variations in subtropical Cairo station

In this section, using *RS* and *COSMIC* daily data from the subtropical Cairo station, we were able to determine the frequency distribution of cold point tropopause height (CPTH) and cold point tropopause temperature (CPTt). Figure 4.4 (a & b) depicts the frequency distribution of CPTH for the Cairo station, based on *RS* and *COSMIC* data. The range of CPTH values from *RS* is 14.5 to 16.8 km, with a mean of 15.87 km and standard deviation (std) of 0.49 km. On the other hand, the range of CPTH values from *COSMIC* is 14.8 to 16.9 km, with a mean of 15.51 km and std of 0.53 km. The Gaussian fit is superimposed on Figure 4.4 (a & b). Two crests can be seen in Figure 4.4 (a) in the CPTH frequency distribution: one is roughly centered at 15.3 km, while the other is close to 15.8 km. Figure 4.4 (b), one crest at 15.9 km, can be seen in the CPTH frequency distribution. Figure 4.4 (c & d) displays the frequency distribution of CPTt for the Cairo station based on *RS* and *COSMIC* data. The frequency distribution of CPTt ranges from 187 to 216 K from *RS* with a mean of 201.43 K associated with standard deviation (std) of 4.26 K, while from *COSMIC* data it ranges from 188 to 216.2 K with a mean of 201.78 K associated with std of 4.98 K. Figure 4.4 (c & d) shows the Gaussian fit to the frequency distribution of CPTt. Figure 4.4 (c & d) show that there are two distinct crests in the frequency

Figure 4.4: Frequency distribution of daily (a) CPT_h in *RS*, (b) CPT_t in *RS*, (c) CPT_h in *COSMIC* and (d) CPT_t in *COSMIC* Over Cairo, Egypt during the year from 2006 to 2020 obtained from the *RS* and *COSMIC*. The solid red line shows a Gaussian fit.

distribution of the CPT_t. Figure 4.4 (c) shows a crest located roughly at 205 K, while Figure 4.4 (d) shows a crest located approximately at 202 K. In the subtropical zone of Egypt, Cairo, (Zhran et al., 2019) have reported similar results.

4.3.4 Periodic oscillations from cold point tropopause height (CPT_h) and cold point tropopause temperature (CPT_t) over tropical station Addiss and subtropical station Cairo

In this section, we use the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) technique to extract both long and short term periodic oscillations from monthly mean TLS (1 to 25 km) temperatures obtained from *RS* and *COSMIC* data. The first vertical panel of Figure 4.5 (a & c) displays the time series data of CPT_h values for the tropical station Addiss from 2006 to 2020 derived from *RS* and *COSMIC* data, while the second vertical panel of Figure 4.5 (b & d) displays the corresponding wavelet spectrum. The amplitude of the wavelet spectrum of CPT_h is up to 3 km, and it shows that SAO, AO, QBO, and ENSO are prominent during the observational period. The first vertical panel of Figure 4.6 (a & c) displays the time series data of CPT_h values for the subtropical station Cairo from 2006 to 2020 derived from *RS* and *COSMIC* data, while the second vertical panel of Figure 4.6 (b & d) displays the corresponding wavelet spectrum. The wavelet spectrum of CPT_h indicates that AO, QBO, and ENSO are prominent during the observational period. The amplitude of these effects

Figure 4.5: (a & c) Time series monthly mean CPTH and (b & d) its corresponding wavelet spectrum in Addiss station from 2006 to 2020

can reach up to 2.3 km from RS and 2.9 km from COSMIC data. The small amplitude can be attributed to the distribution of energy spectra over time. Figure 4.7 (a & c) first vertical panel displays the time series data of CPTt values for the Addiss station from 2006 to 2020, while the second vertical panel Figure 4.7 (b & d) displays the corresponding wavelet spectrum. The CPTt's wavelet spectrum, seen in Figure 4.7 (b & d), indicates the existence of strong AO (QBO, SAO, and ENSO are minor oscillations).

Similar to this, Figure 4.8 (a & c) first vertical panel displays the time series data of CPTt values for the subtropical Cairo station from 2006 to 2020, while Figure 4.8 (b & d) second vertical panel displays the corresponding wavelet spectrum. The CPTt's wavelet spectrum, which indicates the existence of significant AO and SAO from the Figure 4.8 (b & d). According to several researchers, variations in solar radiation and ENSO, which affect atmospheric convection, are attributed for the AO and SAO in the tropopause temperature across different geographic locations. In the tropopause height and temperature over the tropical latitudes, there exists a QBO signal, according to reports from (Randel et al., 2000, 2003; Shimizu and Tsuda, 2000). In addition, our analysis shows that, in comparison to CPTt observations, the strong QBO like signal predominates in CPTH values. Furthermore, CPTH values exhibit long–period oscillations such as QBO and ENSO signals, while CPTt observations reveal short period oscillations like AO and SAO. This variability is described to tropical convection activity. Since earlier research (Gettelman et al., 2002b; Jain et al., 2006) revealed that the intensity of convection controls the upward and downward movement of the tropopause height.

Figure 4.6: (a & c)Time series monthly mean CPT_{th} and (b & d) its corresponding wavelete spectrum in Cairo station from 2006 to 2020

Figure 4.7: (a & c)Time series monthly mean CPT_t and (b & d) its corresponding wavelete spectrum in Addiss Ababa station from 2006 to 2020

Figure 4.8: (a & c) Time series monthly mean CPTt and (b & d) its corresponding wavelet spectrum in Cairo station from 2006 to 2020

4.3.5 The periodicity of the troposphere and lower stratosphere temperature (TLST) variations

We used wavelet analysis on time series temperature data from RS and COSMIC at 5 km intervals for tropical station Addiss to determine whether inter and intra seasonal oscillations exist in the entire tropospheric (2 – 18 km) and lower stratospheric (19 – 25 km) region. The results are shown in Figure 4.9. Figure 4.9 (a – e) left panel shows the wavelet spectrum of TLS temperature using RS over Addiss station from 2006 to 2020, at intervals of 5 km. The cone of influence (COI) at 95 % confidence levels is shown by the thick, solid line. The dominant oscillation of AO and ENSO is observed in the tropospheric region (2 – 18 km). Above 15 km, the QBO and SAO signals are initiated and appeared. Only AO and QBO are visible at 20 km Figure 4.9(d). The troposphere and lower stratosphere in particular show the notable amplitudes of AO. SAO is another significant oscillation that is present in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (ULS). When compared to the 5 km, 10 km, 15 km, and 25 km, the temporal evolution of AO for the 20 km is marginally different. A notable interannual variation in the 15 km is also observed. At 15 km, the SAO, AO, and QBO are relatively robust during the months of 85 – 110 (2013 – 2014 years). Therefore, with the exception of (20 & 25 km), 5 km, 10 km, 15 km, exhibit similar behaviors in the evolution of prominent oscillations. In the TLS region, long period oscillations AO, ENSO, and QBO appear to be very strong oscillations. Using COSMIC data from 2006 to 2020 over the tropical station Addiss, the wavelet spectrum of TLS temperature at 5 km intervals are shown in the right panel of Figure 4.9 (f – j). The two main oscillations seen in the lower troposphere, at around 5 km, are AO and

ENSO Figure 4.9 (f). Only AO and SAO oscillations are dominant at 10–15 km, particularly in the months of 90 – 105 (2013 – 2014 years). SAO oscillations are dominant at this time and are thought to be caused by the prevailing of kelvin waves, while QBO signals are seen at upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (15–25 km).

In a similar vein, Figure 4.10 (a – j) shows the wavelet analysis of time series temperature data for the subtropical station Cairo from RS and COSMIC at intervals of every 5 km. The wavelet spectrum of TLS temperature using RS at 5 km intervals over Cairo station from 2006 to 2020 is shown in the left panel of Figure 4.10 (a – e). The monthly mean tropospheric and lower stratospheric temperature variations are displayed in Figure 4.10 (a – e) at intervals of 5 km in five vertical zones (5 km, 10 km, 15 km, 20 km and 25 km), with the dominant ENSO, QBO, AO, and SAO oscillations. All tropospheric levels (1–18 km) and lower stratospheric levels (19–25 km) exhibit dominance of the interannual oscillations AO and SAO respectively. The presence of SAO can be observed at all heights, except for weak amplitudes at 5 km. On the other hand, AO is dominant at all height levels, except for a weak amplitude at 20 km. Throughout the entire period from 2006 to 2020, QBO (22–36 months) is displayed at heights of 15 km, 20 km, and 25 km, with varying amplitudes. Similarly, ENSO (22–84 months) with varying amplitudes was recorded at heights of 15 km, 20 km, and 25 km during the same period. The right panel of Figure 4.10 (f – j) illustrates the TLS temperature wavelet spectrum using COSMIC data collected over Cairo station between 2006 and 2020, with 5 km intervals. The monthly mean tropospheric and lower stratospheric temperature variations are shown in Figure 4.10 (f – j) with dominant AO, SAO, ENSO, and QBO oscillations, at 5 km intervals in five vertical zones (5 km, 10 km, 15 km, 20 km, and 25 km). It is evident that the interannual and intra-annual oscillations QBO, ENSO, and AO, SAO, respectively, dominate the lower stratospheric levels (19–25 km) and all tropospheric levels (1–18 km). SAO is present at all heights, except for weak amplitudes at 5 and 10 km, while AO is dominant at all height levels, except for weak amplitudes at 20 and 25 km. Long-term oscillations such as ENSO and QBO are displayed at heights of 15 km, 20 km, and 25 km with varying amplitudes throughout the entire period (2006-2020).

4.3.6 Vertical distribution of AO and SAO at TLS region over tropical and subtropical stations

The vertical distribution of amplitude and phases of AO and SAO oscillations are derived by applying harmonic analysis using FFT analysis to monthly mean temperature data at every 1 km interval of TLS region from RS and COSMIC data. Using data from RS and COSMIC, Figure 4.11 (a & b) shows the vertical distribution of AO

Figure 4.9: Wavelete analysis of TLST RS and COSMIC data in Addiss Ababa

Figure 4.10: Wavelete analysis of TLST RS and COSMIC data in Cairo

and SAO oscillation amplitudes over Addis station and their corresponding phases are shown in months in Figure 4.11 (e & f). It is abundantly clear from Figure 4.11 (e & f) that the minimum amplitude of AO is observed at 18 km with amplitude of 7 K and corresponding minimum phase of 10 months at 24 km, while the maximum amplitude of AO reached at 3 km with amplitude of 15 K and corresponding maximum phase of 12 month at 18 km from both RS and COSMIC data. Figure 4.11 (b & f) makes it abundantly clear that the minimum amplitude of the SAO is observed at 4 km & 16 km with an amplitude of 0.13 K and a corresponding minimum phase of a month at 6km & 13km, while the maximum amplitude is reached at 18 km with an amplitude of 0.97 K and a corresponding maximum phase of 6 months at 22 km from both RS and COSMIC data. Similar to the vertical distribution of SAO and AO amplitudes for the subtropical Cairo station shown in Figure 4.11 (c & g), It clearly illustrates that the minimum amplitude of 3 K is observed at 14 km with a corresponding minimum phase of 0.5 month at 15 km, and the maximum amplitude of AO is reached at 8 km with an amplitude of 9.5 K and a corresponding maximum phase of 10 months at 9 km from both RS and COSMIC data. Figure 4.11 (d & h) makes it evident that the minimum amplitude of the SAO is observed at 4 km & 15 km with an amplitude of 0.03 K and a corresponding minimum phase at 4 & 14 km, while the maximum amplitude is reached at 11 km & 16 km with an amplitude of 3.5 K & 2.1 K and a corresponding maximum phase of 5 months at 18 km and again 6 months at 19 km from both RS and COSMIC data. Cairo's AO and SAO amplitudes are larger in magnitude than Addiss station's. Our findings regarding the amplitudes of AO and SAO in the TLS region are somewhat consistent with research using RS and COSMIC data carried out by (Seidel et al., 2001). Furthermore, our findings that the TLS region has a greater predominance of AO magnitude than SAO are consistent with those of (Awange et al., 2015).

4.3.7 Troposphere lower stratosphere temperature responses to natural influence and temperature trends over tropical and subtropical stations

Prior research suggests that, in addition to AO and SAO signals, long-term periodicities and signals like QBO, ENSO, SF, and IOD should be present in the long-term temperature variability in the TLS region (Bègue et al., 2010; Bencherif et al., 2006). By using proxy data of QBO, ENSO, SF, IOD, and aerosol index, we can examine the impact of natural long period oscillations on the temperature of the TLS region. The time series of proxy data for the ENSO, IOD, F10.7 solar flux, aerosol, and QBO oscillations in the zonal mean wind at Singapore station at a pressure of 30 hPa are shown in Figure 4.12 (a–d) for the years 2006 to 2020. High solar activity has a positive impact that is evident from 2013 to 2014. According to Calvo et al. (2010); Hio and Yoden (2005), the QBO and ENSO are well-known dominant modes of

Figure 4.11: Amplitudes observed in (a) AO, (b) SAO, (c) AO and (d) SAO over Addis and Cairo location obtained using measurements of RS and COSMIC (2006 – 2020) respectively. The corresponding phases are shown in panels (e – h)

tropical tropospheric and stratospheric inter-annual variability. Figure 4.13 (a – e) displays the temperature response to the following indices: (a) IOD, (b) ENSO, (c) Solar flux, (d) QBO, and (e) aerosol, derived through regression analysis using both ground based RS and satellite COSMIC data as a function of altitude for tropical station Addis. Higher altitudes are found to have greater variability in each climate oscillation, particularly in solar flux and QBO in both data sets. It is evident that while IOD and ENSO are larger in the UTLS region, whereas the QBO is larger in the upper troposphere (UT) region at tropical Addis station. The interannual variability of temperature in the tropical stratosphere is significantly influenced by the QBO (Baldwin et al., 2001). The equatorial troposphere shows variability on the timescale of the QBO, but a direct link to the stratospheric QBO has not been established. QBO may influence the high latitude northern troposphere through its effect on the stratospheric polar vortex. Coupling between stratospheric zonal mean wind and the mid tropospheric North Atlantic Oscillation is strong, but the cause and effect are not clear. It is possible that QBO induced high latitude wind anomalies penetrate downward into the troposphere (Gray, 2003, 1984). The majority of QBO observations are dominated at a height of around 20 to 25 km, which corresponds to the 30 hPa pressure level. Many scholars just used single pressure surfaces, such as 30 hPa, 40 hPa, 50 hPa, etc., when examining the temperature trend of the lower and middle atmosphere (Bègue et al., 2010; Sivakumar et al., 2011). A strong ENSO minimum of $-0.1\text{K}/\text{SOI}$ is reported at tropical station Addis around 18 km, while a strong ENSO maximum of $0.4\text{K}/\text{SOI}$ is observed from RS/COSMIC at 8 km. Since QBO generates near UTLS, a high positive response is detected from 6 to 21 km. For both RS and COSMIC data, QBO displays maximal response around upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (19–25 km). For solar flux, there is almost null response at all TLS levels. Aerosols show their largest response below 10 km in both RS and COSMIC data, as they are created and transported mostly below lower troposphere (Kerzenmacher et al., 2006). Oceanic indicators such as ENSO and IOD have shown a maximum influence at about 5–15 km. For instance, it has been demonstrated that ENSO influences Walker circulation, or global circulation through the tropospheric area, which influences Ethiopia’s climate (Gebregiorgis et al., 2019).

Regression analysis utilizing both ground-based RS and satellite COSMIC data is used in Figure 4.13 (f – j) to show the temperature response for the subtropical station Cairo as a function of altitude to the following indices: (f) IOD, (g) ENSO, (h) Solar flux, (i) QBO, and (j) aerosol. From RS/COSMIC, strong positive maximum responses for IOD, ENSO, solar flux, QBO, and aerosol are identified at heights of 15, 23, 19, 25, and 16 km, respectively, with amplitudes of 0.24, 0.2, 0.18, 0.14, and 0.8 K. Strong ENSO and QBO signals are present around 12 and 22 km with

Figure 4.12: Monthly variation of (a) SOI, (b) IOD, (c) Solar flux and (d) Aerosol Cairo and Addiss and (e) QBO in zonal wind for January 2006 – December 2020.

Figure 4.13: monthly mean temperature variability response to (a & f) IOD, (b & g) ENSO, (c & h) SF, (d & i) QBO, (e & j) aerosol, during a 15 year period as a function of altitude using RS and COSMIC data in Addiss and Cairo station. In the upper panel (a – e) is Addiss and the lower panel (f – j) is Cairo. the blue line indicates RS observation, red line indicates COSMIC observation, green line indicates temperature measure of RS error (RSE) and black line indicates temperature measure of COSMIC error (COSE)

negative minimum of -0.13 and -0.09. Large errors noted in the Addiss station's atmospheric temperature response to natural forcing, including IOD, ENSO, SSF, QBO, and aerosol, ranges from 20-25 km, 9-15 km and 20-25 km, 6-25 km, 2-25 km and 17-25 km, respectively displays in Figure 4.13 (a – e). Similar to this, Figure 4.13 (f – j) shows that there are higher inaccuracies in the atmospheric temperature response of IOD, ENSO, SSF, and QBO in Cairo station from 1-11 km, 1-10 km, 1-15 km, and 1-11 km, respectively. There is not much error in the aerosols seen in Cairo Station. Figure 4.14 (a – e) for the tropical station Addiss and Figure 4.14 (f – j) for the subtropical station Cairo display the lag (months) versus height, respectively, derived from lag analyses utilizing the cross correlation technique on temperature and natural forcings. COSMIC observations are represented with a red solid line, while RS observations are displayed as blue solid lines. With the exception of oceanic oscillations (ENSO and IOD show a 3-4 month lag), and SSF (shows a 3 month lag), we conclude that all atmospheric natural forcing caused a one-month delay in the upper and lower troposphere (below the tropopause, or 15 km) temperature for the Addiss and Cairo stations. There was a 3-4 month lag in both stations and observations due to all natural forcings above the tropopause.

Figure 4.14: monthly mean temperature variability lag to (a & f) IOD, (b & g) ENSO, (c & h) SF, (d & i) QBO, (e & j) aerosol, during a 15 year period as a function of altitude using RS and COSMIC data in Addis and Cairo station. In the upper panel (a – e) is Addis and the lower panel (f – j) is Cairo. the blue line indicates RS observation and red line indicates COSMIC observation

Using the MLR technique described in the methodology section, we generated the trend per decade at 1-km altitude intervals while accounting for the response of natural forces. Figure 4.15(a) and Figure 4.15(b) display the profile of trend for both stations, respectively. The height profile of Addis’s long-term trends in the TLS region displayed in Figure 4.15(a) reveals lower troposphere is warming from both COSMIC (0.01 K per decade) and RS (0.27 K per decade). Our results, for tropical regions ranging from 0.1 to 0.15 K, are clearly in line with previous reports (Gray, 2006; Karl, 2012). Temperature trends show a cooling trend beginning at 5 to 15 km and peaking at -0.16 K per decade for RS and -0.35 K per decade for COSMIC. Our findings are in complete agreement with earlier reports by (Angell, 1988), (Oort and Liu, 1993), (Parker et al., 1997), and (Bencherif et al., 2006), which found that the difference was -0.16 K per decade, -0.11 K per decade, -0.11 K per decade and -0.101 K per decade respectively. A warming trend is seen above the 15 km UTLS region, with a maximum warming of 0.14 K/decade from RS; however, COSMIC indicates a cooling rate. In the height range of 8 to 11 km, 15 to 19 km, and 23 to 25 km, there is an increasing trend in temperature (> -0.1 K/decade). A small increasing trend is seen at about 2 to 25 km, with three peaks located at 3 km (0.29 K/decade), 11 km (~ 0.09 K/decade), and 19 km (0.12 K/decade). Within the altitude range of 4 to 8 km, 11 to 14 km, and 20 to 23 km, there is a slight decreasing

Figure 4.15: Long term trends in the Troposphere lower stratosphere mean temperature variability as a function of altitude over the periods of 2006 – 2020. the blue line indicates RS observation and red line indicates COSMIC observation whereas the horizontal blue and red line shows there errors.

trend in temperature (< 0.2 K/decade). The error bars are shown by the horizontal line. Error magnitude is more in the Addiss station at 2 km, 11 km, 14 km, 17 km, 20 km, and 25 km. The height profile of long–term trends in Cairo’s TLS region is displayed in Figure 4.15 (b) based on observations from both COSMIC and RS. A warming trend in the lower troposphere is noted by COSMIC (0.1 K/decade) and RS (0.3 K/decade). A cooling trend in temperature is noted starting at 5–15 km, reaching a maximum of -0.25 K/decade for RS and -0.18 K/decade for COSMIC. A warming trend was noted above the 15 km UTLS region, with maximum warming reported by RS at 0.1 K/decade and COSMIC at 0.2 K/decade. Within the height range of 10 to 18 km, there is a slight increasing trend in temperature (greater than 0.2 K/decade). A slightly increasing trend is seen at 17 km (0.19 K/decade), around 16–18 km. Above 20 km increment reaches its maximum of 0.28 K/decade. Similarly at 1 km, 9 km, 15 km, 19 km, 24 km and 25 km more error is observed in Cairo station. The vertical structure of tropospheric warming and stratospheric cooling is caused by variations in stratospheric ozone as a response to human emissions of ozone-depleting substances (ODS) and the radiative effect of rising greenhouse gas (GHG) (Manabe and Wetherald, 1967; Ramaswamy and Schwarzkopf, 2002). Together with the temporal and spatial variations in the related temperature shifts, the complex vertical patterns of stratospheric cooling and tropospheric warming serve as indications of the relevant driving processes. Using satellite data and model simula-

tions, Randel et al. (2016) found that SSTs had a greater influence in the troposphere and very lowest in the stratosphere during the 1979 – 1997 tropospheric warming period compared to 1998 – 2014. However, their influence was negligible above 20 km. Previous studies (Oberländer et al., 2013; Polvani and Solomon, 2012) have conducted calculations to differentiate the specific impacts of greenhouse gases, Ozone - depleting substances, and sea surface temperatures on variations in temperature between the troposphere and stratosphere. These studies have consistently shown that sea surface temperatures have a minimal effect above 20 km, but exert a significant influence in the troposphere and lower stratosphere. Radiative effects typically a warm bias during the day from sunlight heating the sensor and a cold bias at night from the sensor emitting longwave radiation are the main cause of radiosonde temperature biases, where the sensor temperature differs from the air temperature. Smaller errors are brought on by lags in the sensor’s response to changing temperatures as the radiosonde rises. The physical characteristics and mounting of the sensor, as well as environmental factors like surface temperature, solar elevation angle (SEA), temperature lapse rate, ventilation velocity, and clouds, all affect the longwave and shortwave fluxes around the sensor and affect the bias (Bower and Fitzgibbon, 2003, 2004; Luers and Eskridge, 1995, 1998; Mattioli et al., 2007; McMillin et al., 1992). As widely recognized, Radiosonde (RS) can measure with adequate precision up to 25 to 30 km above the surface; beyond that distance, its accuracy may be compromised. Naturally, COSMIC satellite data measures data up to 59 km from the ground, although the resolution is less around 12 to 10 km. This explains why the difference between COSMIC and RS at Addiss station varies very little below 10 km.

Chapter 5

Observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data

The earlier chapters primarily discussed the temperature trends in relation to understanding the impacts of various natural drivers such as the Aerosol effect, IOD, ENSO, QBO, and SF in the TLS region. The focus of this chapter is to examine the observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosond and AIRS satellite temperature data. The findings presented in this chapter have been submitted to the journal of Advance space research by Tsehay N and Prakash Raju (2024).

5.1 Introduction

Equatorial kelvin waves serve as the fundamental building blocks of many aspects of tropical weather and climate (Wheeler and Nguyen, 2015). They are geophysical fluid waves, existing for a range of spatial and temporal scales, which are trapped near the equator. They propagate in the zonal and vertical directions, and may exist at any altitude level in the atmosphere or depth in the ocean. They cause oscillations in the pressure, temperature, and winds or currents, with the magnitude of such oscillations being large enough to cause changes the weather. Equatorial waves are important for their organized contributions to tropical upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) circulation, constituent transport, stratospheric dehydration and cloud formation processes. Equatorial waves In the UTLS play a crucial role in driving the stratospheric QBO and SAO. Therefore, it is essential to accurately asses wave behavior through observations and utilize measurements to assess and limit models. Atmospheric temperature variability in the tropics is coupled with dynamical and physical processes, which have a crucial impact on the Earths climate. Variability in the tropical tropopause region is of special interest because it has an important role in troposphere – stratosphere coupling and exchange (Fueglistaler et al., 2009; Holton et al., 1995) and associated global radiation budget. Thus, detailed knowledge of dynamical processes in the tropical upper troposphere and lower stratosphere is essential for better understanding climate variability and change. It has been found, that decadal variations in global surface climate may be significantly influenced by changes in stratospheric water vapor (Solomon et al., 2010), which

is controlled by temperatures near the tropical tropopause. Furthermore, vertically propagating equatorial waves, which originate from the troposphere and propagate into the upper atmosphere, are main drivers of global-scale zonal wind variation, which is called the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO). The QBO manifests itself as alternating easterly and westerly zonal winds in the tropical stratosphere with a period of approximately 28 months. It has large impacts on the entire global atmosphere (Baldwin et al., 2001). Diabatic heating by organized tropical convection can excite atmospheric equatorial waves, which control the spatial and temporal distribution of convective heating (Dunkerton, 1989). Equatorial atmospheric waves, including eastward propagating Kelvin waves, are generated by heating associated with convection (Alexander and Pfister, 1995; Alexander and Tsuda, 2008; Garcia and Salby, 1987; Karoly et al., 1996; Tsuda et al., 1994; Vincent and Joan Alexander, 2000; Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999). Atmospheric equatorial kelvin waves were theorized by Matsuno (1966) and Holton and Lindzen (1968) and first observed by Wallace and Kousky (1968). Equatorial kelvin waves can propagate vertically in regions of background easterly winds, while they become trapped below regions of westerly winds, and they exhibit strong interactions with the stratospheric QBO (Sato and Dunkerton, 1997). Equatorial kelvin waves dominate sub-seasonal variability in the tropical tropopause region (Tindall et al., 2006). They modulate the height and temperature of the tropical tropopause (Shimizu and Tsuda, 1997; Tsuda et al., 1994) and were found to be important for cirrus formation and dehydration of air entering the lower stratosphere (Fujiwara et al., 2001). Furthermore, they play an important role in stratosphere–troposphere exchange of ozone. Equatorial Kelvin waves in the lower stratosphere commonly occur with periods of order 10–20 days and are known as slow Kelvin waves or Wallace–Kousky waves (Maruyama, 1968; Wallace and Kousky, 1968). What is commonly referred to as fast waves with periods of 6–10 days in the stratosphere (Hirota, 1979) and the 3–6 day period ultra-fast waves in the stratosphere–mesosphere are now well–established (Canziani et al., 1995; Riggan et al., 1997; Salby et al., 1984).

Equatorial kelvin waves have been identified using radiosonde temperature and wind measurements (Tsuda et al., 1994; Wallace and Kousky, 1968). Due to the limited spatial coverage of the radiosonde network, observations were confined to a few specific locations. Radiosonde observations though have the advantage of high vertical resolution, but they lack global coverage particularly over oceanic regions. In order to study the global behaviour and horizontal propagation characteristics of these waves, satellite-based measurements are more useful because they offer global coverage (Hirota, 1979). Later, satellite temperature measurements provided a more global view on atmospheric dynamics. Equatorial atmospheric kelvin waves have

been investigated using satellite data from Nimbus-7 LIMS (Limb Infrared Monitor of the Stratosphere) (Salby et al., 1984), from Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) (Mote et al., 2002), and from High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS) (Alexander and Ortland, 2010). Kelvin waves have been identified in the troposphere lower stratosphere using COSMIC (Anthes et al., 2008; Brahmanandam et al., 2010; Das et al., 2022; Randel and Wu, 2005). Ofcourse literature search reveals null report on subtropical kelvin wave analysis, which motivates to take up this work. Moreover previous researchers concentrates on $5^{\circ}N$ - $5^{\circ}S$ belt of equatorial kelvin wave observations. We extended latitudinal belt for tropics 0 - $15^{\circ}N$ in addition to subtropical bands of 22 - $30^{\circ}N$. This work is first of its kind to observe kelvin wave analysis from subtropics using RS and AIRS satellite observations over a period of March 2019 - February 2020. The methodology and data availability are covered in section 5.2. Section 5.3 describes the results and the discussion.

5.2 Data and the Analysis Methods

5.2.1 AIRS data

The Atmospheric Infrared Sounder (AIRS) instrument is one of six instruments aboard NASA Aqua satellite, which has been operating in a nearly polar, low earth orbit (705 km altitude, 98.2 inclination, 100 min period) since May 2002. The observations provide nearly global coverage with 14.4 orbits per day in a sun - synchronous orbit. We use the version 6 standard Level 3 data from AIRS/AMSU combined retrievals (Tian et al., 2013) on a daily timescale, taking the arithmetic mean from both ascending and descending nodes of the orbit when available. Data is analyzed with $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ grid horizontal resolution, centered on the half degree, which we then averaged to shift to the full degree. Data are available from March 2019 through February 2020. Data are analyzed on standard pressure levels (primarily 10, 70, and 100 hPa). Through the troposphere AIRS temperature retrievals have a vertical resolution of about 2 km, however in the stratosphere the vertical resolution is not sufficiently known due to uncertainties in the weighing functions. Launched into Earth-orbit on May 4, 2002 aboard NASAs Aqua satellite, the Atmospheric Infrared Sounder, AIRS, provides data critical to the monitoring of Earths atmosphere. The AIRS on NASA's Aqua satellite, gathers infrared energy emitted from Earth's surface and atmosphere globally, every day. Its data provides 3D measurements of temperature and water vapor through the atmospheric column along with a host of trace gases, surface and cloud properties. AIRS data are used by weather prediction centers around the world to improve their forecasts. They are also used to assess the skill of climate models and in applications ranging from volcanic plume detection to drought forecasting. AIRS uses cutting edge infrared technology to create three-dimensional maps of air and sur-

face temperature, water vapor, and cloud properties. With 2378 spectral channels, AIRS has a spectral resolution more than 100 times greater than previous infrared sounders and provides more accurate information on the vertical profiles of atmospheric temperature and moisture. AIRS can also measure trace greenhouse gases such as ozone, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and methane. AIRS temperature profiles have an accuracy in the troposphere that matches the accuracy achieved by radiosondes launched from ground stations.

5.2.2 Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR) data

The daily Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR) data is available in latitude-longitude grids from the AIRS satellite. This data measures the amount of terrestrial radiation released into space and provides insights into cloud cover and water vapor in the atmosphere. The record spans from 1979 to the present and is primarily derived from high-resolution infrared radiation sounder (HIRS) observations, as well as data from newer infrared hyperspectral sounders like the Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer (IASI) and the Cross-track Infrared Sounder (CrIS). In this study we take the OLR data available with the NOAA earth system research laboratory under physical sciences division, averaged over 22 - 35° N and 0 - 15° N from March 2019 to February 2020. The daily OLR data is available 2.5° x 2.5° latitude - longitude grid, with data gaps filled by linear interpolation to provide complete sampling. When OLR values are low, it indicates strong convection.

5.2.3 Methods of Analysis

5.2.3.1 Fast Fourier transform Analysis

Fast Fourier transform (FFT) is the most commonly used method for estimating frequency spectra of evenly sampled data (Cooley and Tukey, 1965). It enables the approximation of a time series sampled from a continuous distribution over discrete time steps, through a series of complex sine and cosine waves with varying frequencies. The expected Fourier transform of a discretized signal is given by the convolution of the true transform and the transform of a Dirac comb window function designating those measurement times (VanderPlas, 2018). We applied 2-D FFT analysis technique to identify the periodicity of upper tropospheric lower stratospheric kelvin wave oscillations by using RS and AIRS temperature data in Addis and Cairo station. Interested readers may refer the theory of 2 D FFT technique by (Babu and Stoica, 2010; Munteanu et al., 2016).

5.2.3.2 Curve Fitting

Equatorial Kelvin waves have the strongest amplitudes at the equator with zonal wave number 1 and 2 predominant (Mote et al., 2002). To isolate dominant wave

Figure 5.1: Temperature data (blue color) at 17 km from a - d in Addis station and e - h in Cairo station on 10 March 2019, 10 June 2019, 10 Sep 2019, and 10 December 2019, respectively, and red label for the sinusoidal fitting using AIRS data

numbers, a fitting function,

$$T(\lambda, d) = \sum_{i=1}^2 [A_i \sin(\omega_i(\lambda - p_i))] \quad (5.1)$$

where $\omega_i = \frac{2\pi i}{P}$, λ is longitude, p_i is the phase of wave, P is periodicity of the wave, $T(\lambda, d)$ is temperature in a function of longitude and days, A_i is the amplitude of the wave. Mixing with wave 1 and wave 2 components is then applied to best fit the temperature fluctuations of T' data with the amplitude A and phase p for all longitudes λ solved by means of a nonlinear least-square method. Figure 5.1 (b) shows a sinusoidal fit with 198 - 200 K peak-to-peak oscillation derived from the atmospheric temperature (T) data at 17 km altitude in the equatorial region during 10 June, 2019. The back ground temperature profile T_o (fitted model temperature) curve reveals a mixed wave with wave 1 and wave 2 components. When this data processing is carried out over a longer span of time, the time evolution of large scale zonal waves propagation is revealed. Figure 5.1 (a - h) illustrates the application of T and fitted T_o to a time series at altitudes of 17 km from March 2019 to February 2020.

5.2.3.3 Kelvin Wave Identification Procedure

The atmospheric temperature profile is believed to be composed of the background and fluctuating temperature profiles due to different oscillation mode waves such as kelvin waves. Identifying the characteristics of kelvin waves from the temperature profiles requires removing the background temperature profile. Sinusoidal fitting has been usually applied to estimate the background temperature profiles (Mote et al., 2002). In the present study, the background temperature profile variations are estimated by sinusoidal fitting explained by (Tsuda et al., 1994), and hence the temperature profiles are estimated by subtracting the background quantity from the original measurements. The following procedure has been adopted to extract kelvin wave characteristics in the AIRS temperature profiles. In the first step, the temperature data has been interpolated to 0.5 km. It is to be noted that the original AIRS data are available at 1 km vertical resolution and have an effective vertical resolution on the order of 1.5 km or above in the UTLS and stratospheric region. Due to the high inclination 98.2 orbit of AIRS satellites, the temperature profiles data occurrence rates around the equator are rather sparse and hence an interpolation method in longitude has been applied on the temperature profile data to fill-in the missing data starting from ground to 30 km altitudes. Figure 5.1 depicted in previous section displays the longitudinal temperature profile (blue circles) at 17 km on 10 March 2019, on 10 June 2019, on 10 September 2019 and on 10 December 2019 over the entire equatorial region super imposed by sinusoidal fit (red solid circles). In the second step, we use a sinusoidal T_o to best fit to the interpolated data, which is considered to be background temperature (RS or AIRS temperature T) variation. The background values were then removed from each temperature profile corresponding to each altitude and the resulting fluctuation ($T' = T - T_o$) data has been utilized to identify the Kelvin wave features. Furthermore, fluctuation data during every three month (season) period are put together as ensembles to show the seasonal variation of Kelvin wave activity for Spring (March, April and May (MAM)), summer (Jun, July and August (JJA)), Autumn or Fall (Septemper, October and November (SON)) and winter (December, January and February (DJF)) of March 2019 to February 2020. As a final step, we applied a 2-D Fast Fourier Transform (2D-FFT) on large scale temperature fluctuation components and the subsequent application of incoherent integration on the output of the FFT to identify the typical characteristics of Kelvin waves. The vertical wavelengths (λ_z in the z axis) estimated from simple wave theory for kelvin waves:

$$\lambda_z = \frac{2\pi}{N} \left(\frac{\lambda_x}{\tau} - \bar{U} \right) \quad (5.2)$$

Where, \bar{U} , N , τ , λ_x , and λ_z are velocity of mean zonal wind, bouyancy frequency, wave period (observed parameter), zonal wavelength, and vertical wavelength (observed

parameter) respectively. N is approximately equal to 0.02 s^{-1} , zonal wavelength λ_x for wave number 1 is equivalent to 40,200 km, which is the circumference of the earth's mean radius plus height from the surface, for wave number 2, λ_x is equivalent to 20,100 km and \bar{U} is variant by time and altitude depending on the quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO). According to monthly mean zonal wind data at Singapore, \bar{U} is approximately equal to -1.73 m/s, -1.63 m/s, 0.13 m/s, and 0.88 m/s during Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter respectively, where the minus sign indicates easterly.

5.2.3.4 Gravity wave Energy

We have calculated the wave kinetic energy using fluctuation of zonal and meridional wind observed by radiosonde using equation 5.3 and also potential energy from RS temperature fluctuation data by applying equation 5.4 (Ratnam et al., 2006), integrated over the heights of 15 – 25 km. The linear correlation between kinetic and potential energy was particularly significant (0.716). Gravity Wave (GW) activity is estimated by calculating the potential (E_p), kinetic (E_k) and total (E_t) energies per unit mass as defined by:

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2}(u'^2 + v'^2) \quad (5.3)$$

$$E_p = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{g}{N} \frac{T'}{T} \right)^2 \quad (5.4)$$

where $g(z)$ is the acceleration due to gravity. $N(z)$ is the oscillation frequency of the parcel of the atmosphere (usually called Buoyancy or Brunt–vallisala frequency) and it is expressed as

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (5.5)$$

where $\Gamma_d = \frac{g}{c_p}$ is adiabatic lapse rate, c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure of the atmosphere and for this study $9.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ (K/m)}$ lapse rate is adopted.

$$E_T = E_k + E_p \quad (5.6)$$

5.3 Result and Discussion

5.3.1 Longitude - Time investigation of kelvin wave in the TLS region over tropical and subtropical regions

Our aim is to investigate prevailing of kelvin waves at 15 km (corresponds to tropopause of subtropical region), 17 km (corresponds to tropopause of tropical region) and 25 km (lower stratosphere) for tropical and subtropical regions. Procedure of identification of kelvin wave has been explained in section 5.2.4.3. First we ensemble the temperature fluctuations at the pressure level of 100 hPa (15 km) for

Figure 5.2: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 22 - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 15 km in subtropical Cairo station.

subtropical region during every three months i.e seasonal variations of kelvin wave activity for four seasons has been calculated and corresponding longitude - time contours are draw for each season (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (C), Autumn and (d) Winter in Figure 5.2. The temperature minimum in the cold region varies episodically during these months (in response to variations in deep convection), but overall the patterns are quasi-stationary. The maximum amplitude of kelvin wave from Figure 5.2 (a - d) in spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter are 3 K, 4 K, 4 K and 4 K respectively. In spring the kelvin wave (here after KW) propagets in all longitude in the month of April 16 to May 31 (in the day of 45 to 92). From Figure 5.2 (b) the KW increase slightly in the month of August 20 - 30. The periodicity of KW in June is 5 days, in July is 20 days and in August is 15 days. In Autumn KW have seen in the end of October and the beginning of November. The periodicity of KW in Autumn and Winter are 10 and 5 days respectively.

Figure 5.3 (a - d) depicts the longitude time contours of temperature fluctuations at 15 km (100 hPa pressure level) for tropical station Addis during March 2019 to February 2020. The maximum amplitude of KW in tropical region from Figure 5.3 (a - d) in spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter are 7 K, 6 K, 7 K and 8 K respectively. The periodicity of KW observed in Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter are 10 days, 20 days, 12 days, and 7 days respectively. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 15 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperatures over longitudes $180^{\circ}W - 50^{\circ}E$ in spring, $50^{\circ}W - 50^{\circ}E$ in summer, $(140^{\circ}-50^{\circ}) W - (50^{\circ}-140^{\circ}) E$ in Autumn, and $100^{\circ}W - 40^{\circ}E$ in winter associated with maximum convection (Highwood and Hoskins, 1998; Hormann and Brandt, 2009; Randel and Wu, 2005; Seidel et al., 2001). The temperature minimum in the cold region varies episodically during March 3 - 10, Jun 15 - 23, October 15 - 25 and January 3 (in response to variations in deep convection), but overall the patterns are quasi-stationary. In contrast, temperature fluctuations at 15 km show zonal wavenumber-1 structure with regular eastward propagation. These observational results are consistent with earlier reported results including (Garcia and Salby, 1987; Randel and Wu, 2005). Randel and Wu (2005) using CHAMP and SAC-C RO data have found the quasi-stationary wave structures near the tropopause (15 km) for four consecutive months starting from March 2019 to February 2020. The periodicity of KW at 15 km in tropical station for the four seasons are 15 days. We generalize Figure 5.2 (subtropical region) and Figure 5.3 (tropical region) the maximum amplitude observed 4 K (Summer, Autumn and Winter) in subtropical region and 8 K (Winter) in tropical region which is KW more fluctuate in the tropical region and our results are match with the theory of KW is maximum amplitude in the equator and exponentially decay away from the equator. The maximum periodicity in the subtropical region is 13.3 day in summer and the maximum periodicity observed in tropical region is 20 day which is periodicity and amplitude have no any connections. The maximum tropopause height in the tropical region observed due to KW is maximum temperature fluctuation (maximum amplitude) in the equator.

Now, we try to analyze KW fluctuation at 17 km correspond to tropical tropopause. Figure 5.4 (a - b) depicts the longitude time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at 17 km subtropical region Cairo during March 2019 to February 2020. The maximum amplitude of KW in tropical region from Figure 5.4 (a - d) in spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter are 3 K, 4 K, 4 K and 4 K respectively. The periodicity of KW also observed in Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter are 8 days, 10 days, 11 days, and 12 days respectively. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 17 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of warm temperatures over longitudes of $180^{\circ}-140^{\circ} W$ to $50^{\circ}W-40^{\circ} E$ in March 1- 10, $180^{\circ}W-180^{\circ}$

Figure 5.3: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 0 - 15° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 15 km in tropical Addis station.

Figure 5.4: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 22° - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 17 km in subtropical Cairo station.

E in August 15 - 31, 180° W- 180° E in September 1 - 25 and 40° - 180° E in December 5-25. The temperature fluctuation also from March 2019 to February 2020 at 17 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperature over longitudes of 40° W- 40° E in March 1 - 10, 0° W- 150° E in June 1 - 10, 40° W- 180° E in November 5 - 30 and 180° - 150° W in December 30 - January 25 and 100° - 150° E December 1 - 10 associated with maximum convection. In Figure 5.5 (a - b) depicts the longitude time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at 17 km for tropical station Addis during March 2019 to February 2020. The maximum amplitude of KW in tropical region from Figure 5.5 (a - d) in spring, Summer, Autumn and Winter are 6 K, 4 K, 6 K and 5 K respectively. The periodicity of KW also observed in Spring, Summer, Autumn, and Winter are 13.3 days, 14 days, 11 days, and 12 days respectively. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 17 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperatures over longitudes 50° W- 50° E in spring, 50° W- 100° E in summer, 100° - 40° W in Autumn and

Figure 5.5: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of 0 - 15° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 17 km in tropical Addis station.

100°-40° W in winter. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 17 km are characterized by the climatological structure of warm temperatures over the longitudes of 180°-100° W in spring, 150°-50° W in summer, 40°-140° E in Autumn and 180°-40° W in winter. The periodicity of KW in the warm and cold temperatures are 5 and 10 days in spring, 15 and 25 days in Summer, 10 and 10 days in Autumn, 10 and 20 days in Winter respectively. Generally the maximum amplitude and periodicity at 17 km in subtropical region Cairo is 4 K (in summer, Autumn, and winter) and 12 days in Summer respectively, and also the maximum amplitude and periodicity at 17 km in tropical station Addis is 6 K (in Spring and autumn) and 14 days in Summer respectively. This is what we the expected result due to the KW temperature fluctuation maximum amplitude at the tropical region and its decay in the subtropical region.

Now we analyze the existance of KW in lower stratosphere and its periodicity of

Figure 5.6: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at latitude band of $22 - 35^{\circ}$ N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 25 km in subtropical Cairo station.

temperature fluctuation at tropical and subtropical regions. The maximum amplitude of KW at 25 km in subtropical region Cairo is 2 K in spring, 2 K in Summer, 2 K in Autumn and 4 K in Winter. The maximum periodicity of KW at 25 km in subtropical region Cairo is 5 days in spring, 7 days in Summer, 8 days in Autumn and 5 days in Winter. In Figure 5.6 (a - d) depicts the longitude time diagrams of temperature fluctuations at 25 km subtropical station Cairo during march 2019 to February 2020. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 25 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperatures over longitudes $50^{\circ}W-180^{\circ}$ E in spring, $180^{\circ}W-100^{\circ}$ E in summer, $110^{\circ}-100^{\circ}$ W in Autumn and $180^{\circ}-60^{\circ}$ W in winter associated with maximum convection. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 25 km are characterized by the climatological structure of warm temperatures over the longitudes of $40^{\circ}W-60^{\circ}$ E in spring, $50^{\circ}W-180^{\circ}$ E in summer, $50^{\circ}W-100^{\circ}$ E in Autumn and $50^{\circ}W-180^{\circ}$ E in winter. In Figure 5.7 (a - d) depicts the longitude time diagrams of temperature fluctu-

Figure 5.7: Longitude - time diagrams of temperature fluctuations over 0-15° N during (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter at 25 km in tropical Addis station.

tuations at 25 km tropical station Addis during march 2019 to February 2020. The maximum amplitude of KW at 25 km in tropical region Addis is 6 K in spring, 2 K in Summer, 7 K in Autumn and 4 K in Winter. The maximum periodicity of KW at 25 km in tropical region Addis is 8 days in spring, 7 days in Summer, 11 days in Autumn and 5 days in Winter. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 25 km are characterized by the known climatological structure of cold temperatures over longitudes 10°-90° E in spring, 50°W-100° E in summer, 10°W-50° E in Autumn and 180°-60° W in winter associated with maximum convection. The temperature fluctuations from March 2019 to February 2020 at 25 km are characterized by the climatological structure of warm temperatures over the longitudes of 180°W-180° E in spring, 10°W-150° E in summer, 100°W-10° E in Autumn and 10°-180° E in winter. Generally the maximum amplitude and periodicity at 25 km in subtropical region Cairo are 4 K in winter and 8 days in Autumn respectively, and also the maximum amplitude and periodicity at 25 km in tropical region Addis are 7 K in Autumn and 11 days in Autumn respectively, because of the KW temperature fluctuation's maximum amplitude in the tropical region and their decrease in the subtropical region at higher altitudes, which is anticipated outcome line with previous studies.

Figure 5.8: Altitude - time kelvin wave signatures during different seasons from (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in subtropical Cairo station in RS data.

5.3.2 Altitude – Time investigation of kelvin wave in the TLS region

In order to study the vertical propagation of KWs, we constructed height - time variations of temperature kelvin wave fluctuations for tropical and subtropical stations during different seasons for March 2019 - February 2020 using RS and AIRS data. Figure 5.8 (a - d) shows Altitude - time variations of temperature fluctuations in subtropical station Cairo from RS data corresponding to (a) Spring (March 2019 - May 2019), (b) Summer (June 2019 - August 2019), (c) Autumn (September 2019 - November 2019), and (d) Winter (December 2019 - February 2020). The interesting feature from these figure is that KW phenomenon started below the tropopause height (around 12 km) and extends as high as 24 km and the vertical wavelengths are found 6 km during Spring, 7.8 km during Summer, 7.8 km during Autumn, and 10 km during Winter propagated with a period of 8.8 days in Spring, 7.8 days in Summer, 7.5 days in Autumn and 6.4 days in Winter. The vertical wavelengths observed here are in good agreement with those observed using high vertical resolution radiosonde measurements by (Ratnam et al., 2006). Figure 5.9 (a - d) depicts Altitude - time variations of temperature fluctuations in subtropical Cairo station from AIRS data corresponding to (a) Spring (March 2019 - May 2019), (b) Summer (June 2019 - August 2019), (c) Autumn (September 2019 - November 2019), and (d) Winter (December 2019 - February 2020). KW that propagated with a period of 13.3

Figure 5.9: Altitude - time equatorial kelvin wave signatures during different seasons from (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in subtropical Cairo station in AIRS data.

day in Spring, 7.7 day in Summer, 13.3 day in Autumn, and 10 day in Winter with a vertical wave length of 9.2 km in spring, 11.2 km in summer, 7.7 km in Autumn, and 10 km in Winter. In similar manner, height – time variations of temperature fluctuations in tropical Addis station were depicted in Figure 5.10 (a - d). It depicts Altitude - time variations of temperature fluctuations in tropical Addis station from RS data corresponding to (a) Spring (March 2019 - May 2019), (b) Summer (June 2019 - August 2019), (c) Autumn (September 2019 - November 2019), and (d) Winter (December 2019 - February 2020). KW that propagated with a period of 13.8 day in Spring, 14 day in Summer, 14.5 day in Autumn, and 14 day in Winter with a vertical wave length of 8.5 km in spring, 3.8 km in summer, 4 km in Autumn, and 4.4 km in Winter. The vertical wave lengths that we have determined here agree with previous studies by (ayo; Hirota, 1979; Holton et al., 1995; Holton and Lindzen, 1968; Sridharan et al., 2006; Tsai et al., 2004). In Figure 5.11 (a - d) depicts Altitude - time variations of temperature fluctuations in tropical Addis station from AIRS data corresponding to (a) Spring (March 2019 - May 2019), (b) Summer (June 2019 - August 2019), (c) Autumn (September 2019 - November 2019), and (d) Winter (December 2019 - February 2020). KW that propagated with a period of 10 day in Spring, 9 day in Summer, 10 day in Autumn, and 9.2 day in Winter with a vertical wave length of 13.4 km in spring, 12.5 km in summer, 7.5 km in Autumn, and 11 km in Winter. The vertical wave lengths we observed here are consistent with earlier re-

Figure 5.10: Altitude - time equatorial wave signatures during different seasons from (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Autumn 2020 in tropical Addis station in RS data.

searches (Ryu et al., 2008; Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999; Wheeler et al., 2000). Further, we proceed to verify the above observed KW periods and vertical wavelengths how much fit with theoretical vertical wavelengths derived from KW dispersion relation formulation mentioned in the methodology section 2.4.3. We calculated KW characteristics including wavenumbers (S), wave period (τ) in days, phase speed ($C_x = \frac{L_x}{\tau}$, where, L_x is the zonal wavelength for wavenumber 1 and 2, which is the circumference of the earth over the equator) and the vertical wavelength (L_z) observed during different seasons of March 2019 to February 2020 for tropical and subtropical station. Both observational and theoretical vertical wavelength's show higher coherence during most of the season's which greatly enhances the confidence in our observational methodology. As summarized by (Canziani et al., 1995; Schreiner et al., 2020), KWs are associated with three discrete temporal bands including slow (phase speeds of 20 - 40 ms^{-1} and vertical wavelength ~ 10 km), Fast (phase speed of 50 - 80 ms^{-1} and vertical wavelength ~ 20 km) and Ultra fast (phase speed of ~ 80 ms^{-1} and vertical wavelength ~ 40 km). Since the phase speed and vertical wavelength of KWs during different seasons.

Figure 5.11: Altitude - time equatorial wave signatures during different seasons from (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in tropical Addis station in AIRS data.

Table 5.1: Summary of kelvin wave characteristics in tropical Addis station

EKW parameter	AIRS				RS			
	spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Wavenumbers (S)	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1
Wave period (days)(τ)	10	9	10	9.2	13.8	14	14.5	14
Phase Speed (km per hr)(C_x)	167.5	186.1	83.8	182.1	121.4	59.8	57.8	119.6
Vertical wavelength (λ_z)(km)	13.4	12.5	7.5	11	8.5	3.8	4	4.4
Theoretical wavelength (λ_z)(km)	15.15	18.07	7.35	16.17	11.13	5.73	5.09	5.49

Table 5.2: Summary of kelvin wave characteristics in subtropical Cairo station

EKW parameter	AIRS				RS			
	spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Wavenumbers (S)	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2
Wave period (days)(τ)	13.3	7.7	13.3	10	8.8	7.8	7.5	6.4
Phase Speed (km per hr)(C_x)	125.9	108.8	63	167.5	95.2	107.4	111.7	130.9
Vertical wavelength (λ_z)(km)	9.2	11.2	7.7	10	6	7.8	7.8	10
Theoretical wavelength (λ_z)(km)	11.53	10	5.5	14.59	8.84	9.88	9.78	11.14

Figure 5.12: (a), Daily cold point tropopause height (CPT_h) variation, (b) Kelvin wave fluctuation, and (c) Gravity wave fluctuation from March 2019 to February 2020 in RS data.

5.3.3 Effect of kelvin and gravity wave fluctuations on tropical tropopause variability

This section deals with kelvin and gravity waves association on cold point tropopause height (CPT_h) variability using pearson correlation analysis. Figure 5.12 (a) shows the CPT_h variability over tropical station using time series tropopause data from March 2019 – February 2020 using RS. It depicts interannual variability. The CPT_h is vary from 14.19 to 18.55 km. The CPT_h was seen to increase variation during March 12, March 15, June 15 - 17, October 11, October 13 and December 11 - 15. The tropopause height is strongly vary in April 29. These variation, as shown in Figure 5.12 (a), was an indicative of the presence of an atmospheric wave of kelvin and gravity waves. Temperature perturbations shown in Figure 5.12 (b) and (c) are direct reflections of the atmospheric gravity and kelvin waves. We observed from Figure 5.13 (b) and (c) the maximum kelvin and gravity waves are observed on April 8, Jun 13, August 30 and September 3 respectively, And also the minimum kelvin and gravity waves are seen on August 16, October 24, November 13 and July 29, December 29 respectively. The correlation of tropopause height with kelvin wave and gravity waves are 0.86 and 0.48 respectively. The maximum and minimum KWs are observed in summer and winter respectively. The maximum gravity waves are observed in summer.

We investigated the association between convection and KW activity using global

Figure 5.13: Outgoing long wave (OLR) data averaged between (a) $22 - 35^{\circ}$ N and (b) $0 - 15^{\circ}$ N from March 2019 to February 2020.

Table 5.3: Summary of seasonal correlation coefficient of tropopause height fluctuation with kelvin and gravity waves

Atmospheric Wave	spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Kelvin wave	0.72	0.86	0.81	0.74
Gravity Wave	0.12	0.48	-0.23	0.36

OLR data as a proxy for deep convective activity, since transient deep convection is one of the main source mechanisms for the tropical Kelvin waves. The OLR data, averaged over (a) $22 - 35^{\circ}$ and (b) $0 - 15^{\circ}$ from March 2019 to February 2020, is displayed as a longitude-time graphic in Figure 5.13. Every day, the OLR data are made available in $2.5^{\circ} \times 2.5^{\circ}$ latitude - longitude grid. To ensure comprehensive sampling, data gaps are filled by linear interpolation. Figure 5.13 clearly illustrates the very low OLR values in four regions: $\sim 170 - 110^{\circ}$ W, $\sim 90 - 80^{\circ}$ W, $\sim 50 - 10^{\circ}$ W, and $\sim 90 - 110^{\circ}$ E. These values frequently observe less than $270 W m^{-2}$. Furthermore, Figure 5.13 indicates clearly the most intense and variable deep convection appears in the longitude range of $\sim 0 - 50^{\circ}$ E, with notable enhancements during the summer months of June through August 2019 in the Northern Hemisphere. A large portion of this variability is observed in features that propagate slowly eastward during this period. In addition, as previously mentioned, the climatological structure of the cold temperatures at 17 km in temperature fluctuations seen from July 1 to August 6 over within $\sim 90^{\circ}$ W - 100° E longitude corresponds to convection activity (Highwood and Hoskins, 1998; Randel and Wu, 2005; Randel et al., 2003). Especially it is evident from Figure 5.13 (b) a low OLR values, in turn, are associated with significant convective activity during the summer, which may be the cause of the large amplitude

kelvin wave amplitudes [Figure 5.12 (b)] and the strong correlation with the fluctuation of the tropical tropopause [Figure 5.12 (a)]. As suggested by Shiotani and Horinouchi (1993), the high correlation between Kelvin waves and background winds is most likely caused by thermal damping.

From the above observational results and previous studies, it is conceivable that the tropical convection generated over the Ethiopian region during the present observation period could be the plausible source mechanism for Kelvin waves. This results are coincide with previous results (Salby and Garcia, 1987; Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999). Though Kelvin waves are seen in this study, their phase speed is substantially slower than that of moving OLR patterns Figure 5.13, indicating that the latter are not continuously related to convection. The observed Kelvin waves, on the other hand, are more in line with free modes driven by the wide range of convective variability, particularly over the active Ethiopian region.

Chapter 6

Trace gas (Ozone and Water vapor) exchange in upper troposphere lower stratosphere (UTLS) region over tropical and subtropical regions

In the Earth's atmosphere, upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) is an important region, where the interactions of different processes take place. These include dynamical, radiative and chemical processes together with the exchange of air mass and key minor constituents such as water vapor, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, and ozone across the tropopause. Transport of air masses and minor constituents between the troposphere and the stratosphere is generally known as stratosphere-troposphere exchange (STE) (Holton et al., 1995). These exchange processes play a crucial role in controlling the Earth's radiation budget and are directly linked to the characteristics of the UTLS region (Fueglistaler et al., 2009). According to Holton et al. (1995), the distinction between troposphere and stratosphere is important and useful because of two primary reasons. First, due to the difference in vertical transport time scales in the troposphere and stratosphere. In the troposphere vertical motions can occur on time scales as short as few hours to days; few hours via moist convection in the tropics and few days via baroclinic eddy motions in middle latitudes. However, in the lower stratosphere, due to the increased static stability, vertical motions occur on time scales of several months to year (Brasseur and Solomon, 2005). Moreover, the stratosphere is highly stratified and poorly mixed, the chemical constituents ejected into this layer from troposphere probably will have an increased life-time. Secondly due to the difference in chemical composition between them, the tropospheric air is clearly distinct from the stratosphere. The inhibition of vertical mixing by the strong inversion layer, the stratosphere, results in concentration gradients in the several atmospheric constituents across the tropopause.

The tropospheric air is normally considered as moist and ozone-poor whereas stratospheric air is extremely dry and ozone-rich. The water vapor distribution in the air is largely influenced by the air (atmospheric) temperature as explained by Clausius-Clapeyron relation. This relation results in a rapid decrease in water vapor concentration with altitude in troposphere as temperature decreases. A basic assumption is that the troposphere is in convective-radiative equilibrium. In the troposphere, interaction among radiative transfer, convection and large-scale dynamics regulate the

vertical temperature structure. In the troposphere there is a net radiative cooling due to GHGs. In the stratosphere, cooling due to the emission of longwave radiation. The transport of air from the stratosphere to the troposphere and vice versa plays an important role in the dynamics and composition of the atmosphere. The extreme dryness of the stratosphere is a result of the transport from the troposphere to the stratosphere in the tropics, where the air is strongly dried when it passes the very cold tropopause. CFCs which cause enhanced chemical ozone destruction in the stratosphere, are released at the earth's surface due to human activities and are transported into the stratosphere in the tropics. From here the CFCs are transported toward the poles where the ozone depletion takes place. Despite extensive research on STE, there are still large uncertainties in several important qualitative and quantitative aspects of STE. Recently, Butchart and Scaife (2001) predicted an increase of the air-mass exchange between the troposphere and the stratosphere with 3% per decade due to enhanced greenhouse gas concentrations. In the Hadley cell air rises in the tropics from the surface to upper troposphere. Above the Hadley cell further ascent is caused by the BDC in the stratosphere. When air passing through the cold regions of the tropical tropopause, it is freeze-dried and retains only the saturation mixing ratio corresponding to the low temperatures. Hence the signal of water vapor mixing ratio corresponding to the tropopause temperature is maintained by the air parcel as it ascends through the stratosphere. Mote et al. (1996) have made a classical study, which provided evidence for the connection between annual variation of tropical tropopause temperature and stratospheric water vapor mixing ratio.

The STE is critically important for understanding the interactive chemical, dynamical and radiative process of the atmosphere. The exchange can introduce the tropospheric source gases (water vapor) into the stratosphere and bring ozone-rich air down into the troposphere. The resultant redistribution of the chemical composition in both the troposphere and the stratosphere has a substantial impact on the radiative budget that causes global climate change, as well as the chemical and dynamical characteristics of the atmosphere (Holton et al., 1995). The predictions of future radiative forcing depend on accurate simulations of the upper tropospheric and lower stratospheric chemical concentrations, and hence on accurate simulations of the cross-tropopause transport of air mass and trace gases (Collins et al., 2003). Therefore, it is necessary to understand the dynamical processes across the Cold Point Tropopause (~ 17 km, ~ 100 hPa in the tropics and ~ 14 km, ~ 150 hPa in the subtropics) troposphere stratosphere to estimate the amount of their exchange (Fueglistaler et al., 2009). It is generally accepted that most air enters the stratosphere in the tropics Brewer (1949); Dobson (1956) by a combination of rapid vertical motion in convection (Corti et al., 2008) and slow diabatic ascent. The distribution of water vapor

(WV) in the atmosphere is concentrated mainly below 500 hPa. Above the middle troposphere, including the upper troposphere and the lower stratosphere (UTLS) at 8~20 km, the water vapor mixing ratio (WVMR) is 2~4 times lower than in the lower troposphere. The radiation force produced by the distribution and transformation of WV in UTLS region can change the energy balance of the earth-atmosphere system, and it can have a vital impact on global climate change (Held and Soden, 2000), due to WV is a greenhouse gases which influence on the radiation balance caused by twice that of carbon dioxide in the tropical troposphere (Sinha and Harries, 1995) on the other hand the refrigeration effect caused by increasing WV and ozone fluctuation is considerable (de F. Forster and Shine, 1999). The WV reached into stratosphere from troposphere may have influence on distribution of ozone variability (Oltmans and Hofmann, 1995). Methane oxidation process and upward transportation from the troposphere are the two dominating factors determining how much WV is in the stratosphere (Kremser et al., 2008). In addition, the variation of WV in the UTLS is affected by tropopause temperature and BD circulation (SHI et al., 2009). The quantity of water vapor injected into the stratosphere is largely determined by the temperature of the tropical tropopause. Recent research utilizing the characteristics of the tropical tropopause has revealed a widening of the tropical belt, which is associated with climate change (Birner, 2010; Seidel et al., 2008). The ongoing research focuses on determining the frequency and locations of stratospheric intrusions reaching the planetary boundary layer. Additionally, the extent to which stratospheric intrusions contribute to surface ozone and water levels is also being investigated (Trickl et al., 2010).

The exchange of mass across the tropopause is bidirectional, with a return flow transporting tropospheric air into the lowermost stratosphere. It occurs via a variety of processes on different scales which include both Troposphere to Stratosphere Transport (TST) (Zahn et al., 2000) and Stratosphere to Troposphere Transport (STT) (Danielsen, 1968) events. the transport of tropospheric air into the stratosphere is irreversible. The depletion of stratospheric ozone over antartica is mainly due to stratospheric chlorine and temperature in the Antartica vortex (Strahan and Douglass, 2018). A major effect of ozone loss is on tropospheric temperature, circulation, precipitation, ocean, and ecosystem (bal; Kuttippurath and Nair, 2017). Stratospheric ozone loss over the tropical region due to stratospheric intrusions into the troposphere, which increases the tropospheric ozone (Das et al., 2016). The exchange of air between the stratosphere and troposphere (STE) plays a crucial role in shaping the chemical and radiative characteristics of the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere. Several studies have investigated this exchange using a combination of ground-based instruments and satellite data (Dayan, 2023; Haynes et al., 2021). A 15-

year climatology study using modern reanalyses (ERA-Interim, JRA-55, MERRA-2, and MERRA) provided valuable data on global large-scale STE (Boothe and Homeyer, 2017). This work is first of its kind to observe trace gas of water vapor and ozone analysis from tropics and subtropics using AURA/MLS satellite observations over a period of 2006 to 2020. The methodology and data availability are covered in section 6.1. Section 6.2 describes the results and the discussion.

6.1 Data and the Analysis Methods

6.1.1 AURA MLS Satellite

The Aura satellite was launched on 15 July 2004 and placed into a near-polar Earth orbit at ~ 705 km with an inclination of 98° and an ascending node at 13:45h. It makes about 14 orbits per day. The MLS instrument onboard Aura uses the microwave limb sounding technique to measure chemical constituents and dynamical tracers between the upper troposphere and the lower mesosphere (Waters et al., 2006). The MLS line of sight is in the forward direction of the Aura spacecraft flight track. The Earth's limb is scanned from the surface to 90 km every 26.6 s giving 240 scans per orbit spaced at 1.5° intervals (165 km) with a total of ~ 3500 vertical profiles per day and a nearly global latitude coverage from 82° S to 82° N. MLS satellite measures atmospheric chemical species like OH , HO_2 , H_2O , O_3 , HCl , ClO , $HOCl$, BrO , HNO_3 , N_2O , CO , HCN , CH_3CN in the troposphere and lower stratosphere. The MLS observation data are reliable at several different heights, and an effective vertical range from 316 to 0.002 hPa (Read et al., 2007). The WV vertical resolution is 2.5 km from 316 to 215 hPa and degrades to 3 km from 100 to 1 hPa and Ozone vertical resolution is ~ 3 km from 256 to 0.01 hPa in the upper troposphere and the stratosphere. The radiometric and spectral performance of the MLS instrument is covered in detail by Jarnot et al. (2006) for the GHz (118, 190, 240, and 640) radiometers and by Pickett (2006) for the THz (2.5) radiometer. The standard H_2O and O_3 products are retrieved from the radiances measured by the radiometers centered near 190 GHz (R_2), and 640 GHz (R_4), respectively. The viewing geometry of the MLS instrument allows the innovative use of a two-dimensional approach to the retrieval problem since the limb observations from successive scans overlap significantly which means that effects of line-of-sight gradients can be taken into account (Livesey and Read, 2000). For the assimilation experiment, MLS data are selected according to the precision and quality flags recommended in the MLS Version 6.2 Level 2 data quality (Livesey et al., 2011) and description document (<http://mls.jpl.nasa.gov/data/v6-2dataqualitydocument.pdf>).

6.1.2 Methodology

Mass flux at tropopause: The mass flux can be estimated by multiplying the concentration of a tracer (in this case ozone and water vapor) that indicates stratospheric or tropospheric air by the cross-tropopause. To calculate the mass flux across a surface, we count the number of trajectories that cross the tropopause. The general formula for mass flux of the tracer is:

$$F_{flux} = \rho v A \quad (6.1)$$

Where, F_{flux} is the mass flux of Ozone and Water vapor, ρ is the density of the gas (density of ozone and water vapor) in the tropopause, v is the speed of the wind during tropopause crossing, and A is the cross sectional area of Ozone and Water vapor in the tropopause variation. The stratosphere to the troposphere (STT) density of ozone and Troposphere to the stratosphere (TST) density of water are calculated as:

$$\rho_{O_3} = 1.66 \frac{P}{T} C \quad (6.2)$$

$$\rho_{H_2O} = 0.62 \frac{P}{T} C \quad (6.3)$$

Where, P is tropopause pressure (in our study the tropopause pressure of tropical (Ethiopia) is 100 hPa and tropopause pressure of subtropical (Egypt) is 150 hPa), T is tropopause temperature, and C is concentration or mixing ratio of Ozone or water vapor we get from Aura/MLS satellite. Apart from the tropopause altitude oscillation, the tropopause temperature oscillation plays a significant role in the transport of water vapour from the troposphere to the lower stratosphere (Brewer, 1949). The holding capacities of water vapour in the air and hence the saturation mixing ratio of air is a strong function of air temperature (Clausius-Clapeyron relation). The Saturation Mixing Ratio (SMR) with respect to ice is estimated using the following equation (Bolton, 1980)

$$SMR = 0.623 \left(\frac{e_{si}}{P - e_{si}} \right) \quad (6.4)$$

Where, SMR is saturation mixing ratio, P is pressure in hPa, and e_{si} is saturation vapor pressure in hPa is given by

$$e_{si} = \exp\left(9.550426 - \frac{5723.265}{T} + 3.53068 \ln(T) - 0.00728332T\right) \quad (6.5)$$

T is the tropopause temperature in Kelvin and P is the pressure in hPa (Pressure near the tropopause in tropical region is 100 hPa and subtropical region is 150 hPa).

6.2 Result and Discussion

6.2.1 Long - term monthly and annual mean UTLS water vapor and ozone variation in tropical (Ethiopia) and subtropical (Egypt) region

This section utilizes 15 years (2006–2020) of monthly water vapor (316 - 0.001 hPa) and ozone (261 - 0.001 hPa) data from the MLS satellite in the pressure range known as the upper troposphere lower stratosphere (UTLS). The monthly and annual mean variations in water vapor profiles data from 2006–2020 using MLS satellite over tropical region is depicted in Figure 6.1 (a - b). The monthly mean water vapor volume mixing ratio (WVMR) below 200 hPa is relatively low, ranging from about 100–200 ppmv. However, above 200 hPa, it increases from 600 to 1000 ppmv is depicted Figure 6.1 (a). Figure 6.1 (b) demonstrates the annual mean WVMR variability, with peak values in the range of 400-600 ppmv at UTLS (200-300 hPa) during May-June-July-August. At pressures below 200 hPa, the annual mean WVMR concentrations are very low, ranging from 50 to 100 ppmv. Moreover, the UTLS (200-300 hPa) exhibits the highest observed SAO values, with a peak of 490 ppmv in May and 520 ppmv in August. The monthly and annual mean variations in ozone profiles data from 2006–2020 using MLS satellite over tropical region is depicted in the lower panel in Figure 6.1 (c - d). In Figure 6.1 (d), the annual mean ozone volume mixing ratio (OVMR) variability is shown, with peak values in the range of 6-10 ppmv at UTLS region (0.001-50 hPa) throughout the year. At pressure levels above 50 hPa, the annual mean OVMR concentrations are very low, ranging from 1 to 4 ppmv. Additionally, an annual oscillation (AO) is observed in the UTLS around July/August. Our findings are in good agreement with prior research (Dessler et al., 2013).

Figure 6.2 (a - d) depicts similar analyses of the monthly mean and annual mean water vapor profiles in the pressure range 316 - 0.001 hPa and ozone profiles in the pressure range of 261 - 0.001 hPa for the subtropical Egypt region. The left vertical panels of Figure 6.2 (a & c) show the contours of the monthly mean water vapor (a) and ozone (c) variations. The right panel of Figure 6.2 (b & d) displays the distribution of the annual mean water vapor (b) and ozone (d) variations. The monthly mean WVMR below 200 hPa is fairly low, ranging from about 5–100 ppmv. Above 200 hPa, the WVMR increases from 200 to 350 ppmv. Figure 6.2 (b) illustrates the variability of the annual mean WVMR with peak values ranging from 100 to 200 ppmv at UTLS (200 - 300 hPa) around March to June. At pressures below 200 hPa, the annual mean WVMR concentrations are very low, ranging from 10 to 100 ppmv. Additionally, the TAO (Triannual oscillation) was observed with a peak value of 190 ppmv in March, 200 ppmv in Jun, and 195 in september at the UTLS region (200 - 300 hPa) [Figure 6.2 (b)]. Figure 6.2 (d) demonstrates the annual mean OVMR

Figure 6.1: Contour of water vapor and ozone profiles from 2006–2020 using MLS satellite (a) Monthly profiles of water vapor, (b) annual mean profiles of water vapor, (c) monthly profiles of ozone, and (d) Annual mean profile of ozone tropical region Ethiopia region

variability, with peak OVMR values ranging from 6 - 9 ppmv at UTLS (50 - 0.001 hPa) through out the year. At pressures above 50 hPa, the annual mean OVMR concentrations are very low, with variability ranging from 1 to 5 ppmv.

6.2.2 The temporal and spatial distribution (Latitudinal variation) of water vapor and ozone in tropical (Ethiopia) and subtropical (Egypt) region

The vertical distribution of water vapor and ozone is influenced by complex atmospheric processes due to geography, climate and seasonality (Koji et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2018). So, we studied spatial distribution of WV and ozone in the UTLS region over tropical Ethiopia (0 - 12° N) and subtropical Egypt (22 - 28° N) region from 2006 to 2020 as depicted In Figure 6.3 . In Figure 6.3 (a), we observe that the highest concentration of WV, ranging from 400 to 500 ppmv in the latitudinal interval 0 - 12° N within the pressure range of 356 - 250 hPa, which assumes due to the strong monsoonal flows bringing moisture from the indian ocean and the Atlantic ocean. Additionally, this period coincides with enhanced convective activity, which further increases water vapor levels. Conversely, the minimum value of WV, ranging from 50 to 200 ppmv, is observed below 200 hPa is due to vapor moisture flux transition from the southwestern to the northeastern region. For subtropical region Egypt, the highest concentration of WV, ranging from 150 to 200 ppmv, is found

Figure 6.2: Monthly and annual mean of water vapor and ozone variation based on MLS observations from 2006 to 2020 over subtropical Egypt region

in the latitudinal interval of $22 - 28^{\circ}$ N within the pressure range of 356 - 250 hPa (Figure 6.3 (b)). In subtropical region Egypt has a predominantly dry climate, with a brief rainy season occurring from November to April. During these cooler months, water vapor levels reach their peak, although they still remain relatively low due to limited rainfall. The minimum value of WV is observed to be below 200 hPa, ranging between 50–100 ppmv. In Figure 6.3 (c), the highest ozone levels, between 6–8.8 ppmv, can be found in the latitudinal interval of $0 - 20^{\circ}$ N and within the pressure interval of 50–0.001 hPa. These elevated ozone levels are typically found in areas with significant agricultural activities and biomass burning. on the otherhand, the minimum value of ozone is observed above 50 hPa, ranging between 1-4 ppmv, as forested highlands may have lower ozone concentrations due to less human induced activity. Referring to Figure 6.3 (d), the highest ozone value is between 6–7.8 ppmv in the latitudinal interval of $22 - 35^{\circ}$ N and within the pressure interval of 50 - 0.001 hPa. These higher levels of ozone in Egypt can be attributed to increased photochemical reactions driven by higher temperatures and intense sunlight. Urban and industrial areas, such as Cairo, experience elevated ground level ozone concentrations due to pollution and vehicular emissions. The minimum value of ozone is also observed above 50 hPa, ranging between 1-5 ppmv. This lower value of ozone is a result of reduced sunlight and lower temperatures.

Figure 6.3: Latitude - pressure diagrams of ozone and water vapor at latitude band of 0 - 20^o N and 22 - 40^o N (a) Latitudinally water variation in Ethiopia, (b) Latitudinally water variation in Egypt, (c), Latitudinally ozone variation in Ethiopia and (d) Latitudinally ozone variation in Egypt

6.2.3 Seasonal Distributions of water vapor and ozone in the tropical region Ethiopia

The tropical region of Ethiopia and the subtropical region of Egypt display distinct patterns in the seasonal distributions of water vapor and ozone. These patterns are a result of variations in latitude, atmospheric circulation, temperature, and solar radiation. In tropical region Ethiopia, the distribution of water vapor during the spring season (March-April-May) is influenced by atmospheric circulation patterns, topography, and regional weather systems. This includes the transition from the dry season to the rainy season. In Figure 6.4 (a), it is evident that the highest levels of water vapor, ranging from 700 to 850 ppmv, were recorded in April 2012, April 2016, May 2010, and May 2019 during the spring season. The presence of water vapor in the atmosphere is primarily influenced by factors such as temperature, pressure, and moisture sources like evaporation and transpiration. In tropical region Ethiopia, the arrival of spring marks the onset of the rainy season in certain areas, particularly in the southern and southeastern parts of the country. Key factors during this season include increased humidity, water vapor transport, and regional variability. Humidity levels may rise by the transport of warm air from the Indian Ocean and the Gulf of Aden. In southern and southeastern Ethiopia, the presence of spring rains is particularly noticeable. The distribution of water vapor in Ethiopia is heavily influenced by the

countries topography. The highlands tend to have lower levels of water vapor due to the cooler temperatures at higher elevations. Moist air from the equatorial region, especially from the Indian Ocean, is transported towards the Horn of Africa, leading to an increase in water vapor in the lower atmosphere. During spring, water vapor levels generally rise, especially in the southern and eastern regions of Ethiopia, as a result of the early rainy season and the inflow of moist air from the ocean.

In the summer season (Jun-July-August), the distribution of water vapor in Ethiopia is significantly affected by the country's climate systems, as depicted in Figure 6.4 (b). In Figure 6.4 (b), shows that the highest levels of water vapor, ranging from 800 to 1000 ppmv, were recorded in Jun 2019, July 2010, 2011, 2012, 2020, and August 2006, 2010, 2018, 2019, 2020 during the summer season in the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. The levels of water vapor in Ethiopia are closely linked to the intensity of the monsoon system, temperature, and regional geography. During the summer, the rainy season reaches its peak in most parts of the country, resulting in significant increases in atmospheric water vapor. The key factors influencing the summer seasons include the monsoon's impact, peak rainfall and humidity, and regional variations in tropical Ethiopia region. Tropical Ethiopia's summer is primarily influenced by the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), which moves northwards, bringing moist winds from the Indian Ocean and the Atlantic Ocean. These winds contribute to higher moisture levels, particularly over the Ethiopian highlands and western lowlands. The summer rains are concentrated in the central, northern, and western regions of the country. This period shows the highest water vapor levels throughout the country due to heavy rainfall.

In autumn (September-October-November (SON)) in tropical Ethiopia region, water vapor distributions are influenced by the retreat of the rainy season and a shift in atmospheric circulation patterns. Autumn is a transition period between the main rainy season and the dry season. In Figure 6.4 (c), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 500 to 700 ppmv in September 2006, 2020, October 2014 and November 2020 during the Autumn season. Water vapor levels decrease significantly in these areas as the rains subside.

During winter (December-January-February (DJF)) in tropical Ethiopia region, the seasonal distributions of water vapor are influenced by the dry season, cooler temperatures, and shifts in atmospheric circulation. Winter is generally characterized by low humidity and a stable atmosphere, with distinct patterns for water vapor. In Figure 6.4 (d), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 300 to 400 ppmv were recorded in December 2010, January 2006 and February

2020. In winter, tropical Ethiopia region experiences one of its driest periods, with significantly reduced water vapor levels across most of the country. The countrys geographical and climatic diversity, however, leads to some regional differences. Winter is dominated by the northeasterly trade winds, which bring dry and cool air from the Arabian Peninsula and the Horn of Africa. These winds are part of the larger-scale Hadley Cell circulation that affects much of the region. As a result, most of tropical Ethiopia region experiences very low levels of water vapor. Clear skies and reduced evaporation further limit the amount of moisture in the air, causing low water vapor content. In tropical region Ethiopia, the seasonal distribution of ozone during

Figure 6.4: Seasonal mean of water vapor distribution at latitude band of 0 - 15⁰ N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in tropical Ethiopia region

spring (March-April-May (MAM)) is influenced by a combination of atmospheric circulation patterns, topography, and regional weather systems, including the transition from the dry season to the rainy season as shown in Figure 6.5 (a-d). Near-surface ozone concentrations are influenced by air pollution, including emissions from vehicles, industries, and biomass burning. In rural area of tropical region Ethiopia, ozone levels tend to be lower due to limited industrial activity. However, regions near urban centers like Addis Ababa might experience localized ozone pollution. In the stratosphere, ozone concentrations are higher and provide a protective layer against ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The distribution of stratospheric ozone in tropical region Ethiopia is relatively stable throughout the year, but there is some seasonal variation due to stratospheric circulation patterns, such as the Brewer-Dobson circulation. During spring, this circulation transports ozone-rich air from the tropics towards the

poles, but Ethiopia, located near the equator, typically experiences moderate stratospheric ozone levels during this period. Ozone distribution during the summer is influenced by both natural atmospheric circulation patterns and human activities as shown in Figure 6.5 (b). In the summer, tropospheric ozone in tropical region Ethiopia may increase slightly in some urban and industrialized regions due to higher temperatures and increased solar radiation, which accelerate photochemical reactions involving pollutants (such as nitrogen oxides and volatile organic compounds). This is especially the case in larger cities, where vehicle emissions and industrial activities contribute to ozone formation. During the summer, the Brewer-Dobson circulation plays a role in transporting ozone from the tropics to higher latitudes. Although tropical region Ethiopia is near the equator, this circulation pattern causes slight reductions in stratospheric ozone concentrations as ozone is transported poleward. Ozone levels in autumn are affected by a combination of seasonal weather patterns and regional pollution sources as shown Figure 6.5 (c). As the rainy season comes to an end and cloud cover decreases, more sunlight reaches the surface. This increases photochemical reactions, leading to a slight rise in tropospheric ozone levels, especially in urban areas. These reactions are driven by emissions from vehicles and industries, which interact with sunlight to form ozone near the ground. During autumn, the Brewer-Dobson circulation continues to transport ozone from the tropics towards the poles, but since tropical region Ethiopia is located near the equator, this has minimal impact on overall stratospheric ozone concentrations. There is typically no significant depletion of the ozone layer in tropical region Ethiopia during autumn, and the country remains protected from harmful UV radiation. Overall, Season except summer in tropical region Ethiopia shows a notable ozone distribution remains relatively stable with localized variations due to pollution.

6.2.4 Seasonal Distributions of water vapor and ozone in the Subtropical region Egypt

The subtropical region of Egypt display distinct patterns in the seasonal distributions of water vapor and ozone. In subtropical region Egypt, the seasonal distribution of water vapor during spring (from March to May) varies across regions but generally reflects the country's desert climate as shown in Figure 6.6 (a). In Figure 6.6 (a), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 200 to 300 ppmv were recorded in March 2011, 2015, April 2010 and May 2010, 2020 during the spring season within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. Subtropical region Egypt's geography, including its proximity to the Mediterranean Sea in the north, the Red Sea to the east, and vast arid regions in the interior, influences the distribution of these atmospheric components. Water vapor levels in tropical region Egypt during spring are relatively low overall, but they show regional variations depending on proximity to water bodies

Figure 6.5: Seasonal mean of ozone distribution at latitude band of 0 - 15⁰ N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in tropical Ethiopia region

and prevailing winds. As spring progresses and temperatures rise, water vapor content in the atmosphere also increases slightly, although it remains moderate. The region is relatively dry, but there is a slight increase in atmospheric moisture as temperatures warm up, especially towards May. Spring in the desert regions is characterized by dry, hot winds and very low humidity, especially as the Khamsin winds blow from the Sahara Desert. These winds transport hot, dry air across tropical region Egypt, further reducing water vapor content in the atmosphere.

In summer (June to August) in subtropical region Egypt, water vapor distributions are shaped by the extreme heat and the regional atmospheric circulation patterns as shown Figure 6.6 (b). The summer season is characterized by intense heat, especially in the interior and southern regions, while the influence may be large by the water bodies such as the Mediterranean Sea and Red Sea which plays a role in moderating atmospheric moisture. In Figure 6.6 (b), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 200 to 300 ppmv were recorded in Jun 2020, Jul 2007,2013 and August 2006, 2011, and 2020 during the summer season within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. Summer in subtropical region Egypt is typically hot and dry, with relatively low levels of atmospheric water vapor, particularly in the interior desert regions. However, there are variations depending on proximity to water sources like the Mediterranean Sea and the Red Sea. The sea breeze brings moisture into the atmosphere, leading to moderate to high humidity levels during the summer months.

This is the most humid part of subtropical region Egypt during the summer, and the water vapor content increases steadily as the Mediterranean sea remains warm throughout the season. The presence of the Nile river provides localized moisture, particularly in areas closer to the riverbanks, but overall, the region remains dry due to the intense heat and arid conditions. The proximity to the sea results in more moisture in the air, especially during summer when the sea temperatures are higher, leading to more evaporation and atmospheric water vapor. The sea breezes from the Red Sea help to cool the coast, bringing moisture inland and increasing humidity along the coastline. However, the water vapor content decreases rapidly as one moves farther away from the coast into the interior deserts. The Western Desert, Libyan Desert, and Eastern Desert remain extremely dry throughout the summer. These vast desert regions experience very low humidity and water vapor levels, as the heat causes rapid evaporation and little moisture is retained in the air. The desert areas, particularly in the southern part of Egypt, experience some of the highest temperatures in the world during the summer, with little to no atmospheric moisture (Shangguan et al., 2019).

During autumn (September to November) in Egypt, the seasonal distribution of water vapor is shaped by the transition from the hot summer to cooler winter conditions as shown Figure 6.6 (c). Autumn typically brings cooler temperatures, but the country remains largely dry, especially in its interior desert regions. In Figure 6.6 (c), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 200 to 250 ppmv were recorded in Jun 2020, Jul 2007,2013 and August 2006, 2011, and 2020 during the autumn season within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. In autumn, water vapor levels across subtropical region Egypt are generally decreasing as temperatures begin to cool. The relative humidity and atmospheric moisture levels vary across different regions based on geography and proximity to water bodies. During autumn, the Mediterranean Sea remains warm from the summer heat, which means that sea breezes bring moisture inland, maintaining moderate levels of atmospheric water vapor. As temperatures drop from the summer peak, the evaporation rate decreases, but the proximity to the Mediterranean ensures that humidity remains higher than in inland areas. The Nile Delta and Nile Valley gradually declining water vapor levels as the region transitions to cooler weather. Although there is still localized moisture near the Nile River, the overall air becomes drier compared to the summer.

In winter (December to February) in subtropical region Egypt, the distribution of water vapor is influenced by cooler temperatures, reduced solar radiation, and shifting atmospheric patterns. In subtropical region Egypt's arid climate means that overall humidity levels remain low, but there are regional variations, particularly between

coastal areas and the inland desert regions. In Figure 6.6 (d), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 250 to 350 ppmv were recorded in December 2006, 2016, Jan 2007, 2015 and February 2011 during the autumn season within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. During winter, in subtropical region Egypt experiences cooler temperatures and generally lower humidity levels, though proximity to water bodies like the Mediterranean Sea and the Red Sea results in regional variations in atmospheric water vapor. Winter brings rainfall to the coastal areas due to Mediterranean cyclonic systems, and rain season for subtropical region Egypt, particularly in December and January. However, rainfall is still low by global standards. The cooler temperatures reduce evaporation, but the sea breezes bring moisture inland, leading to moderate humidity levels along the coast. Ozone levels in

Figure 6.6: Seasonal mean of water vapor distribution at latitude band of 22 - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in subtropical Egypt region

subtropical region Egypt during spring are influenced by atmospheric dynamics, regional pollution sources, and the presence of sunlight, which drives ozone formation in the lower atmosphere as shown Figure 6.7 (a-d). tropospheric ozone levels tend to increase during spring due to rising temperatures and longer daylight hours, which promote photochemical reactions involving pollutants such as nitrogen oxides and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). These pollutants mainly come from traffic, industry, and other human activities. In the stratosphere (the ozone layer), ozone levels remain relatively stable throughout the year, including during spring. The Brewer-Dobson circulation transports ozone from the tropics towards the poles, but since Egypt is located in the subtropics, it experiences moderate to high ozone concen-

trations in the stratosphere year-round. Egypt is not located near the polar regions where ozone depletion (such as the Antarctic ozone hole) is a major issue. During spring, stratospheric ozone levels remain largely intact over the region, providing effective protection from harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation.

Ozone levels during the summer in subtropical region Egypt are influenced by the combination of strong sunlight, high temperatures, and human activity, particularly in urban areas. There is a clear distinction between tropospheric ozone (ground-level ozone) and stratospheric ozone (ozone layer) as shown Figure 6.7 (b). The combination of strong solar radiation and high temperatures accelerates photochemical reactions between pollutants (such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs)) and sunlight. This results in the formation of ground-level ozone, a key component of urban smog. In rural areas and the desert regions of subtropical region Egypt, the levels of tropospheric ozone are significantly lower due to the lack of industrial pollution and fewer emissions sources. However, the strong sunlight and high temperatures can still lead to some natural ozone formation, although concentrations are much lower than in urban areas. The ozone layer in the stratosphere remains relatively stable throughout the season except spring. The Brewer-Dobson circulation, which transports ozone from the equator towards the poles, continues to maintain healthy levels of ozone in the stratosphere. Subtropical region Egypt does not typically experience significant ozone depletion in the stratosphere during the summer, and the ozone layer continues to provide effective protection from ultraviolet (UV) radiation. However, the intensity of UV radiation is higher during the summer due to the direct overhead position of the sun, even with a stable ozone layer. Ozone levels in subtropical region Egypt during autumn show both natural seasonal variations and are influenced by human activity in urban areas. During autumn, the levels of tropospheric ozone in subtropical region Egypt begin to decrease compared to the summer. In the stratosphere, ozone levels over subtropical region Egypt remain stable during autumn. The ozone layer continues to protect the region from harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation. Autumn doesn't show significant variations in stratospheric ozone levels, as subtropical region Egypt is far from the polar regions where ozone depletion occurs.

Ozone levels in Egypt during winter are shaped by the cooler temperatures, weaker sunlight, and seasonal weather patterns as shown Figure 6.7 (d). Unlike other reasons, there is a distinction between tropospheric ozone (ground-level) and stratospheric ozone (ozone layer). In winter, the levels of tropospheric ozone (ground-level ozone) in Egypt are generally lower compared to summer and autumn. This is because the cooler temperatures and reduced sunlight slow down the photochemical

reactions responsible for forming ozone at ground level. Without strong sunlight and high temperatures, ozone pollution from vehicle emissions and industrial activities is significantly reduced. The ozone layer in the stratosphere over Egypt remains stable during the winter months. The Brewer-Dobson circulation, which transports ozone from the equator to the poles, continues to maintain healthy levels of ozone in the stratosphere. Egypt, being located in the subtropics, is not directly affected by the seasonal ozone depletion that occurs in the polar regions (such as the Antarctic ozone hole). Therefore, stratospheric ozone levels remain consistent throughout the winter, providing effective protection from UV radiation. Due to the lower angle of the sun in winter, the levels of ultraviolet (UV) radiation reaching the surface are naturally lower, even without significant changes in stratospheric ozone, which means that the risk of UV exposure is reduced during the winter months.

Figure 6.7: Seasonal mean of ozone distribution at latitude band of 22 - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in subtropical Egypt region

6.2.5 Saturation mixing ratio in the tropical and subtropical region

The tropopause controls the two-way transport of air-mass and minor constituents between the troposphere and the stratosphere. A major mixing process in the UTLS region takes place in the tropical region, where a large number of convective systems and thunderstorms occur. These convective systems can inject water vapour into the lower stratosphere through the tropical tropopause. It is well known that the stratosphere is highly stable, less turbulent and have subsidence nature towards the troposphere. The thematic diagram shown in Figure 6.8, explains the role of

tropopause in exchange and mixing of the air masses between the stratosphere and the troposphere. Figure 6.8 shows the relation between the tropopause temperature and saturation mixing ratio of water vapor through Clausius–Clapeyron equation. From the Figure 6.8, it is clear that the holding capacity of water vapour which depends upon the saturation mixing ratio increases with air temperature. For example, the water vapour transport from the upper troposphere to the lower stratosphere increases by ~ 1 ppmv with the tropopause temperature changes from 190 K to 192 K. The tropical CPT_h controls the transport of ozone from the stratosphere to the troposphere, and the tropical CPT_t controls the transport of water vapour across the tropopause region.

Figure 6.8: Relation between the tropopause temperature and saturation mixing ratio in the tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt region

6.2.6 Mass flux of ozone and water vapor across the tropopause in the tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt regions

In this section our aim is to investigate the amount of mass flux of water vapor and ozone across the tropopause in tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt regions. The maximum mass flux of ozone observed in tropical Ethiopia has 3.4 kg/s and in subtropical Egypt is 5 kg/s, whereas the maximum mass flux of water vapor observed in tropical Ethiopia is 68 kg/s and 30 kg/s in subtropical region Egypt as shown in Figure 6.9. The water vapor and Ozone mass flux in the tropopause, which refers to the movement of water vapor from the troposphere to the stratosphere and ozone from stratosphere to troposphere, can vary based on several factors including geographic location, atmospheric conditions, and seasonal variations (Appenzeller et al., 1996). The regions with more frequent tropopause folds and stronger stratosphere

to troposphere exchange (STE) processes tend to have higher water vapor and ozone mass flux. Studies indicates that the eastern mediterranean and middle east, which includes subtropical region Egypt, are hotspots for the tropopause folds and ozone STE during the summer period (Meul et al., 2018). This suggests that subtropical region Egypt might experience higher ozone mass flux in the tropopause compared to tropical region Ethiopia. The overall patterns suggest that subtropical region Egypt, being closer to the mediterranean region known for higher tropopause fold activity, might have a higher ozone mass flux in the tropopause. Regions closer to equator like tropical region Ethiopia tend to have higher water vapor content in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) due to stronger convective activity and higher temperature (Zhang et al., 2024). Tropical region Ethiopia, being closer to the equator compared to subtropical region Egypt, is likely to experience more intense convective processes, leading to a higher water vapor mass flux in the tropopause region due to the upward transport of moisture from the troposphere to the stratospher.

Figure 6.9: Mass flux of ozone and water vapor (a) Ozone mass flux in Ethiopia, (b) Water vapor mass flux in Ethiopia, (c), Ozone mass flux in Egypt and (d) Water vapor mass flux in Egypt

Chapter 7

Conclusion and Recommendation

7.1 Conclusion

The dissertation investigates the Troposphere-Lower Stratosphere (TLS) variability and its dynamics in three ways. The primary motive of the problem, "Study on Long Term Troposphere lower stratosphere Temperature (TLST) trend in tropical and subtropical Northern hemisphere Using ground based and COSMIC Satellite data", has been investigated, leading to the subsequent conclusions:

1. The mean tropospheric altitude of tropical station Addiss is located 17.11 km from the RS data, 17.3 km from the COSMIC data, with mean tropospheric temperatures of 190.86 K from the RS and 194.64 K from COSMIC. In contrast, for the Cairo subtropical station, the mean tropospheric altitude exists at 15.87 km from RS and 15.51 km from COSMIC data, with a mean tropospheric temperature of 201.43 K from RS and 201.78 K from COSMIC. This demonstrates quite well how the tropopause height somewhat decreases as one moves from the tropics to the subtropics and how temperature also slightly increases.
2. A strong AO signal with intermittent QBO was seen in the CPTt wavelet spectrum, whereas a strong QBO signal with intermittent SAO was seen in the CPTth wavelet spectrum. The AO is the primary factor driving temperature fluctuation in the troposphere, whereas SAO, ENSO, and QBO are the primary factors influencing temperature variability in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere. QBO, ENSO, and IOD all have a significant impact on the interannual variability of temperature in the tropical stratosphere at the Addiss station, whereas IOD, ENSO, SF, QBO, and aerosol all have a significant impact on the subtropical Cairo station.
3. Lag analyses demonstrate a one-month delay for all natural forcings, except for oceanic indices and SSF up to three months below the tropopause (below 15 km). There is a noticeable 3 to 4 month lag in every oscillation above the tropopause.
4. The temperature trend for both stations shows a marked increment in the lower and upper troposphere, while the middle troposphere shows a declining trend. In the lower troposphere, a warming trend (0.27 K/decade) is observed from RS

and COSMIC, but a cooling trend (highest cooling of -0.16 K/decade from RS and -0.35 K/decade from COSMIC) in between 5 to 15 km at tropical Addis station. The lower troposphere at the Cairo station shows a warming trend of 0.1 K/decade from COSMIC and 0.3 K/decade from RS. A cooling trend is also noted between 5 and 15 km, with the highest cooling being -0.18 K/decade from COSMIC and -0.25 K/decade from RS which is consistent with previous reports.

The second goal of the topic, "Observations of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data", has been investigated, and the results are as follows:

1. The analysis using longitude-time and altitude-time data from RS and AIRS satellites temperature fluctuations in the TLS region from March 2019 to February 2020 leads to extraction of Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical region. The Kelvin waves show a combination of zonal wave number 1 and zonal wave number 2 components that typically prevail during most time periods, while individual dominance of their zonal wave number 1 or zonal wave number 2 occurs only for brief intervals lasting approximately 7-15 days.
2. It is found that the periodicity of observed kelvin wave is about 10 - 13.8 days in Spring, 9 - 14 days in Summer, 10 - 14.5 days in Autumn, and 9.2 - 14 days in Winter with a vertical wavelength of 8.5 - 10 km, 3.8 - 12.5 km, 4 - 7.5 km, and 4.4 - 11 km respectively in tropical Addis station. Similarly the periodicity observed kelvin wave is about 8.8 - 13.3 days in Spring, 7.8 days in Summer, 7.5 - 13.3 days in Autumn, and 6.4 - 10 days in Winter with a vertical wavelength of 6 - 9.2 km, 7.8 - 11.2 km, 7.8 km, and 10 km respectively in subtropical Cairo station.
3. The height-time cross section of temperature perturbations from both RS and AIRS indicated a downward-propagating kelvin wave, which was especially prominent during the summer season. The peak amplitude of the kelvin wave measured at the tropical location of Addis reaches 8 K in winter, while for the subtropical location of Cairo, it is recorded at 4 K in winter, which supports the exponential decrease of the kelvin wave from tropical to subtropical regions.
4. We can easily concluded that the observed waves belong to slow wave category except Summer and Winter tropical station Addis in AIRS data.
5. The highest correlation between tropopause height and kelvin wave activity is 0.86, while the correlation with gravity waves stands at 0.48. The substantial kelvin wave activity and its strong connection to fluctuations in the tropical

tropopause may be influenced by the outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) values, which are associated with considerable convective activity during the summer. OLR data indicates that intense convective activity occurs over the tropical and subtropical regions throughout the observation period. The KW events noted in temperature variations are influenced either by a convectively coupled wave or free mode waves in these regions. Both kelvin and gravity waves were particularly noticeable during the summer months.

The third and the last motive "Studies on troposphere stratosphere trace gases (ozone and water vapor) exchange in UTLS region over tropical and subtropical regions" leads the following conclusions:

1. the study employs latitude-time and pressure-time data obtained from the AURA/MLS satellite to investigate the mass flux of ozone and water vapor that crosses the tropopause in tropical and subtropical regions from 2006-2020. The ozone distribution is stable at both tropical region Ethiopia except spring and subtropical region Egypt except autumn season.
2. The transport of ozone from the stratosphere to the troposphere is controlled by the tropical CPT_h, while the tropical CPT_t controls the transport of water vapor across the tropopause. In tropical region Ethiopia and subtropical region Egypt the maximum water vapor is observed during summer and winter respectively. The annual mean variability of OVMR in tropical region Ethiopia ranges from 6–8 ppmv and in subtropical region Egypt is 6–9 ppmv within 50 to 0.01 hPa pressure level.
3. The annual mean variability of WVMR in Ethiopia peaks between 400–600 ppmv at UTLS in the pressure range 200 to 300 hPa during May to August. Similarly in subtropical Egypt, the peak WVMR value is between 100 to 200 ppmv at UTLS, occurring from March to June within the pressure interval of 300 to 200 hPa.
4. In tropical Ethiopia, SAO is observed in the WVMR, while AO is observed in OVMR. In subtropical Egypt, TAO is observed in WVMR, and AO is observed in OVMR.
5. The maximum mass flux of ozone crossing the tropopause is 5 kg/s in Egypt and 3.4 kg/s in Ethiopia. On the other hand, the maximum mass flux of water vapor crossing the tropopause is 68 kg/s in tropical Ethiopia and 30 kg/s in subtropical Egypt. Our study reveals that Egypt experiences a higher ozone mass flux in the tropopause compared to Ethiopia. Conversely, Ethiopia experiences a higher water vapor mass flux in the tropopause compared to Egypt.

7.2 Recommendation

This section provides recommendations for further research based on the dissertation's findings. Future research should consider other atmospheric waves, such as tidal, Rossby, and planetary waves, to better understand the causes of the TLS phenomenon. We analyzed temperature trends in the TLS region using just RS data from Addis and Cairo stations. Future studies should include additional stations. Our analysis of trace gas exchange in the TLS region only includes ozone and water vapor. Future research should include other chemical species carbon dioxide, methane, and sulfur dioxide as well.

References

- Albers, J. R., Butler, A. H., Langford, A. O., Elsbury, D., and Breeden, M. L. (2022). Dynamics of enso-driven stratosphere-to-troposphere transport of ozone over north america. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(19):13035–13048.
- Alexander, M. and Ortland, D. (2010). Equatorial waves in high resolution dynamics limb sounder (hirdls) data. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 115(D24).
- Alexander, M. J. and Pfister, L. (1995). Gravity wave momentum flux in the lower stratosphere over convection. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 22(15):2029–2032.
- Alexander, P., de la Torre, A., Llamedo, P., and Hierro, R. (2014). Precision estimation in temperature and refractivity profiles retrieved by gps radio occultations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 119(14):8624–8638.
- Alexander, S. P. and Tsuda, T. (2008). Observations of the diurnal tide during seven intensive radiosonde campaigns in australia and indonesia. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 113(D4).
- Angell, J. (1990). Variation in global tropospheric temperature after adjustment for the el nino influence, 1958–89. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 17(8):1093–1096.

- Angell, J. K. (1988). Variations and trends in tropospheric and stratospheric global temperatures, 1958-87. *Journal of climate*, pages 1296–1313.
- Anthes, R. A., Bernhardt, P., Chen, Y., Cucurull, L., Dymond, K., Ector, D., Healy, S., Ho, S.-P., Hunt, D., Kuo, Y.-H., et al. (2008). The cosmic/formosat-3 mission: Early results. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 89(3):313–334.
- Appenzeller, C., Holton, J. R., and Rosenlof, K. H. (1996). Seasonal variation of mass transport across the tropopause. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 101(D10):15071–15078.
- Ashok, K., Guan, Z., and Yamagata, T. (2003). Influence of the indian ocean dipole on the australian winter rainfall. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 30(15).
- Asnani, G. and Verma, R. (1977). Annual and semi-annual temperature oscillations in the northern hemisphere. *MAUSAM*, 28(4):499–506.
- Aumann, H., Gregorich, D., and Gaiser, S. (2005). Airs hyper-spectral measurements for climate research: Carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide effects. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32(5).
- Avery, M. A., Davis, S. M., Rosenlof, K. H., Ye, H., and Dessler, A. E. (2017). Large anomalies in lower stratospheric water vapour and ice during the 2015–2016 el niño. *Nature Geoscience*, 10(6):405–409.
- Awange, J., Forootan, E., et al. (2015). Interannual variability of upper tropospheric and lower stratospheric (utls) region over ganges-brahmaputra-meghna basin based on cosmic gnss ro data. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques Discussions*, 8(9).
- Babu, P. and Stoica, P. (2010). Spectral analysis of nonuniformly sampled data—a review. *Digital Signal Processing*, 20(2):359–378.
- Baldwin, M. P., Cheng, X., and Dunkerton, T. J. (1994). Observed correlations between winter-mean tropospheric and stratospheric circulation anomalies. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 21(12):1141–1144.
- Baldwin, M. P. and Dunkerton, T. J. (2005). The solar cycle and stratosphere–troposphere dynamical coupling. *Journal of atmospheric and solar-terrestrial physics*, 67(1-2):71–82.
- Baldwin, M. P., Gray, L., Dunkerton, T., Hamilton, K., Haynes, P., Randel, W., Holton, J., Alexander, M., Hirota, I., Horinouchi, T., et al. (2001). The quasi-biennial oscillation. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 39(2):179–229.

- Basha, H. A., Joshi, M., Bapiraju, B., Srinivasan, S., Rao, J., and Dutta, G. (1999). Long period atmospheric oscillations in the troposphere and lower and middle stratosphere over hyderabad.
- Bègue, N., Bencherif, H., Sivakumar, V., Kirgis, G., Mzé, N., and Leclair de Bellevue, J. (2010). Temperature variability and trends in the ut-ls over a subtropical site: Reunion (20.8 s, 55.5 e). *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 10(17):8563–8574.
- Bencherif, H., Diab, R., Portafaix, T., Morel, B., Keckhut, P., and Moorgawa, A. (2006). Temperature climatology and trend estimates in the utls region as observed over a southern subtropical site, durban, south africa. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 6(12):5121–5128.
- Bengtsson, L., Roeckner, E., and Stendel, M. (1999). Why is the global warming proceeding much slower than expected? *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 104(D4):3865–3876.
- Birner, T. (2010). Recent widening of the tropical belt from global tropopause statistics: Sensitivities. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 115(D23).
- Bischoff, S. A., Canziani, P. O., and Yuchechen, A. E. (2007). The tropopause at southern extratropical latitudes: Argentine operational rawinsonde climatology. *International Journal of Climatology*, 27(2):189–209.
- Black, E., Slingo, J., and Sperber, K. R. (2003). An observational study of the relationship between excessively strong short rains in coastal east africa and indian ocean sst. *Monthly weather review*, 131(1):74–94.
- Bolton, D. (1980). The computation of equivalent potential temperature. *Monthly weather review*, 108(7):1046–1053.
- Boothe, A. C. and Homeyer, C. R. (2017). Global large-scale stratosphere–troposphere exchange in modern reanalyses. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 17(9):5537–5559.
- Born, M. and Wolf, E. (2013). *Principles of optics: electromagnetic theory of propagation, interference and diffraction of light*. Elsevier.
- Borrmann, S., Solomon, S., Avallone, L., Toohey, D., and Baumgardner, D. (1997). On the occurrence of clo in cirrus clouds and volcanic aerosol in the tropopause region. *Geophysical research letters*, 24(16):2011–2014.
- Bourassa, A. E., Robock, A., Randel, W. J., Deshler, T., Rieger, L. A., Lloyd, N. D., Llewellyn, E., and Degenstein, D. A. (2012). Large volcanic aerosol load in the stratosphere linked to asian monsoon transport. *Science*, 337(6090):78–81.

- Bower, C. and Fitzgibbon, J. (2003). Flight temperature comparisons between the nasa three thermistor reference radiosonde and the national weather service qualified gps radiosondes. In *12th Symposium on Meteorological Observations and Instrumentation*.
- Bower, C. and Fitzgibbon, J. (2004). National weather service in-situ radiation temperature correction for radiosonde replacement system gps radiosondes. In *Eighth Symposium on Integrated Observing and Assimilation Systems for Atmosphere, Oceans, and Land Surface, Seattle, USA*, volume 10.
- Brahmanandam, P. S., Chu, Y.-H., and Liu, J. (2010). Observations of equatorial kelvin wave modes in formosat-3/cosmic gps ro temperature profiles. *TAO: Terrestrial, Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences*, 21(5):8.
- Brasseur, G. P. and Solomon, S. (2005). *Aeronomy of the middle atmosphere: Chemistry and physics of the stratosphere and mesosphere*, volume 32. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Brewer, A. (1949). Evidence for a world circulation provided by the measurements of helium and water vapour distribution in the stratosphere. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 75(326):351–363.
- Butchart, N. and Scaife, A. A. (2001). Removal of chlorofluorocarbons by increased mass exchange between the stratosphere and troposphere in a changing climate. *Nature*, 410(6830):799–802.
- Calvo, N., Garcia, R., Randel, W., and Marsh, D. (2010). Dynamical mechanism for the increase in tropical upwelling in the lowermost tropical stratosphere during warm enso events. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 67(7):2331–2340.
- Cane, M. A. (1983). Oceanographic events during el nino. *Science*, 222(4629):1189–1195.
- Cane, M. A., Zebiak, S. E., and Dolan, S. C. (1986). Experimental forecasts of el nino. *Nature*, 321(6073):827–832.
- Canziani, P. O., Holton, J. R., Fishbein, E., and Froidevaux, L. (1995). Equatorial kelvin wave variability during 1992 and 1993. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 100(D3):5193–5202.
- CHANGE, I. P. O. C. (1995). Ipcc second assessment. *A Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, WMO-UNEP*.

- Chin, M., Diehl, T., Bian, H., and Kucsera, T. (2016). Aerosols in the atmosphere: sources, transport, and multi-decadal trends. In *Air Pollution Modeling and its Application XXIV*, pages 3–10. Springer.
- Claud, C. and Terray, P. (2007). Revisiting the possible links between the quasi-biennial oscillation and the indian summer monsoon using ncep r-2 and cmap fields. *Journal of Climate*, 20(5):773–787.
- Collins, W., Derwent, R., Garnier, B., Johnson, C., Sanderson, M., and Stevenson, D. (2003). Effect of stratosphere-troposphere exchange on the future tropospheric ozone trend. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 108(D12).
- Cooley, J. W. and Tukey, J. W. (1965). An algorithm for the machine calculation of complex fourier series. *Mathematics of computation*, 19(90):297–301.
- Corti, T., Luo, B., De Reus, M., Brunner, D., Cairo, F., Mahoney, M., Martucci, G., Matthey, R., Mitev, V., Dos Santos, F., et al. (2008). Unprecedented evidence for deep convection hydrating the tropical stratosphere. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 35(10).
- Danielsen, E. F. (1968). Stratospheric-tropospheric exchange based on radioactivity, ozone and potential vorticity. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 25(3):502–518.
- Das, S. S., Venkat Ratnam, M., Uma, K., Patra, A., Subrahmanyam, K., Girach, I., Suneeth, K., Kumar, K., and Ramkumar, G. (2016). Stratospheric intrusion into the troposphere during the tropical cyclone nilam (2012). *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 142(698):2168–2179.
- Das, U., Pan, C.-J., and Yang, S.-S. (2022). Evolution of individual equatorial atmospheric kelvin waves in the stratosphere from formosat-7/cosmic-2 temperatures. *Terrestrial, Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences*, 33(1):4.
- Davey, M., Brookshaw, A., and Ineson, S. (2014). The probability of the impact of enso on precipitation and near-surface temperature. *Climate Risk Management*, 1:5–24.
- Dayan, U. (2023). Long-range and vertical transport, troposphere–stratosphere exchange. In *Atmospheric Chemistry in the Mediterranean Region: Volume 1- Background Information and Pollutant Distribution*, pages 127–141. Springer.
- de F. Forster, P. M. and Shine, K. P. (1999). Stratospheric water vapour changes as a possible contributor to observed stratospheric cooling. *Geophysical research letters*, 26(21):3309–3312.

- Dessler, A., Schoeberl, M., Wang, T., Davis, S., and Rosenlof, K. (2013). Stratospheric water vapor feedback. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(45):18087–18091.
- Dobson, G. M. B. (1956). Origin and distribution of the polyatomic molecules in the atmosphere. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, 236(1205):187–193.
- Dobson, G. M. B., Harrison, D., and Lawrence, J. (1929). Measurements of the amount of ozone in the earths atmosphere and its relation to other geophysical conditions.part iii. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character*, 122(790):456–486.
- Dunkerton, T. J. (1989). Theory of internal gravity wave saturation. *Middle atmosphere*, pages 373–397.
- Dunkerton, T. J. (1997). The role of gravity waves in the quasi-biennial oscillation. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 102(D22):26053–26076.
- Dunkerton, T. J. and Delisi, D. P. (1985). Climatology of the equatorial lower stratosphere. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 42(4):376–396.
- Durre, I., Vose, R. S., and Wuertz, D. B. (2006). Overview of the integrated global radiosonde archive. *Journal of Climate*, 19(1):53–68.
- Eckermann, S. D., Hirota, I., and Hocking, W. K. (1995). Gravity wave and equatorial wave morphology of the stratosphere derived from long-term rocket soundings. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 121(521):149–186.
- Eyre, J. (1994). Assimilation of radio occultation measurements into a numerical weather prediction system. *ECMWF Technical Memorandum*, 34.
- Flannaghan, T. J. and Fueglistaler, S. (2012). Tracking kelvin waves from the equatorial troposphere into the stratosphere. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 117(D21).
- Flannaghan, T. J. and Fueglistaler, S. (2013). The importance of the tropical tropopause layer for equatorial kelvin wave propagation. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 118(11):5160–5175.
- Forster, P. d. F. (1999). Kp shine. *Stratospheric water vapor changes as a possible contributor*.
- Frierson, D. M. (2006). Robust increases in midlatitude static stability in simulations of global warming. *Geophysical research letters*, 33(24).

- Fritts, D. C. and Alexander, M. J. (2003). Gravity wave dynamics and effects in the middle atmosphere. *Reviews of geophysics*, 41(1).
- Fueglistaler, S., Dessler, A., Dunkerton, T., Folkins, I., Fu, Q., and Mote, P. W. (2009). Tropical tropopause layer. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 47(1).
- Fujiwara, M., Hasebe, F., Shiotani, M., Nishi, N., Vömel, H., and Oltmans, S. (2001). Water vapor control at the tropopause by equatorial kelvin waves observed over the galápagos. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 28(16):3143–3146.
- Fujiwara, M., Manney, G. L., Gray, L. J., Wright, J. S., Tegtmeier, S., Ivanciu, I., and Pilch Kedzierski, R. (2022). Sparc reanalysis intercomparison project (s-rip) final report.
- Gao, X.-H., Yu, W.-B., and Stanford, J. L. (1987). Global features of the semianual oscillation in stratospheric temperatures and comparison between seasons and hemispheres. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 44(7):1041–1048.
- Garcia, R. R. and Salby, M. L. (1987). Transient response to localized episodic heating in the tropics. part ii: Far-field behavior. *Journal of the atmospheric sciences*, 44(2):499–532.
- Gebregiorgis, D., Rayner, D., and Linderholm, H. W. (2019). Does the iod independently influence seasonal monsoon patterns in northern ethiopia? *Atmosphere*, 10(8):432.
- Gettelman, A. and Birner, T. (2007). Insights into tropical tropopause layer processes using global models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 112(D23).
- Gettelman, A. et al. (2002a). A climatology of the tropical tropopause layer. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 80(4B):911–924.
- Gettelman, A., Salby, M., and Sassi, F. (2002b). Distribution and influence of convection in the tropical tropopause region. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 107(D10):ACL–6.
- Gray, L. J. (2003). The influence of the equatorial upper stratosphere on stratospheric sudden warmings. *Geophysical research letters*, 30(4).
- Gray, L. J., Anstey, J. A., Kawatani, Y., Lu, H., Osprey, S., and Schenzinger, V. (2018). Surface impacts of the quasi biennial oscillation. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 18(11):8227–8247.
- Gray, V. (2006). Temperature trends in the lower atmosphere. *Energy & environment*, 17(5):707–714.

- Gray, W. M. (1984). Atlantic seasonal hurricane frequency. part i: El niño and 30 mb quasi-biennial oscillation influences. *Monthly weather review*, 112(9):1649–1668.
- Grewe, V., Reithmeier, C., and Shindell, D. (2002). Dynamic-chemical coupling of the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere region. *Chemosphere*, 47(8):851–861.
- Gurvich, A. (1990). Navigation satellites for radio sensing of the earth’s atmosphere. *Soviet J. Remote Sensing*, 6:89–93.
- Hanson, D. R., Ravishankara, A., and Solomon, S. (1994). Heterogeneous reactions in sulfuric acid aerosols: A framework for model calculations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 99(D2):3615–3629.
- Hayashi, Y. (1982). Space-time spectral analysis and its applications to atmospheric waves. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 60(1):156–171.
- Haynes, P., Hitchcock, P., Hitchman, M., Yoden, S., Hendon, H., Kiladis, G., Kodera, K., and Simpson, I. (2021). The influence of the stratosphere on the tropical troposphere. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 99(4):803–845.
- He, W., Ho, S.-p., Chen, H., Zhou, X., Hunt, D., and Kuo, Y.-H. (2009). Assessment of radiosonde temperature measurements in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere using cosmic radio occultation data. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 36(17).
- Healy, S. (2001). Radio occultation bending angle and impact parameter errors caused by horizontal refractive index gradients in the troposphere: A simulation study. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 106(D11):11875–11889.
- Held, I. M. and Soden, B. J. (2000). Water vapor feedback and global warming. *Annual review of energy and the environment*, 25(1):441–475.
- Highwood, E. and Hoskins, B. (1998). The tropical tropopause. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 124(549):1579–1604.
- Highwood, E. J., Hoskins, B., and Berrisford, P. (2000). Properties of the arctic tropopause. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 126(565):1515–1532.
- Hio, Y. and Hirota, I. (2002). Interannual variations of planetary waves in the southern hemisphere stratosphere. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 80(4B):1013–1027.

- Hio, Y. and Yoden, S. (2005). Interannual variations of the seasonal march in the southern hemisphere stratosphere for 1979–2002 and characterization of the unprecedented year 2002. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 62(3):567–580.
- Hirota, I. (1979). Kelvin waves in the equatorial middle atmosphere observed by the nimbus 5. scr. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 36(2):217–222.
- Hirschberg, P. A. and Fritsch, J. M. (1991). Tropopause undulations and the development of extratropical cyclones. part i. overview and observations from a cyclone event. *Monthly weather review*, 119(2):496–517.
- Hoinka, K., Claude, H., and Köhler, U. (1996). On the correlation between tropopause pressure and ozone above central europe. *Geophysical research letters*, 23(14):1753–1756.
- Holton, J. R., Haynes, P. H., McIntyre, M. E., Douglass, A. R., Rood, R. B., and Pfister, L. (1995). Stratosphere-troposphere exchange. *Reviews of geophysics*, 33(4):403–439.
- Holton, J. R. and Lindzen, R. S. (1968). A note on kelvin waves in the atmosphere. *Monthly Weather Review*, 96(6):385–386.
- Holton, J. R. and Lindzen, R. S. (1972). An updated theory for the quasi-biennial cycle of the tropical stratosphere. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 29(6):1076–1080.
- Holton, J. R. and Tan, H.-C. (1980). The influence of the equatorial quasi-biennial oscillation on the global circulation at 50 mb. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 37(10):2200–2208.
- Hormann, V. and Brandt, P. (2009). Upper equatorial atlantic variability during 2002 and 2005 associated with equatorial kelvin waves. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 114(C3).
- Huangfu, J., Tang, Y., Ma, T., Chen, W., and Wang, L. (2021). Influence of the qbo on tropical convection and its impact on tropical cyclone activity over the western north pacific. *Climate Dynamics*, 57:657–669.
- Jain, A., Das, S. S., Mandal, T. K., and Mitra, A. (2006). Observations of extremely low tropopause temperature over the indian tropical region during monsoon and postmonsoon months: Possible implications. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 111(D7).

- James, R. and Legras, B. (2008). Mixing processes and exchanges in the tropical and the subtropical ut/lis. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions*, 8(3):10627–10664.
- James, R. and Legras, B. (2009). Mixing processes and exchanges in the tropical and the subtropical ut/lis. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 9(1):25–38.
- Jarnot, R. F., Perun, V. S., and Schwartz, M. J. (2006). Radiometric and spectral performance and calibration of the ghz bands of eos mls. *IEEE transactions on geoscience and remote sensing*, 44(5):1131–1143.
- Jin, F., An, S., Timmermann, A., and Zhao, J. (2003). El nino and la nina sea surface temperature anomalies: Asymmetry characteristics associated with their wind stress anomalie. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 107:1–10.
- Karl, T. R. (2012). *Long-term Climate Monitoring by the Global Climate Observing System: International Meeting of Experts, Asheville, North Carolina, USA*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Karoly, D., Roff, G., and Reeder, M. (1996). Gravity wave activity associated with tropical convection detected in toga coare sounding data. *Geophysical research letters*, 23(3):261–264.
- Kawatani, Y. and Hamilton, K. (2013). Weakened stratospheric quasibiennial oscillation driven by increased tropical mean upwelling. *Nature*, 497(7450):478–481.
- Keller, L. M., Maloney, K. J., Lazzara, M. A., Mikolajczyk, D. E., and Battista, S. D. (2022). An investigation of extreme cold events at the south pole. *Journal of Climate*, 35(6):1761–1772.
- Kerzenmacher, T. E., Keckhut, P., Hauchecorne, A., and Chanin, M.-L. (2006). Methodological uncertainties in multi-regression analyses of middle-atmospheric data series. *Journal of Environmental Monitoring*, 8(7):682–690.
- Kiladis, G. N. and Diaz, H. F. (1989). Global climatic anomalies associated with extremes in the southern oscillation. *Journal of Climate*, 2(9):1069–1090.
- Kiladis, G. N., Wheeler, M. C., Haertel, P. T., Straub, K. H., and Roundy, P. E. (2009). Convectively coupled equatorial waves. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 47(2).
- Kim, J.-E. (2015). *Impacts of atmospheric waves on tropical convection and the tropical tropopause layer*. PhD thesis, University of Colorado at Boulder.

- Kishore, P., Namboothiri, S., Jiang, J., Sivakumar, V., and Igarashi, K. (2009). Global temperature estimates in the troposphere and stratosphere: a validation study of cosmic/formosat-3 measurements. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 9(3):897–908.
- Kodera, K., Koide, H., and Yoshimura, H. (1999). Northern hemisphere winter circulation associated with the north atlantic oscillation and stratospheric polar-night jet. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 26(4):443–446.
- Koji, A. K., Van Malderen, R., Pottiaux, E., and Van Schaeybroeck, B. (2022). Understanding the present-day spatiotemporal variability of precipitable water vapor over ethiopia: a comparative study between era5 and gps. *Remote Sensing*, 14(3):686.
- Kremser, S., Rex, M., Langematz, U., Dameris, M., and Wohltmann, I. (2008). Validation of water vapour transport in the tropical tropopause region in coupled chemistry climate models. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions*, 8(3):10999–11037.
- Krzyscin, J., Krizan, P., and Jaroslowski, J. (2007). Long-term changes in the tropospheric column ozone from the ozone soundings over europe. *Atmospheric Environment*, 41(3):606–616.
- Kumar, P., Hamlington, B., Cheon, S.-H., Han, W., and Thompson, P. (2020). 20th century multivariate indian ocean regional sea level reconstruction. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 125(10):e2020JC016270.
- Kuo, Y.-H., Schreiner, W., Wang, J., Rossiter, D., and Zhang, Y. (2005). Comparison of gps radio occultation soundings with radiosondes. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32(5).
- Kuo, Y.-H., Wee, T.-K., Sokolovskiy, S., Rocken, C., Schreiner, W., Hunt, D., and Anthes, R. (2004). Inversion and error estimation of gps radio occultation data. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 82(1B):507–531.
- Kursinski, E., Hajj, G., Schofield, J., Linfield, R., and Hardy, K. R. (1997). Observing earth’s atmosphere with radio occultation measurements using the global positioning system. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 102(D19):23429–23465.
- Kuttippurath, J. and Nair, P. J. (2017). The signs of antarctic ozone hole recovery. *Scientific reports*, 7(1):585.

- Lampropoulos, G., Mavromichalaki, H., and Tritakis, V. (2016). Possible estimation of the solar cycle characteristic parameters by the 10.7 cm solar radio flux. *Solar Physics*, 291:989–1002.
- Langford, A., Proffitt, M., VanZandt, T., and Lamarque, J.-F. (1996). Modulation of tropospheric ozone by a propagating gravity wave. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 101(D21):26605–26613.
- Lindzen, R. S. and Holton, J. R. (1968). A theory of the quasi-biennial oscillation. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 25(6):1095–1107.
- Liou, K.-N. (2002). *An introduction to atmospheric radiation*, volume 84. Elsevier.
- Liu, J., Zhang, Q., Singh, V. P., Song, C., Zhang, Y., Sun, P., and Gu, X. (2018). Hydrological effects of climate variability and vegetation dynamics on annual fluvial water balance in global large river basins. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 22(7):4047–4060.
- Livesey, N., Read, W., Wagner, P., Froidevaux, L., Lambert, A., Manney, G., Valle, L., Pumphrey, H., Santee, M., Schwartz, M., et al. (2017). Earth observing system, aura microwave limb sounder (mls): Version 4.2 x level 2 data quality and description document. Technical report, Technical report, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, D-33509.
- Livesey, N. J. and Read, W. G. (2000). Direct retrieval of line-of-sight atmospheric structure from limb sounding observations. *Geophysical research letters*, 27(6):891–894.
- Livesey, N. J., Read, W. G., Froidevaux, L., Lambert, A., Manney, G. L., Pumphrey, H. C., Santee, M. L., Schwartz, M. J., Wang, S., Cofield, R. E., et al. (2011). Version 3.3 level 2 data quality and description document. *JPL D-33509*, 3(2):4–1.
- Livesey, N. J. and Wu, D. L. (2004). Eos mls retrieval processes algorithm theoretical basis. *Jet Propul. Lab. Doc. D*, 16159.
- Lu, J., Xie, F., Tian, H., and Luo, J. (2021). Impacts of ozone changes in the tropopause layer on stratospheric water vapor. *Atmosphere*, 12(3):291.
- Luers, J. K. and Eskridge, R. E. (1995). Temperature corrections for the viz and vaisala radiosondes. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 34(6):1241–1253.
- Luers, J. K. and Eskridge, R. E. (1998). Use of radiosonde temperature data in climate studies. *Journal of climate*, 11(5):1002–1019.

- Manabe, S. and Wetherald, R. T. (1967). Thermal equilibrium of the atmosphere with a given distribution of relative humidity.
- Marshall, A. G. and Scaife, A. A. (2009). Impact of the qbo on surface winter climate. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 114(D18).
- Maruyama, T. (1968). Upward transport of westerly momentum due to large-scale disturbances in the equatorial lower stratosphere. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 46(5):404–417.
- Matsuno, T. (1966). Quasi-geostrophic motions in the equatorial area. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 44(1):25–43.
- Mattioli, V., Westwater, E., Cimini, D., Liljegren, J., Lesht, B., Gutman, S., and Schmidlin, F. (2007). Analysis of radiosonde and ground-based remotely sensed pwv data from the 2004 north slope of alaska arctic winter radiometric experiment. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 24(3):415–431.
- McMillin, L., Uddstrom, M., and Coletti, A. (1992). A procedure for correcting radiosonde reports for radiation errors. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 9(6):801–811.
- Meehl, G. A., Hurrell, J. W., and Loon, H. V. (1998). A modulation of the mechanism of the semiannual oscillation in the southern hemisphere. *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, 50(4):442–450.
- Melbourne, W. (2004). Radio occultations using earth satellites, jpl deep space communications and navigation series.
- Melbourne, W., Davis, E., Duncan, C., Hajj, G., Hardy, K., Kursinski, E., Meehan, T., Young, L., and Yunck, T. (1994). The application of spaceborne gps to atmospheric limb sounding and global change monitoring. Technical report.
- Meul, S., Langematz, U., Kröger, P., Oberländer-Hayn, S., and Jöckel, P. (2018). Future changes in the stratosphere-to-troposphere ozone mass flux and the contribution from climate change and ozone recovery. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 18(10):7721–7738.
- Mohanakumar, K. and Kumar, K. P. (1998). Study of the seasonal cycle of temperature of the troposphere and the stratosphere.
- Mote, P. W., Dunkerton, T. J., and Wu, D. (2002). Kelvin waves in stratospheric temperature observed by the microwave limb sounder. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 107(D14):ACL–10.

- Mote, P. W., Rosenlof, K. H., McIntyre, M. E., Carr, E. S., Gille, J. C., Holton, J. R., Kinnnersley, J. S., Pumphrey, H. C., Russell III, J. M., and Waters, J. W. (1996). An atmospheric tape recorder: The imprint of tropical tropopause temperatures on stratospheric water vapor. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 101(D2):3989–4006.
- Munteanu, C., Negrea, C., Echim, M., and Mursula, K. (2016). Effect of data gaps: comparison of different spectral analysis methods. In *Annales Geophysicae*, volume 34, pages 437–449. Copernicus Publications Göttingen, Germany.
- Nappo, C. J. (2012). *An introduction to atmospheric gravity waves*. Academic press.
- Nath, O., Singh, B. B., and Kunchala, R. K. (2024). El niño southern oscillation (enso) and indian ocean dipole (iod) signatures in tropical ozone in the upper troposphere lower stratosphere (utls). *Meteorology and Atmospheric Physics*, 136(2):10.
- Negash, T. and Raju, U. P. (2024). Study on long term troposphere lower stratosphere temperature (tlst) trend in tropical and subtropical northern hemisphere using ground based and cosmic satellite data. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 261:106306.
- Noersomadi and Tsuda, T. (2017). Comparison of three retrievals of cosmic gps radio occultation results in the tropical upper troposphere and lower stratosphere. *Earth, Planets and Space*, 69:1–15.
- Oberländer, S., Langematz, U., and Meul, S. (2013). Unraveling impact factors for future changes in the brewer-dobson circulation. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 118(18):10–296.
- Oltmans, S. and Hofmann, D. (1995). Increase in lower-stratospheric water vapour at a mid-latitude northern hemisphere site from 1981 to 1994. *Nature*, 374(6518):146–149.
- Oort, A. H. and Liu, H. (1993). Upper-air temperature trends over the globe, 1958–1989. *Journal of climate*, 6(2):292–307.
- Pan, Y. H. and Oort, A. H. (1983). Global climate variations connected with sea surface temperature anomalies in the eastern equatorial pacific ocean for the 1958–73 period. *Monthly Weather Review*, 111(6):1244–1258.
- Parker, D., Gordon, M., Cullum, D., Sexton, D., Folland, C., and Rayner, N. (1997). A new global gridded radiosonde temperature data base and recent temperature trends. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 24(12):1499–1502.

- Philander, S., Lau, N., Pacanowski, R., and Nath, M. (1989). Two different simulations of the southern oscillation and el niño with coupled ocean-atmosphere general circulation models. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, 329(1604):167–178.
- Philander, S. G. (1990). El niño, la niña, and the southern oscillation. *International Geophysics Series*, 46:293.
- Pickett, H. M. (2006). Microwave limb sounder thz module on aura. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 44(5):1122–1130.
- Polvani, L. M. and Solomon, S. (2012). The signature of ozone depletion on tropical temperature trends, as revealed by their seasonal cycle in model integrations with single forcings. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 117(D17).
- Ramaswamy, V., Chanin, M.-L., Angell, J., Barnett, J., Gaffen, D., Gelman, M., Keckhut, P., Koshelkov, Y., Labitzke, K., and Lin, J.-J. (1999). Stratospheric temperature changes: Observations and model simulations.
- Ramaswamy, V. and Schwarzkopf, M. (2002). Effects of ozone and well-mixed gases on annual-mean stratospheric temperature trends. *Geophysical research letters*, 29(22):21–1.
- Randel, W. J. and Cobb, J. B. (1994). Coherent variations of monthly mean total ozone and lower stratospheric temperature. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 99(D3):5433–5447.
- Randel, W. J. and Jensen, E. J. (2013). Physical processes in the tropical tropopause layer and their roles in a changing climate. *Nature Geoscience*, 6(3):169–176.
- Randel, W. J., Polvani, L., Wu, F., Kinnison, D. E., Zou, C.-Z., and Mears, C. (2017). Troposphere-stratosphere temperature trends derived from satellite data compared with ensemble simulations from waccm. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 122(18):9651–9667.
- Randel, W. J., Smith, A. K., Wu, F., Zou, C.-Z., and Qian, H. (2016). Stratospheric temperature trends over 1979–2015 derived from combined ssu, mls, and saber satellite observations. *Journal of Climate*, 29(13):4843–4859.
- Randel, W. J. and Wu, F. (1999). Cooling of the arctic and antarctic polar stratospheres due to ozone depletion. *Journal of Climate*, 12(5):1467–1479.
- Randel, W. J. and Wu, F. (2005). Kelvin wave variability near the equatorial tropopause observed in gps radio occultation measurements. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 110(D3).

- Randel, W. J., Wu, F., and Gaffen, D. J. (2000). Interannual variability of the tropical tropopause derived from radiosonde data and ncep reanalyses. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 105(D12):15509–15523.
- Randel, W. J., Wu, F., and Rivera Ríos, W. (2003). Thermal variability of the tropical tropopause region derived from gps/met observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 108(D1):ACL–7.
- Rao, D. N., Ratnam, M. V., Mehta, S., Nath, D., Basha, S. G., Rao, V., Murthy, B., Tsuda, T., and Nakamura, K. (2009). Validation of the cosmic radio occultation data over gadanki (13.48 n, 79.2 e): A tropical region. *Terrestrial, Atmospheric & Oceanic Sciences*, 20(1).
- Ratnam, M. V., Tsuda, T., Mori, S., and Kozu, T. (2006). Modulation of tropopause temperature structure revealed by simultaneous radiosonde and champ gps measurements. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 84(6):989–1003.
- Read, P. and Castrejón-Pita, A. (2012). Phase synchronization between stratospheric and tropospheric quasi-biennial and semi-annual oscillations. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 138(666):1338–1349.
- Read, W., Lambert, A., Bacmeister, J., Cofield, R., Christensen, L., Cuddy, D., Daffer, W., Drouin, B., Fetzer, E., Froidevaux, L., et al. (2007). Aura microwave limb sounder upper tropospheric and lower stratospheric h₂o and relative humidity with respect to ice validation. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 112(D24).
- Rezaei, A. (2021). Ocean-atmosphere circulation controls on integrated meteorological and agricultural drought over iran. *Journal of Hydrology*, 603:126928.
- Richard, E., Rosenlof, K., Ray, E., Kelly, K., Thompson, T., and Mahoney, M. (2001). Upper tropospheric-lower stratospheric in-situ measurements over hurricane floyd: The impact of tropical cyclones on stratosphere-troposphere exchange. In *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*, volume 2001, pages A51H–09.
- Riggin, D. et al. (1997). High resolution doppler imager observations of kelvin waves in the equatorial mesosphere and lower thermosphere. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 102(26):117–26.
- Rocken, C., Ying-Hwa, K., Schreiner, W. S., Hunt, D., Sokolovskiy, S., and McCormick, C. (2000). Cosmic system description. *Terrestrial Atmospheric and Oceanic Sciences*, 11(1):21–52.

- Rodriguez-Franco, J. J. and Cuevas, E. (2013). Characteristics of the subtropical tropopause region based on long-term highly resolved sonde records over tenerife. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 118(19):10–754.
- Romps, D. M. and Kuang, Z. (2009). Overshooting convection in tropical cyclones. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 36(9).
- Ryu, J.-H., Lee, S., and Son, S.-W. (2008). Vertically propagating kelvin waves and tropical tropopause variability. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 65(6):1817–1837.
- Salby, M. L. and Garcia, R. R. (1987). Transient response to localized episodic heating in the tropics. part i: Excitation and short-time near-field behavior. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 44(2):458–498.
- Salby, M. L., Hartmann, D. L., Bailey, P. L., and Gille, J. C. (1984). Evidence for equatorial kelvin modes in nimbus-7 lims. *Journal of the atmospheric sciences*, 41(2):220–235.
- Sato, K. and Dunkerton, T. J. (1997). Estimates of momentum flux associated with equatorial kelvin and gravity waves. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 102(D22):26247–26261.
- Schmidt, T., Wickert, J., Beyerle, G., and Heise, S. (2008). Global tropopause height trends estimated from gps radio occultation data. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 35(11).
- Schreiner, W., Rocken, C., Sokolovskiy, S., Syndergaard, S., and Hunt, D. (2007). Estimates of the precision of gps radio occultations from the cosmic/formosat-3 mission. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 34(4).
- Schreiner, W. S., Weiss, J., Anthes, R. A., Braun, J., Chu, V., Fong, J., Hunt, D., Kuo, Y.-H., Meehan, T., Serafino, W., et al. (2020). Cosmic-2 radio occultation constellation: First results. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 47(4):e2019GL086841.
- Seidel, D. J., Angell, J., Christy, J., Free, M., Klein, S., Lanzante, J. R., Mears, C., Parker, D., Schabel, M., Spencer, R., et al. (2004). Uncertainty in signals of large-scale climate variations in radiosonde and satellite upper-air temperature datasets. *Journal of Climate*, 17(11):2225–2240.
- Seidel, D. J., Fu, Q., Randel, W. J., and Reichler, T. J. (2008). Widening of the tropical belt in a changing climate. *Nature geoscience*, 1(1):21–24.

- Seidel, D. J., Gillett, N. P., Lanzante, J. R., Shine, K. P., and Thorne, P. W. (2011). Stratospheric temperature trends: Our evolving understanding. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 2(4):592–616.
- Seidel, D. J. and Randel, W. J. (2006). Variability and trends in the global tropopause estimated from radiosonde data. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 111(D21).
- Seidel, D. J., Ross, R. J., Angell, J. K., and Reid, G. C. (2001). Climatological characteristics of the tropical tropopause as revealed by radiosondes. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 106(D8):7857–7878.
- Shangguan, M. and Wang, W. (2022). The semi-annual oscillation (sao) in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (utls). *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(14):9499–9511.
- Shangguan, M., Wang, W., and Jin, S. (2019). Variability of temperature and ozone in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere from multi-satellite observations and reanalysis data. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 19(10):6659–6679.
- Shea, D. J., Van Loon, H., and Hurrell, J. W. (1995). The tropical-subtropical semi-annual oscillation in the upper troposphere. *International journal of climatology*, 15(9):975–983.
- SHI, C.-H., ZHENG, B., CHEN, Y.-J., and BI, Y. (2009). The quasi-biennial oscillation of water vapor in tropic stratosphere. *Chinese Journal of Geophysics*, 52(10):2428–2435.
- Shimizu, A. and Tsuda, T. (1997). Characteristics of kelvin waves and gravity waves observed with radiosondes over indonesia. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 102(D22):26159–26171.
- Shimizu, A. and Tsuda, T. (2000). Variations in tropical tropopause observed with radiosondes in indonesia. *Geophysical research letters*, 27(16):2541–2544.
- Shindell, D. T., Miller, R. L., Schmidt, G. A., and Pandolfo, L. (1999). Simulation of recent northern winter climate trends by greenhouse-gas forcing. *Nature*, 399(6735):452–455.
- Shiotani, M. and Horinouchi, T. (1993). Kelvin wave activity and the quasi-biennial oscillation in the equatorial lower stratosphere. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 71(1):175–182.

- Sinha, A. and Harries, J. E. (1995). Water vapour and greenhouse trapping: The role of far infrared absorption. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 22(16):2147–2150.
- Sivakumar, V., Bencherif, H., Bègue, N., and Thompson, A. M. (2011). Tropopause characteristics and variability from 11 yr of shadoz observations in the southern tropics and subtropics. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 50(7):1403–1416.
- Smith, E. K. and Weintraub, S. (1953). The constants in the equation for atmospheric refractive index at radio frequencies. *Proceedings of the IRE*, 41(8):1035–1037.
- Solomon, S., Rosenlof, K. H., Portmann, R. W., Daniel, J. S., Davis, S. M., Sanford, T. J., and Plattner, G.-K. (2010). Contributions of stratospheric water vapor to decadal changes in the rate of global warming. *science*, 327(5970):1219–1223.
- Son, S.-W., Tandon, N. F., and Polvani, L. M. (2011). The fine-scale structure of the global tropopause derived from cosmic gps radio occultation measurements. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 116(D20).
- Sridharan, S., Tsuda, T., Nakamura, T., Kozu, T., Mori, S., and Russell, J. M. (2006). Observations of the 7-day kelvin wave in the tropical atmosphere during the cpea campaign. *J*, 84:259–275.
- Strahan, S. E. and Douglass, A. R. (2018). Decline in antarctic ozone depletion and lower stratospheric chlorine determined from aura microwave limb sounder observations. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 45(1):382–390.
- Suzuki, J., Shiotani, M., and Nishi, N. (2010). Lifetime and longitudinal variability of equatorial kelvin waves around the tropical tropopause region. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 115(D3).
- Tian, B., Manning, E., Fetzer, E., Olsen, E., Wong, S., Susskind, J., and Iredell, L. (2013). Airs/amsu/hsb version 6 level 3 product user guide. *Jet Propulsion Laboratory, Pasadena, CA), Tech Rep*.
- Tindall, J., Thuburn, J., and Highwood, E. (2006). Equatorial waves in the lower stratosphere. i: A novel detection method. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society: A journal of the atmospheric sciences, applied meteorology and physical oceanography*, 132(614):177–194.
- TJ, D. (1995). Horizontal buoyancy flux of internal gravity waves in vertical shear. *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 73(3):747–755.

- Toniazzo, T. and Scaife, A. A. (2006). The influence of enso on winter north atlantic climate. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 33(24).
- Trickl, T., Feldmann, H., Kanter, H.-J., Scheel, H.-E., Sprenger, M., Stohl, A., and Wernli, H. (2010). Forecasted deep stratospheric intrusions over central europe: case studies and climatologies. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 10(2):499–524.
- Tsai, H.-F., Tsuda, T., Hajj, G. A., Wickert, J., and Aoyama, Y. (2004). Equatorial kelvin waves observed with gps occultation measurements (champ and sac-c). *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II*, 82(1B):397–406.
- Tsuda, T., Murayama, Y., Wiryosumarto, H., Harijono, S. W. B., and Kato, S. (1994). Radiosonde observations of equatorial atmosphere dynamics over indonesia: 1. equatorial waves and diurnal tides. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 99(D5):10491–10505.
- Tsuda, T., Nishida, M., Rocken, C., and Ware, R. H. (2000). A global morphology of gravity wave activity in the stratosphere revealed by the gps occultation data (gps/met). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 105(D6):7257–7273.
- Van Loon, H. (1967). The half-yearly oscillations in middle and high southern latitudes and the coreless winter. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 24(5):472–486.
- vAN LooN, H. and Jenne, R. L. (1969). The half-yearly oscillations in the tropics of the southern hemisphere. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 26(2):218–232.
- VanderPlas, J. T. (2018). Understanding the lomb–scargle periodogram. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 236(1):16.
- Vincent, R. A. and Joan Alexander, M. (2000). Gravity waves in the tropical lower stratosphere: An observational study of seasonal and interannual variability. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 105(D14):17971–17982.
- Wallace, J. M. and Hobbs, P. V. (2006). *Atmospheric science: an introductory survey*, volume 92. Elsevier.
- Wallace, J. M. and Kousky, V. (1968). Observational evidence of kelvin waves in the tropical stratosphere. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 25(5):900–907.
- Wang, B.-R., Liu, X.-Y., and Wang, J.-K. (2013). Assessment of cosmic radio occultation retrieval product using global radiosonde data. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 6(4):1073–1083.

- Wang, J. S., Seidel, D. J., and Free, M. (2012). How well do we know recent climate trends at the tropical tropopause? *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 117(D9).
- Warren, H. P., Emmert, J. T., and Crump, N. A. (2017). Linear forecasting of the f 10.7 proxy for solar activity. *Space Weather*, 15(8):1039–1051.
- Waters, J. W., Froidevaux, L., Harwood, R. S., Jarnot, R. F., Pickett, H. M., Read, W. G., Siegel, P. H., Cofield, R. E., Filipiak, M. J., Flower, D. A., et al. (2006). The earth observing system microwave limb sounder (eos mls) on the aura satellite. *IEEE transactions on geoscience and remote sensing*, 44(5):1075–1092.
- Wheeler, M. and Kiladis, G. N. (1999). Convectively coupled equatorial waves: Analysis of clouds and temperature in the wavenumber–frequency domain. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 56(3):374–399.
- Wheeler, M., Kiladis, G. N., and Webster, P. J. (2000). Large-scale dynamical fields associated with convectively coupled equatorial waves. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 57(5):613–640.
- Wheeler, M. C. and Nguyen, H. (2015). Tropical meteorology and climate— equatorial waves.
- Xian, T. and Homeyer, C. R. (2019). Global tropopause altitudes in radiosondes and reanalyses. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 19(8):5661–5678.
- Yu, D., Xu, X., Luo, J., and Li, J. (2019). On the relationship between gravity waves and tropopause height and temperature over the globe revealed by cosmic radio occultation measurements. *Atmosphere*, 10(2):75.
- Zahn, A., Brenninkmeijer, C., Maiss, M., Scharffe, D., Crutzen, P., Hermann, M., Heintzenberg, J., Wiedensohler, A., Güsten, H., Heinrich, G., et al. (2000). Identification of extratropical two-way troposphere-stratosphere mixing based on caribic measurements of o₃, co, and ultrafine particles. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 105(D1):1527–1535.
- Zhang, L., Han, W., Meehl, G. A., Hu, A., Rosenbloom, N., Shinoda, T., and McPhaden, M. J. (2021). Diverse impacts of the indian ocean dipole on el niño–southern oscillation. *Journal of Climate*, 34(22):9057–9070.
- Zhang, W., Zhao, X., Feng, X., Liu, C., Xiang, N., Li, Z., and Lu, W. (2022). Predicting the daily 10.7-cm solar radio flux using the long short-term memory method. *Universe*, 8(1):30.

- Zhang, Y., Huang, Q., Guo, K., Wang, M., Liao, H., Chou, Y., and He, X. (2024). Tropopause folds over the tibetan plateau and their impact on water vapor in the upper troposphere-lower stratosphere. *Climate Dynamics*, 62(2):1423–1437.
- Zhran, M., Mousa, A., Rabah, M., and Zeidan, Z. (2019). Utility of gnss radio occultation technique for tropopause height investigation over egypt. *NRIAG Journal of Astronomy and Geophysics*, 8(1):45–54.
- Zou, L., Hoffmann, L., Müller, R., and Spang, R. (2023). Variability and trends of the tropical tropopause derived from a 1980–2021 multi-reanalysis assessment. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 11:1177502.